

Therapist Manual for Psilocybin-Assisted Therapy of Treatment-Resistant Major Depression

Developed for the EPIsoDE Trial
Efficacy and Safety of Psilocybin in Treatment-Resistant Major Depression
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List of Abbreviations

5-HTP	5-Hydroxytryptophan
AE	Adverse Event
AHA	American Heart Association
BDNF	Brain-Derived Neurotrophic Factor
BP	Blood Pressure
BPM	Beats per Minute
CFR	Code of Federal Regulations
DBP	Diastolic Blood Pressure
DSM-5	Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders - Fifth Edition
HPPD	Hallucinogen-Persisting Perception Disorder
HR	Heart Rate
MD	Doctor of Medicine
MDD	Major Depressive Disorder
mmHg	Millimeters of Mercury
PhD	Doctor of Philosophy
PI	Principal Investigator
SBP	Systolic Blood Pressure
SOP	Standard Operating Procedures
TRD	Treatment-Resistant Depression

1 Introduction

1.1 Acknowledgments

We developed this therapy manual to be the main clinical guideline for therapists treating patients in the EPIsoDE trial, a phase IIb trial to investigate the efficacy and safety of psilocybin-assisted therapy for patients with treatment-resistant depression (Clinicaltrials.gov identifier: NCT04670081). This study was one of the first clinical trials on psychedelic therapy with psilocybin in Germany since the legal ban of the substance, which followed the United Nations Convention on Psychotropic Substances in 1971.

The creation of this manual has been inspired by, and follows in large parts, the Usona Institute's Manual of Clinical Facilitators for the PSIL201 Phase 2 Study of Psilocybin for Major Depressive Disorder (Version 2.0, not published). We conducted the EPIsoDE study in scientific collaboration with Usona Institute. Our team would like to thank Usona Institute for their invaluable contribution to this manual.

We are also grateful to Jeffrey Guss and the team at New York University (NYU), who provided us with their knowledge and experience on clinical trials with psilocybin to treat end-of-life anxiety and depression, and who provided us with their unpublished manual for a planned study of psilocybin for treatment-resistant depression (TRD).

Finally, we very much appreciate the inspiration and the advice we received from many more researchers and therapists: Franz Vollenweider, Robin von Rotz, Eva Schindowski, Peter Gasser, Anke Röskamp, Katrin Preller, Matthew Johnson, and Rosalind Watts, just to mention a few. Particularly, Matt Johnson's Safety Guidelines for Psychedelic Therapy (Johnson, Richards, & Griffiths, 2008) have been an important source of knowledge and hands-on experience for the creation of this manual.

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1.2 EPIsoDE Study Overview

For a brief overview of the experimental design and the timeline of the EPIsoDE trial, see Figures 1 and 2 below. Further details concerning in- and exclusion criteria, study visits, rating scales etc. are provided in the latest version of the study protocol. It is mandatory for all study personnel to familiarize themselves with the study protocol.

The study design and primary results of the EPIsoDE study have been published in Mertens et al. (2022) and Mertens et al. (2026), respectively.

Figure 1. EPIsoDE Study Flow Chart.

Figure 2. EPIsoDE Study Timeline.

2 Therapists

Therapists play a central role in ensuring patient safety throughout the study. Therapists are responsible for:

1. Optimally preparing each patient to be psychologically and physically safe during his or her dosing session.
2. Monitoring the patient's physical and psychological well-being throughout the dosing session.
3. Supporting the patient throughout the integration sessions following the patient's dosing session and the follow-up period. Each patient will be assigned a lead therapist and a co-therapist. Both lead and co-therapists should develop a supportive relationship and an individual sense of clinical rapport, or therapeutic alliance, with each patient to enhance the patient's ability to fully experience and make use of the dosing session.

2.1 Formal Training Requirements

2.1.1 Lead Therapists

Lead therapists at all study sites will be an appropriately qualified physicians or licensed psychotherapists supervised by the local principal investigator (PI). Both medical and psychological lead therapists will have undergone training in the treatment of TRD.

Specifically, if the lead therapist is a physician, he/she should ideally be trained as:

- Licenced psychiatrist or
- Specialist for Psychosomatic Medicine or
- Medical Doctor in training with at least 2 years of clinical experience in one of the two above-mentioned fields

If the lead therapist is a psychologist, he/she should ideally be trained as:

- Licenced Psychotherapist or
- Psychotherapist in training with at least 1 year of appropriate training in psychotherapy

Caution: A psychologist can only take the lead role if the co-therapist is a physician, or if a physician is available on-site.

2.1.2 Co-Therapists

Co-therapists at all study sites will hold a minimum of a master's degree in psychology that qualifies for the post-graduate psychotherapy training in Germany, an approbation (physician), or approbation (nurse) with a specialization in mental health care and at least two years of clinical experience in this field. Preference will be given to those with experience working in the mental health field and/or prior experience working in clinical research trials, especially with psilocybin.

2.2 Roles and Responsibilities

Certain responsibilities regarding medical and psychological safety fall to the lead therapist to maintain consistency in communication with the patient and with other study personnel. This consistency will aid in minimizing patient risk and ensuring long term integration of the psychedelic experience into the patient's life throughout the study. Please note that if both therapists share the same credentials and level of experience, it is important to identify a lead therapist and co-therapist early in the study for each patient. Once these roles are established, it is important that they remain consistent throughout the patient's treatment.

The lead therapist is primarily responsible for decisions involving handling extreme psychological distress and assisting the study physician – if not the same person – in determining the need for medical or emergency psychiatric assessments. The final decision to notify the study physician and/or local PI or document an adverse event (AE) is the responsibility of the lead therapist during the therapy sessions. The role of the co-therapist in these cases will be to assist the lead therapist in these steps and provide any additional safety and comfort measures needed for the patient. Specific instructions on handling AEs and SAEs and steps for documentation on the part of the investigators are documented in the study protocol and will be taught during a study protocol and therapy manual training.

During study sessions, it may be either the lead therapist or the co-therapist who has the strongest rapport with the patient and who, therefore, is the most appropriate person to initiate supportive gestures or verbal responses according to the patient's perceived needs and/or verbal or physical signals. In general, except when the lead therapist's responsibility is mandated by protocol, the lead therapist and the co-therapist should both act to build trust and rapport with each patient to skillfully and smoothly manage interactions that take place within this study.

2.3 Study Therapist Training

All therapists taking part in this study must partake in in-person trainings. These trainings will cover a variety of topics from this manual and the study protocol to ensure the patients' psychological and physical safety throughout the study. In-person trainings will include items such as:

- Reviewing protocol-specific information
- Themes and characteristics of TRD
- Safety precautions and instructions
- Identifying markers and reporting of adverse events
- Identifying markers and reporting serious adverse events
- Identifying when to call the study physician/local PI/coordinating PI
- Identifying physical and psychological concerns
- Reviewing all content covered in preparatory, dosing, and integration sessions
- Case studies
- Practicing therapeutic behaviours in role-play
- Handling challenging dosing sessions

Along with the in-person trainings, all study staff will receive this manual, the study protocol, and complementary readings.

In-person trainings must be completed by all therapists prior to working in this study. The study personnel, along with the local PI at each study site, are collectively responsible for evaluating the

readiness of lead and co-therapists before they can begin engaging with patients. Therapists will be trained regarding specific responsibilities and mandated requirements. The goal of this training will be to help ensure that therapists will be able to identify adverse events and serious adverse events, and know how to handle psychological distress markers etc., along with protocol specifics for this study.

Study therapists must demonstrate that all assigned written materials have been read with good understanding and likewise that online instructions have been viewed and key points correctly identified and understood. Furthermore, through in-person observation and evaluation, readiness of candidates for the role of therapist will be determined by the PI.

2.4 Therapist Qualities

A dosing session has the potential to bring up sensitive, profound, challenging emotions and insights that may place the patient in a vulnerable emotional state; therefore, it is essential that therapists are able to establish a strong therapeutic alliance with the patient by demonstrating qualities such as: kindness, curiosity, neutrality, empathy, authenticity, openness, compassion, and acceptance from the point of initial contact with the patient through the completion of their time together in the study.

The Seven Attitudes of Mindfulness Practice proposed by Kabat-Zinn (Kabat-Zinn, 2013) highlights important qualities for therapists to continuously practice while working with patients and within their therapist dyad during this study. These qualities are paraphrased below:

- **Non-judging:** Cultivating the stance of being an impartial witness to whatever we are experiencing, breaking out of habitual categorizing and judging experiences which locks us into automatic responses/reactions.
- **Patience:** A type of wisdom, recognizing that, at times, things must unfold at their own pace; letting go of the tendency to be impatient with ourselves, others, our efforts, etc.
- **Beginner's mind:** Coming to each experience as if for the first time; freeing ourselves from preconceptions and biases so that we may see things in a new light and perceive new possibilities.
- **Trust:** Learning to have faith in ourselves and our own intentions, honoring our own feelings, our native wisdom; following our own path, not imitating someone else.
- **Non-Striving:** Non-doing, with the intention of creating space for simply being with what is already here; realizing that, for the purposes of this study, it is helpful not just to have goals, but also to be able to back off from striving and focus on seeing and accepting things as they are, in the moment. Non-striving is a quality used in balance with more active approaches to health and doing so requires expanding of one's view to hold this paradox.
- **Acceptance:** Seeing and accepting things as they really are in the present, which reduces the energy drained by denying, suppressing, or resisting what is already here, thus freeing and focusing our energies for positive change. Acceptance is not to be confused with giving up. On the contrary, acceptance allows us to use our energy to see what is and to face it and work with it honestly and earnestly.
- **Letting go:** Non-attachment, letting go of investment in particular thoughts, feelings and experiences; not elevating one thing while rejecting another, but accepting whatever is here in the moment.

2.5 Therapist Skillsets

Therapist skillsets should include the ability to identify psychological and medical concerns, to sit still or make minimal position changes (potentially for long periods of time), to stay calm and emotionally grounded, to remain neutral and non-judgmental when intense psychological and emotional material emerges from the patient, to think fast and problem-solve, to expect the unexpected while assuming nothing and make sound medical and psychological decisions rapidly. Due to the potential for intense emotional, autobiographical, and existential experiences during the dosing session, it is important that both therapists remain emotionally and physically present for, and supportive of, the patient throughout the entirety of preparatory, dosing, and integration sessions. However, should one therapist need to step out of the room (to use the restroom, or converse with study personnel) one therapist must always remain in the room with a patient. During the dosing session, therapists must be able to provide support through reassurance, therapeutic touch, and by conveying to the patient a sense of security and safety, while simultaneously providing a sense of warmth and compassion.

Therapists must establish their own emotional boundaries and maintain a sense of gentle neutrality in response to the emerging contents of a patient's experience. Therapists should be mindful not to display preference or distaste for certain emotional or existential contents. For example, therapists should not attempt to redirect experiences of anguish or sadness towards more joyous states. The non-directive approach of the Standard Protocol recognizes that prematurely or superficially attempting to alleviate emotionally difficult experiences may cut short an experience, which, if more fully explored, could bring insight, meaning, and value to a person's longer-term path. Indeed, attempts to direct the patient's experience, however well-intended, may hinder more complex psychological and emotional processing mechanisms that are unique to the individual and his or her personal narrative. Apart from regular check-ins, therapists intervene in a patient's experience only when the patient requests assistance or in cases where the patient's or a staff member's safety is deemed to be at risk.

2.6 Therapist Dyad

Studies conducted with psilocybin in both healthy and other patient populations have almost universally employed a male/female dyad of therapists. Given that many patients with TRD have been victimized/traumatized by individuals of one sex or the other, having a representative from both sexes is believed to enhance patients' felt sense of psychological safety during the vulnerable emotional states often induced by psilocybin because there is always a member of the "safer" sex present in the room during the dosing session.

2.7 External Supervision

A supervision by an experienced therapist with expertise in the field of psychedelic-assisted psychotherapy is part of the study conduct to serve the following goals:

- Help maintain a high quality of the therapeutic work
- Minimize adverse therapy reactions in patients
- Identify (negative) reactions towards the lead and/or co-therapist (transfer)
- Identify and solve (negative) reactions of therapists towards the patient (counter-transfer)
- Find new strategies in handling difficult situations
- Give feedback for help solving difficult decisions and ethical dilemmas (e.g. exclusion of a patient)

- Prevent/identify/help reduce compassion fatigue in therapist dyads

The supervision is either planned onsite or as an internet-based video group session. There is a presentation of cases to discuss per session, which are decided for and prepared beforehand. The external supervision is a service of an independent expert therapist.

2.8 Intervision

Additional intervision takes place on a regular basis at both study sites, for the same reasons as the external supervision. Therapist dyads and PIs discuss progress in the therapies, particularly difficult cases and passages.

3 Set and setting

Set and setting have been recognized as important factors in the therapeutic work with psychoactive substances for decades. Previous studies with psilocybin administered for research purposes, but without a consideration of set and setting, engendered a wide range of responses, including panic and episodes of paranoia that were highly distressing to study participants (Griffiths et al., 2011; Griffiths, Richards, McCann, & Jesse, 2006). From these early experiments came an increased appreciation of the importance of designing more optimally supportive conditions under which psilocybin could be safely administered within the research setting. The supportive framework used for this study with a high emphasis on the importance of set and setting was derived from the *Psychedelic Therapy* approach, which covers a single high dose of a psychedelic with psychological support, and was further developed by Stanislav Grof and other researchers (Grof, 1980). This treatment protocol, which we call in the following the *Standard Protocol of Psychedelic Therapy*, has been the main approach used in virtually all psilocybin studies conducted in the modern era since approximately 2000, with only small differences between the individual study protocols.

Set refers to the emotional and cognitive mindset of the patient, along with their behavioural state and any expectations they may bring into the study, prior to psilocybin exposure. Contributing to these factors are current situations in the patient's life as well as the hopes and beliefs the patient holds regarding their dosing session ahead, which he/she knows may be a psychedelic experience.

Setting refers to the physical environment during preparation, dosing, and integration sessions. It is helpful to prepare the room with attention to all aspects of possible sensory perception. When the environment appears safe, welcoming, and pleasant, patients are better able to relax and tune in to key messages and experiences during preparatory, dosing, and integration. Because patients experience therapists as belonging to the larger environment in which the dosing day occurs, therapists are an important part of the study setting and should perceive themselves as such. Because therapists can be influenced by past and current narratives, assumptions, training, and life situations, it is equally important for therapists to have a supportive presence, as expressed through words, tone, body posture, gestures, actions and physical appearance.

Creating an appropriately supportive set and setting includes:

- Building rapport and trusting relationships between the patient, therapists, and all members of the study team.
- Ensuring a familiar, secure, private, safe, and comfortable physical and psychosocial environment for the patient during preparatory and dosing sessions and until debriefing on the following day.

3.1 Set

3.1.1 Psychological Factors in Patients

The patient's current psychological status should be thoroughly assessed during preparatory sessions, including psychiatric and physical symptoms, personal history and various biographical aspects.

Moreover, the current mindset will again be shortly explored at the day prior to the dosing session, including current symptoms, expectations, and fears concerning the session to identify more of the patient's helpful inner resources for the day and potential pitfalls and thereby defining or

consolidating a purpose for the session. Key aspects of safety will again be mentioned - but without focusing too much on risks and potential dangers.

It cannot be overemphasized that the contact prior to the session should focus on positive and helpful aspects of relationship and bonding between the patient and therapists, decreasing potential catastrophic cognitions and expectations in the patients regarding the sessions. At the end of the conversation, therapists should have a comprehensive picture of how the patients thinks and feels when beginning the session to further establish a stable and trustful contact for the session.

3.1.2 Therapists as a Set Factor

The patient-therapist relationship provides a primary – and primal – setting that contains the patient in his/her encounter with psilocybin. The therapists' role consists of helping the patient prepare for the dosing session, providing a quiet meditative presence during the dosing session, debriefing the psilocybin experience, and integrating the experience during integration sessions.

Qualifications and requirements for therapists are detailed in the Therapists section (Section 2). Besides, the formal qualification and the skills provided, therapists' awareness of their role as a factor in set and setting of the psilocybin session is a relevant factor to facilitate the optimal environment for the patient's experience.

Each therapist brings her or his identity, history with depression (or not), with psychedelics (or not), and time spent in relationship with depressed patients. Therapists also carry their own experiences, transferences toward the study, their home institution, transferences between therapists, and between disciplines. All these are part of what therapists bring to the setting. It is valuable for therapists to be mindful of how their life experience affects what they bring into the clinical sessions.

3.2 Setting

3.2.1 Dosing Session Room Setup

The physical setting should consist of an inviting, and private, environment in which the patient feels comfortable and safe to both experience and express themselves. Other psychedelic researchers have used such things as an oriental rug, single rose, Buddha books, icons and a couch. All physical environment factors should aim at enhancing the psychedelic experience through providing a calm and positively stimulating physical framework that allows for unimpeded immersion into the inner processes.

Establishing a safe and therapeutic physical setting and mindset for the patient requires that therapists take an active role in creating an environment that is conducive to the therapeutic psilocybin experience, and which will allow the patient to fully attend to her/his internal experience.

The physical setting should generally be private, free from interruption, with minimal external stimuli. The room itself should be comfortable and, to the extent possible, should avoid an overly clinical feeling. The room can be made more comfortable with the presence of such things as fresh flowers, artwork without strong contextual or religious implications, warm colors and home-like furnishings. The patient should be made aware of all safety measures and equipment in place to respond to the unlikely possibility of a medical complication.

Integral to the physical space is the ability to play music. Besides the physical space, the music provided during the dosing sessions is a central factor shaping the patient's inner experiences during dosing sessions. Choice implications for music selection will be detailed below.

Other necessary parts of the physical setting are medical equipment, including means of readily assessing blood pressure and heart rate, and locked areas for protocol materials and records. Maintaining physical safety includes providing access to treatment for possible reactions to the medicine during or immediately after each treatment session. Most reactions can be dealt with through supportive care. Psychedelic-assisted therapy should be done in a setting where Basic Cardiac Life Support (BCLS) is immediately available and Advanced Cardiac Life Support (ACLS) can be summoned reasonably via the general public emergency system in the unlikely event of an acute medical problem.

During dosing sessions, therapists should ensure the patient's physical safety by providing adequate cautions when the patient ambulates. Therapists should also ensure adequate but not excessive fluid intake (i.e. not more than 3 liters over the course of the dosing session). They may also provide electrolyte-containing beverages or juices. Gaseous beverages and beverages containing added sugar should be avoided.

To deal with blood sugar fluctuations, small snacks such as dried fruits and nuts should be available during the session and be counterchecked concerning possible allergies and patient preferences before the dosing session.

3.2.2 Music

Throughout the development of psychedelic therapy from the 1950s to present day clinical research, the use of music in psilocybin and other psychedelic therapies has been a cornerstone in supporting the emotional, cognitive, and somatosensory effects of the psychedelic experience (Kaelen et al., 2018). Along with the empathic presence and guidance of the therapists, the musical component of the Standard Protocol acts as a container for the patient's experience throughout the dosing session.

Dosing rooms will be equipped with a stereo system for playing music over headphones and speakers. During the main phase of dosing sessions (Section 8.4.3), the patient will usually mostly listen to music over headphones while wearing eyeshades to prevent distraction by external sensory stimulation. Therapists should actively encourage patients to listen to the provided music but should be supportive of patients who prefer not to engage with the music. The request to take off the headphones or mute the music should be granted, but the commencement of music-listening should be suggested after a period of silence. Under no circumstances should the patient be pressed or urged to put on the headphones.

The volume of the music played over headphones and speakers can be regulated independently. Unless therapeutic considerations demand otherwise, the speakers should never be completely muted while the patient is listening over headphones. This way, therapists are hearing what music the patient is being exposed to at any given moment, which will increase their capacity for empathic presence. Furthermore, stimulus continuity is preserved when patients take off the headphones. On occasion, therapists may decide to mute the speakers due to therapeutic considerations (e.g., when the patient asks for a break from the music). As a general rule for such situations, the music should not be stopped or paused but only muted (i.e., allowed to continue playing unheard).

3.2.3 The Music Block System

The music for dosing sessions in the EPIsoDE study is organized in a block system (see Figure 3 below, and Appendix R for the detailed playlists and Spotify Links for illustration; notably: No Spotify playlists were used during conduct of the trial). For each of the four phases of the dosing session's experiential arc after drug administrations (i.e., ascent, peak, descent, and return; see Section 4.4) there are five music blocks with an approximate duration of 1:30 hours each. These blocks have been carefully designed to accommodate the specific requirements of the given phase. The main phase of the dosing session begins when the patient is administered the study drug and lasts approximately 6:00 hours. At the beginning of this phase, the therapists should select which block is going to be played during phase 1. Blocks for phases 2, 3, and 4 should be selected and played after 1:30 hours, 3:00 hours, and 4:30 hours, respectively. Each selection should be noted in the Dosing Session Checklists (Appendix I). To maintain the fit between the music and the experiential arc, only the five blocks that have been designed for the given phase should be selected. For the same reason, the playlist should not be paused or stopped, but only muted when required. To be able to make the block selections based on an intuitive assessment of both the patient's current needs and the musical quality of the available block, therapists should be familiar with the pieces of music and their sequence within each block.

Figure 3. Music block system for dosing sessions.

4 The Psilocybin Experience

The following section reviews information specific to psychedelic experiences occasioned by a high dose of psilocybin, such as the 25 mg dose in the present study.

4.1 Common Acute Effects of Psilocybin

It is important to note that even though comprehensive preparation will be completed with each patient, a broad range of phenomenological and autobiographical content may emerge within the psilocybin experience (Garcia-Romeu & Richards, 2018; Preller & Vollenweider, 2018; Swanson, 2018).

The following is a list of possible acute responses that may occur during the dosing session, including those that may or may not have been recorded in previous studies:

- Alterations in visual or auditory perception (distortions, hallucinations and imagery seen with eyes open or closed, misinterpretation of sounds)
- Altered ability to accurately assess the passing of time (perception that one can alter time and/or that time is slowing down or speeding up)
- Anxiety
- Changes in thought (the experience of thinking speeding up or slowing down)
- Changes in proprioception
- Depersonalization (feeling as if one is "outside oneself")
- Derealization (feeling as if the world is unreal or as if one is "in a dream")
- Dizziness, lightheadedness
- Fatigue
- Impaired concentration
- Inattention
- Mood lability (rapid and sometimes profound changes in mood)
- Nausea
- Chills
- Nervousness
- Panic Response
- Paresthesia (strange bodily sensations or feelings)
- Perceptual alterations (general)
- Prolonged emotionally unpleasant experiences
- Unusual thoughts or feelings about the self or the world
- Physiological effects related to slight sympathetic system activation include pupillary dilation and detectable but moderate increases in blood pressure or heart rate, sometimes only at one point in time during the medication effects.

The perceived effects of high-dose psilocybin typically last approximately 4-6 hours (Brown et al., 2017; Griffiths et al., 2016). The therapeutic approach in this trial emphasizes that whatever occurs within the patient's consciousness during the dosing session can be important for better understanding and overcoming his or her clinical symptoms. Moreover, this mental material can be safely supported and worked with as it emerges and later during the integration sessions that follow the dosing day (see Section 9 on Integration Sessions for details). As such, it is important

that therapists develop familiarity with the phenomenological qualities that can be engendered during a psilocybin experience.

In research studies using psilocybin, some patients occasionally have exhibited paranoid ideation or temporarily lost insight into the experimental situation. Therapists will be trained to identify and respond (if necessary) to the commonly occurring, acute effects of psilocybin in order to be able to support the patient during his/her experience. Because this is a research study, therapists will also receive specific training to identify situations that may qualify as adverse events (AEs) or serious adverse events (SAEs) that mandate specific documentation and reporting to regulatory agencies. See Section 10 for detailed information on safety monitoring, including information on adverse events.

Thus, therapists must be prepared to respond to a wide variety of emotional states and behaviours ranging from fear, silence, and withdrawal to wonder and passionate expression. While preparation is crucial for therapists and patients, preparation does not ensure that either therapists or patient will be able to anticipate the actual content of the psilocybin experience (Richards, 2017). It is appropriate during the preparatory session to explore with the patient the potential for a range of experiences, so that he or she may be better prepared should such experiences manifest during the dosing session. Equally important is the introduction to the patient of the concept of their own capacity to safely navigate through the psychedelic experience, which can be trusted to bring forth the experiences that are most beneficial for their mental health (see Section 7 on preparatory sessions for more details).

In addition to experiencing a variety of psychological themes while under the effects of psilocybin, patients may also experience alterations in some or all their senses. For instance, patients may experience augmented auditory perceptions, changes in proprioceptive awareness, and/or synaesthesia (a crossing-over of different sense perceptions, such as seeing sounds or tasting colours). Patients may also encounter profound, beautiful, strange, and/or frightening images during their dosing session. Some may experience highly symbolic content such as visions of animals, people, entities, and geometric patterns or even sense that they have become one of these entities.

Felt senses which are closely linked to the body, such as tingling sensations, feelings of lightness or heaviness, and nausea may be understood as somatic manifestations of anxiety, emotional pain, and pleasure. Importantly, because a patient's capacity to speak may be altered during a psilocybin session, he or she may not be able to easily name or precisely explain the experience occurring, even if the experience itself is quite detailed. It is important for the therapists to encourage the patient to stay with the experience, and it is for this reason that therapist observations are recorded, and a post-dosing session summary is required from patients.

4.2 Mystical-Type Experiences

In addition to alterations in sensory perceptions that patients may experience during their dosing session, psilocybin-induced mystical-type experiences can occur, and therapists play a crucial role in supporting the patient's own exploration of personal meaning or significance of such an experience. Contemporary studies have examined the frequency and impact of these experiences (Bogenschutz et al., 2015; Griffiths et al., 2006; Johnson et al., 2014; Johnson et al., 2008). In a study conducted at Johns Hopkins University, psilocybin-induced mystical-type experiences were reported by study patients as having provided a sustained and substantial sense of well-being, personal meaning, and spiritual significance for up to 14 months after the administration of psilocybin (Griffiths et al., 2006). Multiple studies have suggested that these types of mystical

experiences predict the long-term beneficial effects of psilocybin on personality, as well as depression and anxiety (Carhart-Harris, Bolstridge, et al., 2016; Griffiths et al., 2016; Ross et al., 2016).

Understanding the characteristics of mystical-type states may help therapists navigate through preparatory, dosing, and integration sessions with greater awareness. Note the term "mystical" within the context of this manual does not connote religious association or adherence but rather encompasses a set of phenomenological or intuitive experiences as defined here in greater detail.

In *Classic Hallucinogens and Mystical Experiences: Phenomenology and Neural Correlates* (Barrett & Griffiths, 2017) "mystical experience" is defined as follows:

"Mystical experiences are not similar to the altered states of consciousness associated with intoxication of many common psychoactive drugs such alcohol or opiates... Nor are mystical experiences necessarily associated with religious experiences... Mystical experiences may be accompanied by spiritual insights, but the mystical experience is not, in and of itself, simply the experience of religious or spiritual insight. Mystical experiences are also not simply an interesting aesthetic and/or euphoric experience, an experience of an archetypal construct, or a psychodynamic or intellectual insight. Mystical experiences are defined as a self-reported experience of unity accompanied by the additional dimensions of experience as outlined by Stace."

Below are characteristics that define a mystical-type experience, as adapted from Walter Stace's *Mysticism and Philosophy* (Griffiths et al., 2016; Pahnke, Kurland, Unger, Savage, & Grof, 1970):

Unity:

- A sense of interconnectedness with the totality of reality and all of existence
- Transcendence of self-identity; ego-dissolution
- An experience of pure awareness
- An inner and/or outer experience of unity that may be experienced as devoid of or containing any and all content

Transcendence of time and space:

- Dissolution of ordinary space-time orientation
- Inundation within an experience of infinite quality that may encompass and/or negate ordinary concepts of both space and time
- A sense that one is beyond the bounds of past, present, and future
- An experience of timelessness

Deeply felt positive mood:

- Feelings of joy, bliss, ecstasy, pleasure, rapture, peace, and tranquillity
- Experiences of kindness, caring, tenderness, and love

Sense of sacredness:

- Feelings of reverence, inspiration, and humility
- A sense of awe, wonderment, holiness, and yearning
- Experiences of a deeply felt sense of meaning

- Profound spiritual connection

Noetic quality:

- Subjective experience of trans-cognitive, intuitive insight into and knowledge of an ultimate truth or the nature of reality
- Experiences of enlightenment

Paradoxicality:

- A sense that contradictory perspectives or realities are concurrently veridical (true or expressing truth) or possible
- Insights that oppose the boundaries of rational thought and concepts

Ineffability:

- A sense that what one is experiencing cannot be defined or translated into words
- A sense that it would be difficult to adequately communicate the experience to someone who has not had a similar experience

While psilocybin-induced mystical states have been associated with long-term improvements in mental, behavioural, and spiritual health (Griffiths et al., 2011; Griffiths, Richards, Johnson, McCann, & Jesse, 2008), potential facets of the experience such as ego-dissolution may lead to periods of psychological, emotional, or spiritual challenge for the patient (see Section 4.3). Though such challenging experiences are often found by the patient to be ultimately beneficial (Carbonaro et al., 2016) it is crucial that these experiences be properly addressed in the preparatory sessions, in real-time during the dosing session if the patient indicates a need for discussion (although therapists in general guide patients to hold off on detailed discussion until post-dosing in order to minimize distraction) as well as through the integration sessions, during which meaning, significance, and applicability to life themes may deepen or shift.

The characteristics described above are inherently challenging to convey didactically, and therapists will find that patients' baseline ability to relate to or comprehend concepts that describe altered states of consciousness or mystical experiences they may encounter during dosing will vary greatly, whereas during integration, the patient may be able to relate more directly to these concepts. Therefore, during preparation, it may be helpful to encourage the patient to reflect upon previously experienced states of deep relaxation, intense emotionality, paradoxicality, etc., that the patient may have had within any context, positive or challenging. Such experiences may be present in a patient's life through contemplative practices such as meditation, through spending time in nature, through sexual intimacy with a partner, through the birth of a child, or through listening to beautiful music. Likewise, difficult experiences such as acute bereavement or trauma can also contain potent traces of intense emotionality, visions, or insight that may help prepare them for their experience with psilocybin. Exploring such meaningful life events for the patient may elicit other relatable examples to enhance preparation.

4.3 Challenging Experiences

While psilocybin may induce experiences of great beauty and joy, it may also, as already mentioned above, manifest challenging content such as difficult emotions, frightening imagery, unsettling thoughts and sensations, and confusing confrontations with paradoxical perceptions. Some authors have profiled potential challenging experiences that may arise in a psilocybin session (Barrett, Bradstreet, Leoutsakos, Johnson, & Griffiths, 2016). These experiences include unpleasant affect (like fear, panic, sadness, depressed mood or anger), cognitions (such as confusion, delusion, paranoia, dissociation, depersonalization, perceived loss of mental sanity, "ego loss"), disturbing perceptual effects (synaesthesia, illusions, hallucinations), and physiological symptoms (nausea, increased heart rate).

It is important that from a psychotherapeutic perspective challenging experiences are not necessarily considered adverse events but may in fact be a functional part of the therapeutic action of psilocybin. Whether or not a challenging experience can have beneficial long-term effects has been proposed to depend on whether or not the patient is able to undergo a learning process that results in a resolution of challenging emotions, memories etc. (Roseman et al., 2019; Wolff et al., 2020). This potentially beneficial aspect of challenging experiences, referred to as *emotional breakthrough*, has been shown to predict positive changes in well-being after psychedelic experiences (Roseman et al., 2019). In contrast, challenging experiences that remain unresolved for prolonged periods of time are potentially associated with subsequent psychological difficulties (Carbonaro et al., 2016). Thus, it is important that therapists remain attentive throughout the entire session to assess whether and when patients may need additional support through a difficult passage of their experience.

Preparatory discussions of potential challenging experiences (Section 7.3.4) are not meant to scare or intimidate the patient but should rather inform and gently prepare the patient for the fact that difficult experiences may emerge during his or her dosing session. Therapists should reiterate that even (and at times, especially) scary and challenging experiences may provide an opportunity for deepening one's self-knowledge and psychological growth, and that should such manifestations emerge, it is beneficial to engage with and explore that content. The patient should also be reminded that he or she will have the support of the therapists and will never be left alone.

4.4 Experiential Arc of Psilocybin Sessions

Although each patient's psychological and sensorial psilocybin experience will vary, listed below is a chronological breakdown of what might be expected with regards to a patient's experience throughout a psilocybin session. The experiential arc can be broken down into five different timeframes, following a structure delineated by Kaelen (Kaelen et al., 2018).

Please note the following information is provided for psilocybin, but it is possible that patients receiving placebo may experience similar phenomena over a time course of similar, shorter or longer duration. Note that time frames provided are estimates, and each patient's experience will be different.

Pre-onset:

The pre-onset phase begins when the patient first enters the dosing session room and lasts until psilocybin ingestion. This introductory period may be accompanied by a sense of anticipation or anxiety, and thus the therapists should provide reassurance through invoking a sense of calm,

relaxation, trust, and comfort through their presence and by attending to the environmental factors within the session room.

Ascent (~ 0 - 1.5 hours):

The phase of ascent begins after the patient has ingested the study drug and is laying prone while the study medication is taking effect. This period may be accompanied by somatic phenomena such as tingling, a sense of lightness, dizziness, chills, or nausea. Feelings of anxiety, fear, and excitement may be present at this time, and as such, therapists provide a sense of calm and relaxation, as well as encouraging the patient's sense of positive curiosity towards the experience.

Peak (~ 1.5 - 3 hours):

This phase of the psilocybin session correlates with the most intense drug effects and may be associated with experiences of emotional confrontation and release, autobiographical insight, intense sensory phenomena, and the potential for profound mystical-type experiences. Patients may experience fluctuating periods of intensity and calm throughout this timeframe, and therapists should be ready to provide additional support as appropriate.

Descent (~ 3 – 4.5 hours):

The descent phase is defined by the gradual decrease in the intensity noted in the peak phase. At this time, patients are likely to be in a state of increased emotional openness and greater reflection and contemplation regarding the contents that have emerged thus far in their experience.

Return (~4.5+ hours):

The return phase of the experience encompasses the patient's return to an ordinary state of consciousness. As the study drug effects begin to wear off, it will be important for the therapists to demonstrate calmness, ease, and reassurance to aid the patient's transition back into an ordinary state of consciousness.

5 The Placebo Experience

The following information refers to the placebo effect and is especially relevant regarding the active placebo conditions in this study (low dose, i.e. 5 mg, psilocybin and 100 mg nicotinamide). However, it should be noted that acute and long-term responses to high doses of psilocybin (see Section 4) are also assumed to be influenced by placebo effects. For an in-depth discussion of the relation between placebo effects and responses to psychedelics, see (Hartogsohn, 2016).

5.1 Nicotinamide

Niacin is also known as nicotinic acid and as Vitamin B3. It is an essential human nutrient typically obtained from the diet. Niacin is converted in the human body into a more soluble molecule, nicotinamide (Minto 2017). Insufficient niacin/nicotinamide can result in skin and mouth lesions, nausea, anemia, headaches, and fatigue. When used as a medication or dietary supplement, niacin is thought to be of primary value for high blood cholesterol.

Niacin has been frequently used as a placebo in studies of psilocybin (e.g. Ross 2016) because, while having no known antidepressant effects, it produces a skin flushing reaction that is expected to increase the likelihood that study patients will not be able to tell whether they have received the active drug or placebo. On the other hand, a strong flushing reaction can be experienced as very unpleasant by study participants. Nicotinamide, compared to niacin, appears to be less associated with flushing effects, which is why nicotinamide was chosen as placebo substance in the present study. It is considered as a very safe control substance at the dose levels used in this trial, as adverse effects such as nausea, vomiting, and signs and symptoms of liver toxicity have only been observed at nicotinamide intakes of at least 3,000 mg/day (Rader et al., 1992).

Still, due to the lack of psychedelic effects, there has been a very high rate of unblinding by study participants and monitors in trials using niacin as placebo, which is why a second control condition with low-dose psilocybin was added in the present study.

5.2 Low-Dose Psilocybin

In a psilocybin dose-finding trial, already the lowest dose of 5 mg compared to placebo produced transient elevation of blood pressure and heart rate, and showed significant psychedelic effects like alterations of vision, mood, thought, perception of time and space etc., as measured by subjective rating scales and observers (Griffiths et al., 2011). Interestingly, in this trial as many as 5.6% of the participants fulfilled the criteria of a "complete" mystical-type experience. We chose the dose of 5 mg as a control condition, because these effects will provide more effective blinding, and lower the rate of self-unblinding of patients and therapists. In a clinical trial with patients showing depressive symptoms, low doses of psilocybin (1 mg/3 mg) were used as controls for this reason, which seemed at least partially successful (Griffiths et al., 2016).

Therapists will expect the mentioned physiological, subjective and observable effects of the low dose condition. If questions about the dosage and/or disappointment due to the lack of a "full experience" should arise, therapists should proceed as stated below (section 5.4).

5.3 The Placebo Effect

The placebo effect has been shown in countless studies to be a real physiological phenomenon that has measurable health benefits across a range of medical and psychiatric conditions (Price, Finniss, & Benedetti, 2008). The placebo effect is generally considered to arise from a combination of factors inherent to the therapeutic relationship between clinician and patient. Such factors include expectations of improvement, trust in the clinician, a feeling of support and caring from the clinician, and the belief that one is taking an active medication. From this perspective, the substance (nicotinamide, but also high or low dose psilocybin) is only a partial determinant the acute effect observed after substance administration. Other key elements include the rapport established between therapists and patients in the preparatory sessions, as well as the emotional support patients receive from therapists during the dosing and subsequent integration sessions.

Placebos are used in clinical trials to help separate direct biological effects of a medication from all the non-specific therapeutic effects of the context in which the medication is delivered (e.g., patient expectation and hope, trust in the clinician, etc.). For the placebo condition to operate optimally in the study of psilocybin it is of paramount importance that therapists do not know whether a patient received high dose (25 mg) or low dose (5 mg) psilocybin, or nicotinamide (100 mg). For this reason, therapists are blinded to what a patient receives. Because therapists do not know what a given patient receives, it is also of utmost importance that they try not to allow any sense of what a patient received have an impact on how they approach the dosing session. All patients should be assumed to have received a high dose of psilocybin and should be treated accordingly. Patients who do not show an altered mental state should not be assumed to have received low dose psilocybin or nicotinamide. Several patients in prior trials have had profound emotional and/or mystical experiences in response to a placebo. A recent study (Olson, Suissa-Rocheleau, Lifshitz, Raz, & Veissiere, 2020) found large inter-individual variability responses to a placebo described to participants as a drug resembling psilocybin: Whereas some participants reported no changes, others showed effects typically associated with moderate or high doses of psilocybin. It is for these reasons that all aspects of the dosing day protocol are identical, regardless of which drug (psilocybin high dose vs. low dose vs. nicotinamide) a patient receives.

5.4 Handling Difficult Situations in Placebo Sessions

It is likely that some patients will ask the therapists before, during or after the dosing session if they have received the high dose, the low dose or the placebo. Therapists should by no means answer these questions in a direct way (e.g., by guessing, concluding, considering patients' behaviour), which could lead to expectancy effects and bias. Importantly, even sessions with the non-effective placebo nicotinamide can be of great value for the patient, due to the psychotherapeutic setting with two therapists present, positive effects of the day-dreaming-like state, exploration of self-related emotions, cognitions and memories, the music experience etc.

Therapists should be prepared that patients might be disappointed during or after the dosing session, once they conclude that they might not have received the high dose. Therapists should validate the disappointment, point to the fact that every patient will receive at least one high dose, and try to lead the discussion to the potentially beneficial effects of the session regardless of the administered drug.

5.5 Blinding Assessment

After the end of the dosing session, patients and therapists rate on visual analogue scales the suspected drug (substance and dose) that the patient has received to assess the efficacy of blinding procedures (Blinding and Music Questionnaire; Appendix N).

6 A Guide for Therapists

6.1 Therapist and Patient Relationship

Several aspects of psilocybin studies increase the likelihood that both therapists and patients will have intense experiences, regardless of whether a patient is randomized to psilocybin or placebo. Given this, it is important that therapists work to build a trusting, open relationship with the patient that will provide maximum opportunity for the patient to allow himself or herself to be as emotionally open as possible to the entire dosing day experience. To accomplish this, therapists can and should work to cultivate a mindset which expresses approachability and helps the patient to feel safe. Early in the preparation process, therapists can express that there will be ample time for the patient and therapists to get to know each other, for questions to be asked, hesitations to be shared, and plans to be made for how to handle new experiences, whether anxiety-producing or wonder-inducing. One of the most important aspects of being a therapist is to exude an assurance to the patient that the full range of his or her experience (outside of certain adverse and severe adverse events) is normal, okay, to-be-expected, and even healthy or helpful. This can be summarized as an authentically non-judgmental stance toward all that arises in the human condition, a mindset that arises through the practices of mindfulness and compassion (both self and other-directed).

Therapists will enhance the quality of therapeutic relationships for this study by entering (or continuing) various practices of self-compassion and self-care as detailed in Section 6.5. Therapists will also find it helpful to be able to convey a range of attitudes from friendly encouragement to sober reassurance or insistence on certain parameters involving safety as needed. Overall, the relationship between therapist and patient should be one of mutuality, authenticity, and healthy clinical boundaries, knowing that this study may call for moments of actual, physically supportive touch even while maintaining clear boundaries to assure psychological and physical safety. This balance is achieved by the therapist demonstrating warm empathy and trustworthiness, as these qualities are crucial to developing a therapeutic alliance (Phelps, 2017).

6.2 Therapist Dyad Dynamics

To cultivate an environment of ease, nurturance, and safety, as well as to promote communication and collaboration throughout the study, it is crucial for the two therapists working together to develop a strong and healthy working relationship. The strength and stability of a dyad's communication serve to support the patient's experience throughout the entirety of his or her participation in the study. Therapists should keep in mind the following as they begin to develop a professional relationship with each other:

- Therapists should take time to get to know each other—they will be spending a significant amount of time during sessions in which strong emotional content may be unfolding.
- Therapists should discuss how they may most effectively work together, and how their personalities and strengths may complement one another in the roles and duties within the structure of the dyad.
- Therapists should provide professional and emotional support to each other throughout the length of the study. The situations and content that may arise for patients throughout their time together may be personally triggering and challenging to integrate into their own values and worldviews. Therapists should take time to debrief with one another after each of the preparatory, dosing, and integration sessions.

- Therapists should make it a priority to maintain emotional well-being and balance within the dyad dynamic. They should be open to regular and constructive feedback, while being mindful to do it in a supportive and professional manner. If issues or tensions arise within a dyad, therapists should address them in an open, honest, and respectful manner.
- If any significant issues or concerns arise between therapists in a dyad that cannot be resolved within the dyad, therapists should speak with the local PI and/or the coordinating PI.

6.3 Rewards of Being a Therapist

Being a therapist in this study exposes one to the struggle and suffering of individuals with depression, as well as the potent nature of psilocybin when administered within the Standard Protocol of psychedelic therapy. Although challenging, this work offers several rewards. Given the amount and type of contact therapists have with the intimate stories, intense emotions and experiences of patients, a profound sense of trust, honour and appreciation often grows out of the work. Therapists may hear that the research experience changed an aspect of a person's life or opened his or her eyes to an entirely new perspective. In fact, the therapist may also grow because of a patient's personal growth or healing. Therapists and study staff often develop a strong sense of contributing to science, and in this case, to research that may lead to better and more widely available treatments for a disease with disabling effects for so many across the globe. The feeling of contributing to a decrease in human suffering and to enhanced connection and health can be a reward in and of itself.

6.4 Challenges of Being a Therapist

As with most potentially rewarding work, there are challenges that accompany the role of therapist. Broadly speaking, because this work is taking place within the context of research, any and all therapeutic relationship building must happen within the bounds of rules and regulations that go beyond even the professional guidelines for clinical staff: strict limits are set as to the type and length of professional contact allowed and as to the predetermined responses that must be enacted when certain circumstances arise. In sum, much effort must be given to following rules and regulations and filling out checklists precisely and consistently.

Unfortunately, after all the preparatory, dosing, and integration sessions, there are no guarantees that patients will see any benefit. In fact, it is possible that some patients may see a worsening of their depression, which can be very disappointing and frustrating not only for the patient but also for research staff who have gotten acquainted with each patient. When a patient who enters screening and preparation later fails to meet inclusion criteria at randomization just before dosing, this can cause extreme disappointment which has an impact on patient and therapist.

While such cases are expected to be in the minority, some patients may have challenging personalities or challenging needs or totally reasonable, and expected feelings of frustration with the study, especially if their depression is not improving. It can be a strain to know how to respond in a supportive manner in such situations. Likewise, challenges do arise between therapists, and while they can be normal and worked out in a healthy fashion, it takes energy and attention to navigate such periods wisely.

A challenge that may arise during the dosing day is the ability to stay present with patients who remain very inward, quiet and/or inactive for much of the session. While the patient's inward experience is desirable, it's helpful if therapists have practiced ahead of time remaining present during long periods of silence and lack of stimulation. Knowing that one can maintain attention

through these periods is quite critical and necessary so that one can be alert to small signs and/or be respectfully present.

On the other hand, the patient may be very active and in need of greater reassurance, whether it is physical touch or verbal communication. A patient may have an experience of seeing the therapist as an object of anger, fear, or any negative transference. In such a case, remember that this process can be healthy and helpful for the patient, and there is no need to take it personally or respond defensively. In a related manner, it can be difficult to tame one's desire to help, to want to fix things for the patient. Thus, it can be hard work to simply allow the patient to have his or her experience the way it unfolds, not stepping in to cut it short or redirect it prematurely.

Finally, there can be emotional work in discontinuing the research relationship. The drive toward human affiliation may trigger a sense of loss for one or the other or both therapist and the patient when it comes time to say goodbye. For this reason, having a closing ceremony or small act to note the significance of the work can be helpful for all. It is also recommended that therapists identify a mentor, an individual, or site staff member not directly involved in the study with whom they can process their experiences and emotions. This helps therapists prevent the accumulation of stress reactions and to begin the next interaction with a patient with a fresh outlook.

Compassion Fatigue is another challenge of this role, which is explored in greater detail in the following section.

6.5 Compassion Fatigue and Therapist Self-Care

Compassion Fatigue is "a state experienced by those helping people in distress; an extreme state of tension and preoccupation with the suffering of those being helped to the degree that it is traumatizing for the helper" (Figley, 1995).

Due to the nature of this work, it is important for all therapists to be mindful of emotional boundaries with patients and the need for regular self-care. Compassion fatigue arises when caretakers have close interpersonal contact with a suffering patient and their emotional boundaries become blurred to the point that the caregiver unconsciously assimilates the distress experienced by the patient (Bush, 2009).

As a therapist, it can be a challenge physically and emotionally to be fully present with a patient for long periods of time. Therapists spend many hours in close contact with patients as they share their medical history, anxieties, dreams, personal life stories, traumas, and discuss a wide variety of psychological content throughout the study. Compassion fatigue may emerge suddenly, and it can affect one's physical, emotional, and social health and overall well-being.

Therefore, it is important that therapists be mindful of practicing self-care activities throughout the study. This work should include processing their own emotional responses to working with study patients and fellow therapists (countertransference). This is not only important for an individual therapist to process, but it also helps maintain healthy dynamics within therapist dyads and the ability to fully engage and be present with patients.

The following are some examples of self-care activities:

- Getting adequate sleep
- Maintaining a balanced and healthy diet
- Engaging in daily exercise
- Engaging in de-stressing activities. Some examples include walks in nature, yoga, meditation, guided imagery, breathwork, drawing, dancing, journaling etc.
- Giving oneself enough time before starting a session to gather one's thoughts and ground oneself.
- Taking time after a session to debrief with one's co-therapist

- Identifying the people that are in one's life who can offer support
- Engaging in activities one enjoys (walking with a pet, meeting with friends, cooking etc.)
- Consider partaking in one's own psychotherapy

If at any point a therapist or another study personnel needs any emotional support or resources, please contact the local PI and/or coordinating PI.

7 Preparatory Sessions

7.1 General Aspects

By this point, the patient has completed the screening and provided informed consent. In most cases, and ideally, the patient will already have met one or both of his or her two therapists during the screening visits. In rare cases where this is impossible for organizational reasons, however, the General Prep session will be the patient's first encounter with one or even both therapists. Preparatory sessions will be held 7 days before the first dosing session (General Prep), one day before the first dosing session (Prep 1), and one day before the second dosing session (Prep 2). Both therapists are required to be present in all preparatory sessions.

Before the patient has arrived, therapists should ensure that the session room is well-organized and welcoming. If the dosing room is not available, it should be attempted to make the meeting space as comfortable and aesthetically pleasing as possible.

Please note that communications between therapists and the patient and outside of the preparatory sessions is discouraged. Only if therapists are concerned for the safety of the patient should additional communication occur. This includes informal phone calls and in-person visits, throughout the full duration of the study. All communication must be documented and, if possible, routed through the study coordinator so as not to confound any aspect of the study.

While we have written sample statements for therapists, they are simply a point of reference from which therapists may extract helpful phrases and ideas. Beyond that, therapists are encouraged to draw on their own clinical skills and personal approach when communicating and connecting with patients during preparatory and integration sessions. Nonetheless, we do ask that therapists review, complete, and document all items as they are listed in each session checklist with each patient to help ensure maximal adherence to the protocol.

7.1.1 Goals of Preparatory Sessions

The preparatory sessions serve multiple purposes. A central goal of preparatory sessions is to build trust and rapport between the patient and the therapists. Furthermore, these sessions will provide an opportunity for therapists to become more familiar with the patient's personal background, their life story, and current life situation - especially those aspects that are relevant to the patient's depression. For the patient, these discussions should serve as an invitation to begin an accompanied process of deep therapeutic engagement with these personal topics. Another important goal of preparatory sessions is to prepare the patient for the dosing day in such a way that the safety and efficacy of the treatment are maximized.

Whenever possible, preparatory sessions should be held in the dosing room to familiarize the patient with the room and any equipment in the room before their dosing session. As discussed with the patient during informed consent, all preparatory, dosing and integration sessions will be videotaped. Therapists are responsible to start the recording at the beginning of the session and to save the data at the end of each session. Therapists should recall that empathic listening and an open presence are paramount in creating a safe container for the patient to share personal, sensitive, and emotional information. Throughout this process, it is encouraged that therapists take detailed notes on relevant information given by the patient.

7.2 General Preparation

The General Prep session should have an approximate duration of 100 minutes. Whenever required, therapists may suggest a short break. The following should be covered in this session (see General Prep Checklist; Appendix A):

- Introduce yourselves and give an overview of preparatory sessions (~10 min)
- Discuss topics relevant to the patient's depression (~30-45 min)
- Discuss previous treatments (~10 min)
- Discuss the patient's expectations and hopes regarding treatment with psilocybin (~10-25 min)
- Discuss agreements necessary for study participation (~5 min)
- Hand over patient information on dosing sessions (~10 min)
- Clarify organizational issues (~5 min)
- Close the session (~5 min)

Documents needed for this session:

- General Prep Checklist (Appendix A)
- Print-out of Scheduling Form (Appendix C)
- Session Summary Form (Appendix D)
- Handout – Patient Information on Dosing Sessions (Appendix G)
- Biographical Questionnaire (prepared by the patient; Appendix X)

7.2.1 Introduce Yourselves and Give an Overview of Preparatory Sessions

Before the session begins, the therapist dyad should agree upon which therapist will lead the intake of this discussion. If (only) one of the therapists has already met the patient during screening visits, it is recommended that this therapist should lead the intake and introduces the other therapist to the patient. The opening of the session will derive from the therapists' own way of welcoming new patients into treatment, introducing themselves, and cordially beginning the process of rapport building. This may include questions about experiences in the screening and consenting process, the experience of coming to the sessions, or any way the therapists may choose to make the patient comfortable and welcome.

At the beginning of the session, the position of the video camera should be shown to the patient. Therapists should then review the overall structure of the preparatory sessions.

Sample statements
<ul style="list-style-type: none">● In our first preparatory session today, we want us to get to know you further and you both get to know us even better.● Above all, we want to learn more about your life and your depression.● At the end, we will discuss some organizational things.● In the second preparatory session next week, we will go over typical experiences that are common in dosing sessions and discuss possible ways to deal with challenging or difficult experiences.● Also, we will go through the schedule of the day of the dosing session and answer all your open questions. If you bring a support person next week, we would like to meet them at the end of the session.

Note: Sample statements are meant not as strict defaults but as positive examples of therapist verbalizations in the given situation. Therapists may orient themselves by sample statements but are encouraged to use their own language and therapeutic style of communication for the purpose of authenticity.

7.2.2 Discuss Central Topics Relevant to the Patient's Depression

Based on the information gathered during screening visits and provided by the patient in the Biographical Questionnaire (Appendix Q), which both therapists should have reviewed before opening the session, the therapists will by this point already have an impression of the patient's personal background, their life story, and current life situation. The General Prep session is an opportunity for the therapists to become more familiar with these topics - especially those aspects that are relevant to the patient's depression. However, in contrast to screening visits, the primary goal of the General Prep session is not to gather information but to build trust and rapport. Furthermore, these discussions should serve as an invitation for the patient to begin a therapeutic process of intensive engagement with the personal topics that are relevant to his or her depression. The following topics should be discussed in this section:

- Motivation for study participation
- Depression: Course, symptoms, coping strategies, and patient's explanatory model
- Stressful life events
- Values, interests, and important relationships
- Personality and self-image

As mentioned above, the goal is not to collect a psychiatric history but to listen to the unique story of the patient's depression. The patient is encouraged to speak freely and tell their own stories in an unstructured way. If the patient is unsure of what to say, he or she is invited to describe how his or her depression manifests in everyday life, current support systems and coping strategies. This can include how depression has affected his or her relationships, jobs, and/or the ability to carry out daily tasks, self-esteem, physical health, energy, and core beliefs about the self or the world. If the patient and one or both therapists have already met during screening visits, therapists should pay attention to avoid redundancies in discussed topics and may decide to give less room to topics that have already been discussed. On the other hand, based on their therapeutic judgment, therapists may also decide to revisit topics that have been discussed during screening visits, and address aspects that appear especially relevant more in depth. Generally, the conversational style during preparatory sessions should be more patient-led and more emotionally activating compared to screening visits.

To prepare for this phase of the session, therapists should review the patient's filled-out Biographical Questionnaire (Appendix Q) before starting the session.

Sample statements
Motivation for study participation: How did you come to participate in this study?

Depression (course, symptoms, coping strategies, patient's explanatory model):

- Can you tell us a little about your depression?
- How does depression manifest itself in your daily life?
- How does depression affect the way you interact with other people?
- What symptoms do you observe in yourself?
- How do you deal with the symptoms?
- Which symptoms do you find particularly stressful?
- When did the depression/current depressive episode start?
- When was the last time you felt good for a longer period of time?
- How did depression arise from your point of view?
- Do you have an explanation for why your depression doesn't stop/keeps coming back?

Stressful life events:

- Has/had anything changed in your life before the depression began?
- Have you experienced extremely stressful events in your life? What were these events?
- Do they still feel affected by it today?
- What do you currently perceive as stressful in your life?

Values, interests, and important relationships:

- What is important to you in your life?
- How do you spend your free time?
- Are there people in your life who are particularly important to you?
- Are you in a partnership?
- What kind of job do you have?

Personality and self-image:

- To get a picture of who you are as a person: How would relatives or friends describe you?
- Can you tell us something about your qualities that define you as a person?

Referring to patient answers in the Biographical Questionnaire:

- In the questionnaire you filled out, we read that (...). Would you like to tell us more about it?

Note: Sample statements are meant not as strict defaults but as positive examples of therapist verbalizations in the given situation. Therapists may orient themselves by sample statements but are encouraged to use their own language and therapeutic style of communication for the purpose of authenticity.

7.2.3 Discuss Previous Treatments

Patients in this study are likely to have had several courses of treatment and to have experienced numerous medications, and medication combinations. Exploring past treatments may be of value in understanding the patient's experiences (and disappointments) with previous pharmacological therapies. If the patient has had some experience with psychotherapy, this should also be explored. It will often be useful to ask the patient what he or she thought was helpful and unhelpful about prior pharmacological or psychological therapies. This will provide insights on what type of psychological processes patients have engaged in to better understand themselves and their symptoms. This will also provide information on their experience and comfort reflecting on their histories and current subjective experiences in a clinical setting.

As with the previous section of the General Prep session, the primary goal of this section is not to gather information but to build the relationship between the patient and both therapists and to begin a therapeutic process.

A detailed history of past and current medications will have been collected by research personnel during consenting. However, it is important to remind the patient to disclose all over-the-counter medicines and supplements that they may be taking to designated staff.

Sample statements
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• What forms of treatment have you tried so far?• What experiences have you had with antidepressants?• Have you ever undergone psychotherapy? What experiences have you had with it?• What helped you? What rather not?

Note: Sample statements are meant not as strict defaults but as positive examples of therapist verbalizations in the given situation. Therapists may orient themselves by sample statements but are encouraged to use their own language and therapeutic style of communication for the purpose of authenticity.

7.2.4 Discuss the Patient's Expectations and Hopes Regarding Treatment with Psilocybin

Additionally, this will elucidate how/if they've attached and connected to supportive others, which may give insight into what therapists should expect during their work with the patient. Listening to these details may help therapists better understand the attitude that the patient may have toward the study treatment and how the patient thinks that the study treatment may help him or her. At this point, therapists should also get insight into the patient's expectations and worries regarding the upcoming psilocybin treatment.

Sample statements
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• What are your expectations for the treatment in this study?• What do you hope to gain from the treatment?• Do you have any fears?

Note: Sample statements are meant not as strict defaults but as positive examples of therapist verbalizations in the given situation. Therapists may orient themselves by sample statements but are encouraged to use their own language and therapeutic style of communication for the purpose of authenticity.

7.2.5 Discuss Agreements Necessary for Study Participation

Patients are requested to make three major commitments during the study that were discussed with the patient during the informed consent. Therapists should remind the patient of the agreements at the end of the General Prep session and let the patient confirm his or her consent to these agreements.

1. The patient agrees to remain overnight on-site after ingesting the psilocybin or placebo capsule until all identified study personnel agree that the patient may safely leave the facility the following integration session.
2. The patient agrees to not harm himself or herself or anyone else during the dosing day.
3. The patient agrees to call the study personnel and/or ambulance service if they should experience acute suicidality throughout the duration of the study.

Therapists should ask the patient once again if he or she can adhere to these commitments, with an affirmative statement such as, "I agree". If they feel they cannot commit to these agreements, further discussion is warranted, and he or she may not be a good candidate for this study.

7.2.6 Hand over information on dosing sessions

At this point, therapists should provide the patient with the Handout – Information on Dosing Sessions (Appendix G). This document summarizes instructions, recommendations and further bits of useful information that are not covered in the patient information.

Therapists should briefly go through the first page of the handout (instructions and recommendations for the days before the dosing session) together with the patient and answer any questions the patient may have. Therapists should then ask the patient to read through the whole handout as soon as possible (e.g., on the evening or morning after the General Prep session) in order to prepare for the dosing session. Therapists should inform the patient that the information in the handout will be reviewed in the Prep 1 and Prep 2 sessions.

7.2.7 Clarify organizational issues

Confirmation of support person (if applicable):

If the patient has designated a support person, therapists should confirm the support person's identity with the patient. One therapist should speak with this person prior to the dosing session. Ideally, this meeting will occur in person during the following preparatory session (Prep 1). Therapists should instruct the patient on what will be required of the support person, remind the patient that the support person should accompany them to the following preparatory session. A phone assessment is acceptable but is not optimal and is discouraged. If the conversation happens over the phone, the patient must give written permission.

Confirmation of next session:

Therapists should confirm the appointment for the following preparatory session (Prep 1). A print-out of the completed Scheduling Form (Appendix C) with all remaining appointments should be given to the patient.

Emergency and study staff contact information:

The patient information document given to the patient upon study enrolment includes emergency and study staff contact information. Therapists should remind the patient that their safety is of primary importance, above any data collection or other research-related activities. The patient should be encouraged to call the emergency number in case of any emergency, and to contact the study staff if any organizational issues (e.g., necessity to reschedule an appointment) should arise.

7.2.8 Close the session

Therapists should ask for any additional questions or concerns and say goodbye. After closing the session, therapists are required to submit the Session Summary Form (Appendix D) along with the General Prep Checklist (Appendix A) to the study coordinator.

7.3 Prep 1/Prep 2: Before the First/Second Dosing Session

The Prep 1 and Prep 2 sessions should have an approximate duration of 100 minutes. Whenever required, therapists may suggest a short break. The Prep 2 session held before the second dosing session should be very similar to the Prep 1 session held before the first dosing session. Therapists should keep in mind that the patient may have received either nicotinamide or low-dose psilocybin during their first dosing session. It is therefore important to repeat the education on possible effects of psilocybin and how to handle challenging experiences with the patient. The following should be covered in Prep 1 and Prep 2 sessions (see Prep 1 and 2 Checklist; Appendix E):

- Ask for open questions from the previous session and give an overview of the session structure (~5 min)
- Guided mindfulness exercise (see Appendix F) (~10 min)
- Discuss common experiences in dosing sessions (~10 min)
- Discuss potential for challenging experiences and how to handle them (~20 min)
- Introduce physical space, music, and eyeshades (~5 min)
- Set an intention for the dosing session (~10 min)
- Discuss dosing day structure, instructions, and recommendations (~20 min)
- Meet the support person (if applicable; ~10 min)
- Clarify organizational issues (~5 min)
- Close the session (~5 min)

Documents needed for this session:

- Print-out of Scheduling Form (Appendix C)
- Session Summary Form (Appendix D)
- Prep 1 and 2 Checklist (Appendix E)
- Instructions for Mindfulness Exercise (Appendix F)
- Handout – Patient Information on Dosing Sessions (Appendix G)

7.3.1 Ask for Open Questions and Give Overview of Session Structure

Before beginning the Prep 1/Prep 2 session, therapists should invite the patient to discuss remaining questions from the previous session. Therapists should then review the overall structure for the Prep 1/Prep 2 session.

Sample statements
<p>Ask for open questions from previous session:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">● Do you have any questions about the things we discussed in the last session?

Give overview of session structure:

- Today's preparatory meeting is about the very concrete preparation for tomorrow's substance meeting. We will walk you through typical experiences that are common in the dosing sessions and also discuss possible ways to deal with challenging or difficult experiences.
- In addition, we will look at the substance meeting room together, discuss the schedule of the day of the dosing session and answer all your open questions.
- If you have brought your support person with you, we would like to get to know them briefly at the end of the session.

Note: Sample statements are meant not as strict defaults but as positive examples of therapist verbalizations in the given situation. Therapists may orient themselves by sample statements but are encouraged to use their own language and therapeutic style of communication for the purpose of authenticity.

7.3.2 Guided Mindfulness Exercise

The Prep 1/Prep 2 session should start with a brief introduction to the concept of mindfulness. To start this conversation, therapists may ask the patient about their own conception of mindfulness and give a brief explanation of what mindfulness means.

The therapist should then explain to the patient that taking a mindful stance during the psilocybin experience is generally considered beneficial. To provide the patient with first-hand experience in mindfulness, one of the therapists should then guide the patient through a standardized mindfulness exercise (see Instructions for Mindfulness Exercise; Appendix F). The therapist should invite the patient to assume a relaxed but upright sitting position and to close the eyes. If the patient prefers keeping the eyes open, the therapist may suggest letting a soft gaze rest on a fixed point in their visual field. When guiding through the exercise, the therapist should use a calm, soft voice, and pay attention not to rush. Afterwards, the therapist should ask the patient about their experience during the exercise. Therapists should remind the patient that being in a mindful state will be helpful during their upcoming experience.

Sample statements

Asking for the patient's concept of mindfulness:

- During the dosing session, it can be very helpful to adopt a mindful attitude.
- Do you know the term mindfulness? What do you mean by that?

Explaining mindfulness in simple terms:

- Mindfulness means consciously perceiving what is happening in the here and now without judgment.
- "What is happening in the here and now" means everything that is somehow perceptible to you: For example, your sensory perceptions, such as the things you can see, sounds, touches, etc. But also things that are going on inside you, such as thoughts, inner images or feelings that are there right now.
- Mindfulness therefore means perceiving all this consciously and without judgment.
- Consciously perceiving means that you observe these things attentively. For example, you observe what you see, smell, taste, etc. You can also observe your thoughts and feelings.
- Perceiving without judgement means that you simply observe things without judging them as good or bad. For example, you observe a feeling in your stomach and instead of saying to yourself "this is a bad feeling" or "this is a good feeling", you simply say to yourself: "There is a feeling."
- Do you have any questions about this?

Introducing the mindfulness exercise:

- To help you familiarize yourself with mindfulness, we have prepared an exercise that we would like to do with you now.

Debriefing after the mindfulness exercise:

- How did you experience the exercise?
- Did you have the feeling that you succeeded in being "mindful"?
- What was difficult for you?

Note: Sample statements are meant not as strict defaults but as positive examples of therapist verbalizations in the given situation. Therapists may orient themselves by sample statements but are encouraged to use their own language and therapeutic style of communication for the purpose of authenticity.

7.3.3 Discuss Common Experiences in Dosing Sessions

Therapists should review common experiences that may occur during dosing sessions with psilocybin and placebo. To clarify the therapeutic relevance of the subjective experience, those effects that might be beneficial from a psychotherapeutic perspective will be emphasized.

However, therapists should not actively suggest or emphasize certain (assumed) therapeutic mechanisms (e.g., emotional breakthrough or mystical experience) to the patient. Importantly, the discussed experiences should not be framed as effects of psilocybin, but as possible (but not necessary) outcomes of the specific set and setting in combination with the study substance (i.e. psilocybin or placebo). Note that patients have been thoroughly informed about effects of psilocybin previous to preparatory sessions.

Sample statements

Asking for the patient's expectations:

- As has already been discussed in detail in the consultation with you, you will receive either 25 mg psilocybin, 5 mg psilocybin or a placebo in tomorrow's dosing session. You will then listen to specially selected music lying down for a longer period. You have your eyes closed and focus your attention on your inner experience for several hours.
- Regardless of what substance you receive, this particular situation can cause you to have an extraordinary experience.
- Do you already have a certain idea of what such an experience could look like?

Emphasizing the individuality of the experience:

- The way in which each individual person experiences this and what insights they draw from it is very individual. So there is no "guarantee" for a particular experience.

Addressing common effects (emphasis on potential therapeutic effects):

I would like to give you a few examples of the types of experiences that this therapy often evokes. These experiences can be very important therapeutically.

- Feelings are often felt more strongly than in everyday life. It can also happen that you feel feelings that you otherwise don't really know in your life.
- The strong feelings can also occur together with images or memories from the past that arise in you as if you were reliving them, e.g. as a child or as a young woman/young man. It may happen that you then understand these memories from a new perspective.
- Sometimes this is very pleasant, e.g. redeeming or joyful, and sometimes this is unpleasant, e.g. Fears, anger, grief or shame come up, which we often avoid in normal everyday life.
- Your body experience can also change greatly, so that you have the impression that you are experiencing inner processes such as blockages, tension or pain in the body more consciously.
- It can happen that your view of yourself and the world changes. One experience you might have is that you "discover" something about yourself or the world that is completely unexpected. For example, it can happen that you suddenly see a certain problem in a completely new light.
- Your perception of us can also change, so that you no longer perceive us only as therapists, but we remind you strongly of other people, for example.
- Other things that you otherwise take for granted can also change, e.g. it can feel as if the boundaries of your body are dissolving, or as if time and space are changing.
- It can also happen that profound and challenging topics arise, e.g. the topic of death, religion or spirituality, even if you do not otherwise experience yourself as a religious or spiritual person.
- None of this *has to* occur in your experience tomorrow – these are all just possibilities for experiences that can occur.
- Do you have any questions about this?

Note: Sample statements are meant not as strict defaults but as positive examples of therapist verbalizations in the given situation. Therapists may orient themselves by sample statements but are encouraged to use their own language and therapeutic style of communication for the purpose of authenticity.

7.3.4 Discuss Potential Challenging Experiences and How to Handle Them

It is crucial that therapists take enough time to discuss potentially frightening and disturbing experiences. As discussed above (Section 4.3), challenging experiences are very common in psychedelic therapy. It is important for therapists and patients to understand that, from a psychotherapeutic point of view, challenging experiences are *not necessarily* considered adverse events, but should be understood as an opportunity for overcoming psychological conflicts, gaining self-knowledge, and finding new, healthier ways of relating to one's experience. Therapists should accommodate this by using the term "challenging experience", while avoiding terms such as "negative" or "bad" when describing these experiences. It may be appropriate at this point to work with suitable metaphors (see sample statements below), and to mention to the patient that they will be taught methods that can be used to deal with challenging experiences during the dosing session. The discussion of challenging experiences is not meant to intimidate patients. On the contrary, it is a practice specifically designed to enhance the patient's self-efficacy and confidence regarding their ability to cope with the uncertainties associated with the upcoming dosing session. It should be communicated to the patients that whenever challenging experiences arise during the dosing session; therapists will be available for support.

Sample statements
<p>Summarizing potential experiences:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The noticeable effects during the dosing session, as I said, can be very different. Strong feelings, images, thoughts, physical sensations or memories may arise. • It is possible that you will have pleasant and sometimes unpleasant, challenging experiences with it.
<p>Fostering positive attitudes towards challenging experiences:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The important thing about everything you experience is trust in the process. Often, the challenging experiences are a very important part of therapy and their personal development. • We recommend that you be open to any content. Consider challenging experiences as an opportunity for your personal development and an opportunity to make therapeutic progress. • Experience shows that in the dosing session, exactly what is important and bearable for you at that moment usually comes up. • If you're having a challenging experience, don't try to escape it – we recommend the opposite: go there, dive deeper, go with it. Get involved in everything that comes, be open and curious.
<p>Introducing a journey metaphor (sailboat):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The experience is comparable to a trip where you don't know in advance what you will encounter. But if you get into a storm on a sailing ship, for example, then it's better to accept the storm, haul in the sails, rather than steer against it - until you come out the other side. Then you have certainly learned something from this experience and have become stronger. • Some people are helped by the image that every person has a kind of "inner compass" that they can trust and follow.
<p>Introducing a journey metaphor (theme park):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The experience is comparable to a ride in a gondola through a theme park. When you get in, you don't know where the gondola will go and what you'll see. It may be that you have pleasant and beautiful views, but it may also be that the gondola goes through the ghost train. • Even if it doesn't look pleasant there, you are always safe in your gondola. They can sit back, perceive and observe. At the end, the gondola always comes out of the ghost train.
<p>Emphasizing physical safety and the transient nature of the experience:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The acute psychological effects of psilocybin can be very intense. However, as you know, the risk of severe physical side effects is extremely low, and the effect of the substance automatically wears off over time.
<p>Emphasizing support by therapists:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • We will be with you all the time and support you. We are familiar with such situations.

Note: Sample statements are meant not as strict defaults but as positive examples of therapist verbalizations in the given situation. Therapists may orient themselves by sample statements but are encouraged to use their own language and therapeutic style of communication for the purpose of authenticity.

7.3.4.1 Patient-led Techniques

Therapists should talk to the patient about specific patient-led techniques that he/she may use during dosing sessions to handle challenging experiences. These techniques are meant to bring the patient back into the moment-to-moment reality of bodily experience, promoting relaxation, awareness, and acceptance of the present moment. They may aid the patient in learning how to manage and transform challenging situations into opportunities for psychological growth and gaining self-knowledge.

For increased accessibility of patient-led techniques during dosing sessions, therapists and patient may agree upon a limited set of short cues that therapist may use to prompt patient-led techniques when needed (e.g., "perceive and observe" as a cue for mindfulness; "go deeper" as a cue for "leaning into" the experience).

Sample statement
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Now we would like to show you some techniques that you can use before, after and especially during the dosing session. They should serve to deal with challenging experiences, to be able to take something away from them, or, in the best case, to grow from them. • We will be present the whole time to guide you if necessary.

Note: Sample statements are meant not as strict defaults but as positive examples of therapist verbalizations in the given situation. Therapists may orient themselves by sample statements but are encouraged to use their own language and therapeutic style of communication for the purpose of authenticity.

Mindfulness:

Therapists should remind the patient that assuming a mindful state, i.e. bringing attention to one's ongoing experience without judging it, is generally considered beneficial during the psilocybin experience. During challenging experiences, the patient may choose to observe the experience rather than reacting to it.

"Leaning into" the experience:

Therapists should remind the patient that challenging experiences may provide an opportunity for psychological growth and gaining self-knowledge. When a patient encounters challenging moments, the recommended approach is to confront frightening aspects of the experience rather than trying to avoid, suppress, or seeking distraction from them. To convey this as comprehensibly as possible, therapists may use figurative language, e.g., encourage the patient to "lean into", "move/turn towards", or "open up to" the experience rather than trying to "push it away", "move/run/turn away", or "get out of it". To motivate the patient to apply this technique, therapists should underscore the opportunity for growth and self-knowledge inherent in challenging experiences. A more detailed discussion of the concept of engagement with (versus disengagement from) challenging aspects of psychedelic experiences and related recommendations for therapists is provided in Section 8.4.3.2 (Guidelines for Handling Psychological Distress).

Removal of eyeshades and/or headphones:

If the patient becomes overwhelmed by his or her inner experience, it may be of benefit to remove the eyeshades and/or headphones in order to re-center and relax.

Sample statements
<p>Mindfulness:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • As already discussed, a mindful attitude is recommended during the dosing session. • We advise you, especially during difficult phases, to observe the experience consciously and without judgment. Don't judge, just observe what you're experiencing.
<p>Short phrases:</p>

- During the dosing session, we will sometimes only use short sentences and instructions so that you can understand them well even in altered states of consciousness.
- For example, I may say "perceive and observe" to you to remind you to adopt a mindful attitude.

"Leaning into" the experience:

- A very important technique in dealing with challenging experiences is to consciously go even further into the experience.
- Whenever you experience something that scares you, try to turn to it. This going into the experience makes the experience much more bearable than if you are trying to escape the experience somehow.
- If you encounter something you're afraid of, try to be curious and open anyway. Don't run away from it, go there. Ask, "What are you doing here? What can I learn from you?"
- If you feel like you're melting, dissolving, or exploding, don't fight it, let it happen. Melt, dissolve, explode! We will always be with you and ensure your safety.
- During the dosing session, we will sometimes use only short sentences and instructions so that you can understand them well even in altered states of consciousness. For example, I may say to you "go deeper" to remind you to go deeper into the experience.

Removal of eyeshades and/or headphones:

- If at any point the experience becomes too overwhelming for you, you have the option to remove the headphones and blindfold. This can help to anchor oneself in the here and now.

Note: Sample statements are meant not as strict defaults but as positive examples of therapist verbalizations in the given situation. Therapists may orient themselves by sample statements but are encouraged to use their own language and therapeutic style of communication for the purpose of authenticity.

7.3.4.2 Therapist-led techniques

After introducing patient-led techniques, therapists should explain to the patient those therapist-led techniques for handling challenging experiences that require some kind of interaction between therapists and the patient. Note that Section 8.4.3.2 below (Guidelines for Handling Psychological Distress) discusses therapist-led techniques more in detail, introduces the important concepts of engagement versus disengagement and self-efficacy versus support, and provides additional recommendations for therapists. These topics are not covered in the present section, which focuses on informing and preparing the patient for therapist-led techniques rather than explaining their application.

Reassurance:

Therapists should remind the patient that if he or she should need additional assistance, therapists will be there to support them, and that the patient will never be left alone. If patients should experience perceptions of dissolving, warping, disappearing and melting, to the point that they may feel as if they are dying, therapists may reassure them that their physical body is safe and will continue to function. Therapists may also remind the patient by that they have taken psilocybin (which the patient may have forgotten), that they are participating in a study, and that the effects of the psilocybin are time-limited and will wear off. They can remind the patient that while the psychological and somatic effects may feel extreme and real, the physical risks of ingesting psilocybin remain extremely low.

Physical touch, including boundary agreements:

Therapeutic touch consists of a gentle and reassuring touch through holding the patient's hand or placing one's hand on the patient's shoulder. At absolutely no time throughout the course of this

study there should be any sexual touch or unsolicited physical contact between therapists and the patient. Any form of therapeutic touch should be agreed upon, discussed and practiced prior to the dosing session. If this is felt by the patient to be sub-optimal, therapists can work with the patient to identify a manner of touch he/she would find most comfortable. It is important to discuss with patients the topic of therapeutic touch and physical boundaries. This topic is important for both therapists to address and agree upon with the patient, as a patient may have a history of sexual trauma or abuse with one gender. This may come up during a session, and it is something to be sensitive and aware of. Therapists should agree upon what type of therapeutic touch the patient prefers, and to reassure the patient that clear sexual boundaries will be held. For this information to be available in dosing sessions, it is crucial that therapists note the boundary agreement in the session checklist (Appendix E) and the Session Summary Form (Appendix D).

Breathing exercises:

Therapists may encourage the patient to focus attention on inhalation and exhalation of the breath, and to rest in the awareness that he or she is breathing, alive, and present. If the patient is experiencing discomforting emotions, imagery, or somatic sensations, they may benefit from "breathing into" that physical space, emotion, or image.

Encouraging the patient to use patient-led techniques:

Since the patient may have difficulties remembering and/or trusting in the patient-led techniques discussed above (Section 7.3.4.1). Hence, therapists may at any point remind the patient of the patient-led techniques discussed above (e.g. leaning into the experience) and encourage their use.

Rescue medication:

Tell the patient that in the unlikely case that the study physician determines that a patient's symptoms qualify as psychosis and not an expected part of the psilocybin experience, safety medications such as an oral benzodiazepine will be available for on-site acute anxiety (e.g., oral lorazepam), and an oral anti-psychotic will be available for on-site antipsychotic treatment (e.g., oral risperidone). Explain to the patient that the necessity to prescribe any rescue medication is always assessed by the study physician. For the most part, using any rescue medication will be a joint decision of the study physician and patient. However, in the case of an unresolvable difference of opinion, the patient must accept the clinical judgement of the study physician.

Sample statements
<p>Introducing therapist-led techniques:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In addition to the techniques discussed earlier that you can use on your own, there are other techniques that we as therapists can use to help you through challenging experiences if necessary. • The two of us will be with you all the time. If you need our support, simply signal this, e.g. by saying something or raising your hand. However, we will also regularly inquire about your condition on our own.
<p>Reassurance:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In most cases, we would just talk to each other briefly. For example, we can encourage you or remind you that you are safe and that the experience will pass. We are well versed in such situations and can easily assess what you need at the moment.

Physical touch, including boundary agreements:

- Holding a hand or a light touch on the shoulder can help you feel safer and accompanied in challenging situations. Therefore, we would like to make an agreement with you on what types of touch are okay for you.

Encouraging the patient to use patient-led techniques:

- We can also encourage and support you in using your own techniques, e.g. mindfulness or going into the experience.

Breathing exercises:

- Certain breathing exercises can also help to calm down. If it seems sensible to us, we can guide you to let the breath flow, observe it or even "breathe into" a certain part of the body or a certain feeling.

Rescue medication:

- In the extremely unlikely event that you develop extreme anxiety or even psychosis under the substance, which cannot be regulated by psychotherapeutic interventions, emergency medication is also available, as you know, i.e. benzodiazepines and antipsychotics.
- Of course, these medications are only administered in an emergency on the basis of the assessment of the study doctor and in consultation with you.

Note: Sample statements are meant not as strict defaults but as positive examples of therapist verbalizations in the given situation. Therapists may orient themselves by sample statements but are encouraged to use their own language and therapeutic style of communication for the purpose of authenticity.

7.3.5 Introduce Physical Space, Music, and Eyeshades

Therapists will give the patient an opportunity to adjust and try on the eyeshades that will be used in the dosing session, as well as listening to a few minutes of the music playlist. At the same time, the patient will be given an opportunity to recline on the bed they will use during the actual dosing session.

7.3.6 Set an Intention for the Dosing Session

Encouraging the patient to set an intention for their participation in the study and for the dosing session can serve several purposes. First, an intention can help focus the patient's attention on what type of change he or she is seeking, if relevant in relation to their depression. Second, if the patient encounters challenges along the way, the intention can serve as a mental reminder of a deeper purpose or desire. If the patient encounters psychological challenges during the dosing session, the intention can serve as an anchor that reminds the patient the reason the patient agreed to enrol in the study in the first place. Finally, an intention is often remembered well beyond the dosing session itself and therefore may serve as a tool for extending any psychological insights or emotional/cognitive gains the patient may have made during and immediately after the dosing session.

Therapists should encourage the patient to come back to this intention at any time. He or she might also explain that the intention may shift or be deepened or changed in some way as the experience of the dosing session and integration takes place. For many patients it will be important that the therapists delineate an intention from an expectation. An intention is a flexible hope that does not

require the dosing experience to conform to that hope. On the other hand, expectations can produce rigid internal demands that the dosing session unfold in particular ways and resulting disappointment if it does not. Patients should be told that one of the most salient features of dosing day experiences is that they are often felt to occur in ways that cannot be consciously controlled or forced into preconceived expectations.

Intentions that patients set in the context of a psilocybin trial often relate to the problem that brought them into the study, in this case his or her depression. For patients who explicitly name a depression-specific intention, it may be valuable to connect the presenting problem (i.e., depression) to the work a patient identifies as needing to be done to improve his/her condition. Therapists should encourage the patient to come back to his/her intention at any time, while simultaneously remaining open to whatever emerges throughout the study experience. They should also remind the patient that the intention may shift or deepen as the study progresses.

Sample statements
<p>Introducing the concept of an intention</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• At this point, we would like to develop one or two intentions for the dosing session together with you. What changes would you like to see in your depression?• Having a concrete intention can help you to direct your focus during the dosing session and thus support your desired change. At the same time, your intention can serve as a reminder of a desire for change, which can guide you especially during a challenging experience and remind you why you have chosen this treatment.• Do you already have a specific intention for the dosing session?
<p>Managing expectations regarding the intention:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• We recommend that you don't think of the intention as a fixed goal that you absolutely have to achieve. Think of the intention more as a wish, a kind of hope that you can focus on, but that doesn't necessarily have to be fulfilled exactly as you thought. Sometimes this very topic comes up during the experience of substance, but sometimes it doesn't.• Your intentions can also change during the treatment. That's perfectly fine and shows how important it is to go into this experience with an open mind.

Note: Sample statements are meant not as strict defaults but as positive examples of therapist verbalizations in the given situation. Therapists may orient themselves by sample statements but are encouraged to use their own language and therapeutic style of communication for the purpose of authenticity.

7.3.7 Discuss dosing day structure, instructions, and recommendations

Therapists should discuss the structure of the dosing day along with any related instructions and recommendations. This discussion should be guided by the Handout – Patient Information on Dosing Sessions (Appendix G), which has been given to the patient at the end of the General Prep session. All information in this handout must be reviewed with the patient prior to the dosing session, and therapists should answer open questions by the patient.

7.3.8 Meet the support person (if applicable)

At the end of the Prep 1/Prep 2 session, at least one of the therapists should meet the support person chosen by the patient, if applicable. It is important that this step is repeated in the Prep 2 session if the patient has designated a different support person in the meantime.

The support person may have questions related to the study drug (psilocybin/nicotinamide) or the study procedures. This is a valuable opportunity to confirm that this person is supportive of the patient's involvement in the trial. Therapists should reconfirm that both the patient and the support person have the study personnel's contact information.

7.3.9 Clarify organizational issues

Confirmation of next session:

Therapists should confirm the appointment for the dosing session. A print-out of the completed Scheduling Form (Appendix C) with all remaining appointments should be given to the patient.

Emergency and study staff contact information:

The patient information document given to the patient upon study enrolment includes emergency and study staff contact information. Therapists should remind the patient that their safety is considered to be of primary importance, above any data collection or other research-related activities. The patient should be encouraged to call the emergency number in case of any emergency, and to contact the study staff if any organizational issues (e.g., necessity to reschedule an appointment) should arise.

7.3.10 Close the session

Therapists should confirm the date and time of the dosing day. Ask if there are any additional questions or concerns and close the session. After closing the session, therapists are required to submit the Session Summary Form (Appendix D) along with the Prep 1 Checklist (Appendix E) to the study coordinator.

8 Dosing Sessions

Dosing sessions are the centrepiece of treatment in this study. Each patient will generally undergo two dosing sessions at an interval of 6 weeks.

In the first dosing session, the patient will receive either a high dose (25 mg) or a low dose (5 mg) of psilocybin, or the active placebo nicotinamide (100 mg).

If the patient had a high dose in the first session, he or she will receive either a low dose of psilocybin, or another high dose of psilocybin in the second session. Patients who received low dose psilocybin or nicotinamide in the first session will be administered a high dose psilocybin.

Neither the patient nor therapists will know which drug the patient receives for a given dosing session. As explained in Section 5.3 (The Placebo Effect), it is also of utmost importance that therapists do not allow any supposition on which drug a patient received to influence their behaviour during the dosing session. All patients should be assumed to have received high dose psilocybin and should be treated accordingly. Dosing sessions follow a highly standardized structure (Section 8.1) and put high requirements on therapists (Section 8.2). Therapists should adhere to the Dosing Session Checklists (Appendix I) throughout the dosing day.

Documents needed for dosing sessions:

- Session Summary Form (Appendix D)
- Dosing Session Checklist (Appendix I)
- Dosing Session Monitoring Form (Appendix J)
- AHA Cuff Size Recommendations (Appendix K)
- Cardiovascular Monitoring Instructions (Appendix L)
- Cardiovascular Monitoring Form (Appendix M)
- Blinding and Music Questionnaire (Appendix N)

8.1 Structure of the Dosing Day

Procedure	Time	Provider
Patient arrival, assessments	08:30 – 09:00	Study personnel
Urine tests (drugs of abuse/pregnancy), breathalyzer test (alcohol), vital sign	09:00 – 09:30	Study personnel
Preparations of dosing room, medication etc.	09:00 – 09:30	Lead and co-therapist
Settling in	09:30 – 10:00	Lead and co-therapist
Main phase of dosing session	10:00 – 16:00	Lead and co-therapist
Cardiovascular monitoring	30, 60, 90 minutes and 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8 hours after drug administration	Lead or co-therapist
Blood samples for plasma levels of psilocin at 2:00 and 3:00 hours post dose (butterfly needle)	2 and 3 hours after drug administration	Study physician
End of dosing session Debriefing Going for a gentle walk (optional) Questionnaires on acute experience	16:00 – 18:00	Lead and co-therapist

Evaluating the patient for transfer to overnight stay room	18:00 – 18:30	Lead therapist and study physician
Transfer to overnight stay room	18:30 – 19:00	Study personnel Night monitor
Dinner, support person can visit until 21:30 at the latest	19:00 – 21:30	Night monitor
Overnight stay at the study site	21:30 –	Night monitor Study physician (on-call)

8.2 Role of Therapists during Dosing Sessions

The therapists' primary role is to monitor the safety of the patient while supporting whatever psychological material arises during the patient's dosing session.

For most of the dosing session, both therapists will attend to the patient, and at least one therapist will always be present in the session room to continuously observe and evaluate the patient's physical and mental status. Should a therapist need to leave the session room, it will only be for a brief period (such as to use the bathroom or speak with study personnel). Continuous supervision provides a safety structure and ensures that the patient will receive ample reassurance and emotional support from the therapists should he/she experience strong emotions or become anxious or agitated during the session.

Throughout the session, therapists will ensure the study patient is safe and comfortable. They may check in with the patient with a verbal inquiry ("*How are you doing?*") or by putting a hand on his or her shoulder or arm. The patient has been made aware that this might happen periodically during the session and should have given permission for touch during preparatory sessions. Therapists and the patient should have discussed any physical touch, boundaries or preferences (placement of a hand on the hand or shoulder) before the dosing day.

As possible interventions, therapists may mute the music (in order to maintain the fit between music and the experiential arc, the music playlist should never be stopped or paused; see Section 3.2.2), adjust lighting or room temperature, get a glass of water or a blanket for the patient, and/or assist the patient to the bathroom. As the effects of psilocybin may alter patients' sense of balance and coordination, all patients must be escorted to the bathroom by study personnel of the same sex. Bathroom doors will remain unlocked and study personnel must remain outside of the bathroom until the patient is ready to be escorted back to the session room.

Light snacks, water or juice will be provided to the patient throughout the day. The patient is encouraged to reach out to the therapists if he or she should find themselves needing assistance during the session.

If the patient expresses emotional distress, therapists may draw upon their clinical skills and the techniques for handling challenging experiences which they have discussed with the patient in preparatory sessions. Specific guidelines for handling psychological distress are summarized in Section 8.4.3.2 below.

8.2.1 Specific Symptom and Safety Monitoring

Specific symptom assessment and safety monitoring will be achieved through the Dosing Session Monitoring Form (Appendix J), which assesses the occurrences of adverse events (AEs) throughout the dosing session. While these events are unlikely, it provides therapists the ability to monitor symptoms and communicate any observed symptoms to the study physician, who will determine

whether immediate clinical assessment is warranted. Additional information on safety monitoring is provided in Section 10 (Safety Monitoring).

8.2.2 Cardiovascular Monitoring during the Dosing Session

In published studies to date, the most common physical effects of psilocybin were transient elevations in BP and HR. To date, these elevations have rarely required medical intervention and were resolved by the end of the dosing session.

For safety monitoring purposes, heart rate and blood pressure will be taken at the following intervals during the dosing session: 30, 60, 90 minutes, 2, 4, 6, 7 and 8 hours after drug administration. Measurements will be conducted by trained study personnel. Blood pressure measurements should occur after the patient has been recumbent a minimum of 10 minutes.

Please refer to the Cardiovascular Monitoring Instructions (Appendix L). All therapists will be trained in-person to measure blood pressure and heart rate, and to assess when additional measurement or medication is required for safety purposes. Therapists should review the respective blood pressure and heart rate parameters and be familiar with the protocols in place. Selecting the wrong cuff size for blood pressure measurement can result in artificially low or high blood pressure readings, hence it is important to use the correct cuff size when taking measurements. Please refer to the AHA Cuff Size Recommendations (Appendix K) for detailed cuff size information, provided by the AHA.

Blood samples for research purposes will be taken 2 and 3 hours after drug administration.

8.3 The Study Physician

The study physician can be part of the therapeutic dyad or will otherwise be on-site during the dosing session. He/she is responsible for the overall safety of patients and will oversee the medical management of study patients during the dosing session, as needed. Medications are allowed during the dosing session and will be available in the dosing session room.

A specific protocol for elevated blood pressure and heart rate can be found in the Cardiovascular Monitoring Instructions (Appendix L).

As discussed before, if agitation, fear, paranoia, or any other psychological distress cannot be sufficiently managed, the study physician will evaluate the need for medication administration. While it is highly unlikely a patient will require medications based on previous research with psilocybin, anti-anxiety and antipsychotic medications will be available and administered based on the clinical judgment of the study physician and therapists.

Medication treatment and emergency care will be at the discretion of the study physician, in consultation with the lead therapist (if not the same person) and, if necessary, the local PI.

Please refer to the protocol for additional information on medication administration during dosing sessions.

8.4 Procedures in Dosing Sessions

8.4.1 Prior to Patient Arrival

8.4.1.1 Readiness of staff and dosing room

Therapists should arrive prior to patient arrival to prepare the session room and check that all necessities are in place for the upcoming session. Therapists should also ensure that the session room is clean, organized, and aesthetically pleasing prior to the patient's arrival (see page 1 of the Dosing Session Checklists; Appendix I). Depending on the layout of the session room at the designated study site, this may mean placing artwork in the room and arranging furniture into appropriate positions. If appropriate, therapists may put a sign on the outside of the door to ensure minimal interruptions and privacy. The physical space where the patient and therapists will spend the next 8 or more hours constitutes a foundational aspect of the setting within this therapeutic approach - attention to details concerning the comfort and aesthetics of the session room will serve as a support for both the patient and therapists as they share space together throughout the dosing session.

After the dosing session, the patient will stay overnight in a designated bedroom which is part of the trial site but separated from the session room. Prior to the session, therapists should check if the overnight stay room is ready for use and the night monitor is informed.

Prior to welcoming the patient for their dosing session, the therapist dyad and the greater supporting on-site team should all check in and ensure that each staff member is ready with the proper medical equipment and any forms needed for the upcoming session.

8.4.1.2 Music and Sound System

Prior to the patient's arrival for the dosing session, therapists should check that the playlist and all sound system devices (see Section 3.2.2 for detailed instructions related to music) are working properly and smoothly. Technical difficulties during the dosing session are to be avoided to ensure that the patient's experience unfolds with as little distraction and agitation as possible.

8.4.1.3 Confirming Eligibility for Dosing Session

Upon arrival in the session room, patients will be greeted by his or her two study therapists. These two therapists will remain with the patient for the duration of the dosing session.

The patient will arrive at the research facility at a previously agreed upon time but in general arrival will be between (site specific; default in EPIsoDE trial 08:00 - 09:00).

Upon arrival, and prior to administration of the study drug, the following assessments will occur:

1. Study personnel will inquire about any change in concomitant medication use and adherence. Newly identified medications will be added to the list of concomitant medications and will be discussed with the study physician.
2. Alcohol and drug consumption will be assessed, and a urine drug test for drugs of abuse and an alcohol breath test will be performed.
3. Urine pregnancy testing (women of childbearing potential only, i.e., 13-50 years and no uterotomy) will be performed.

4. Pre-dose vital signs (blood pressure and heart rate) will be assessed.

Urine drug test and breathalyzer test results:

A negative urine drug test and breathalyzer test will be required the morning of dosing prior to drug administration. A positive urine drug test or breathalyzer test will result in the dosing session being cancelled. The study physician will be notified of test results. A positive test will result in the dose being cancelled with no option for future rescheduling.

Pregnancy test results:

A negative urine pregnancy test (women of childbearing potential only) will also be required the morning of dosing prior to drug administration. The study physician will be notified of urine pregnancy test results. A positive pregnancy test will result in the dose being cancelled with no option for future rescheduling.

Pre-dose cardiovascular monitoring:

Please refer to the Cardiovascular Monitoring Instructions (Appendix L) for pre-dose vital sign measurements and parameters.

8.4.2 Preparing the Patient for the Dosing Session

Patients will be asked to remove shoes, belts, earrings, and any other accessories that may be uncomfortable and could also be considered a safety hazard. Study personnel will securely store any personal items and remind the patient where the restroom is. Patients are encouraged to use the restroom before entering the session room or prior to ingesting the study medication.

Once the patient is comfortable in the room, he or she will be asked to take a resting position. If the patient indicates that it would be helpful before dosing, therapists may conduct a brief mindfulness meditation (see Appendix F) or other techniques (see 7.3.2) to encourage a relaxing state.

Therapists will remind the patient that the therapists' role during the dosing session is primarily to provide emotional support and safety monitoring, but that they will engage with the patient should the patient want to verbally share aspects of his/her experience, and will provide regular check-ins. Before the study drug is administered, the importance of the general strategy of allowing and being open to the upcoming experience should be recapitulated one last time. Lastly, therapists will encourage to repeat or discuss the intention he or she may have set for the day.

Sample statements
<p>Assessing the patient's psychological state:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• How are you doing right now?• How did you sleep?• Are you excited?
<p>Asking for open questions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Have there been any questions since yesterday?

Proposing mindfulness exercise:

- A short mindfulness exercise can help you get into a relaxed and open state. Do we want to try that?

Reviewing the role of therapists:

- We would like to briefly explain to you again what role we therapists have during the dosing session. We are here for you to give you the feeling of safety and security while you make your own personal inner experience. We support you if you experience extraordinary, overwhelming or challenging things on your "inner journey" and you would like support for this.
- Of course, you are also welcome to exchange ideas with us at any time. However, we recommend that you concentrate on yourself and your inner experience whenever possible.
- You can contact us at any time. As already discussed, all you have to do is talk to us or raise your hand. We will then see how you are doing right now and how we can support you.
- Otherwise, we will quietly stay here with you in the room to give you an undisturbed inner experience.

Explaining the procedure for visiting the restroom:

- If you need to go to the toilet, please let us know. One of us will then accompany you to the toilet and wait for you in front of the door.

Preparing the patient for check-ins:

- To get an impression of how you are doing now, we will regularly ask you how you are feeling. Because you can't see us with the mask, we will touch you briefly by the hand beforehand.

Preparing the patient for cardiovascular monitoring and blood sampling:

- We will measure your blood pressure and pulse at regular intervals, and after 2 hours and 3 hours we will also take a blood sample. Before that, we will briefly touch you by the hand.

Repeating recommendation to focus on the inner experience:

- As we said before, we recommend that you focus on your inner experience while listening to the selected music while lying down. Of course, you can always contact us if you need anything. However, whenever possible, try to stay with your inner experience and, for example, avoid frequent or longer conversations with us.

Encouraging openness:

- Try to engage with the inner experience with an open and accepting attitude. You are completely safe here. When it comes to difficult moments or phases, try to open yourself up to letting it happen. Trust that everything you experience has a purpose and can help you.

Reminding the patient of the journey metaphor:

- As we discussed yesterday, this can be compared to a voyage by ship, where you may have to sail through certain storms on your way to new shores. It can also be pleasant, ordinary or "unspectacular". Be open to everything that comes.
- Or with a hike where you really work up a sweat on the ascent before you can enjoy the view.
- As we discussed yesterday, you can compare this to a gondola ride through an amusement park. You are safe in your gondola, even if it goes through the ghost train. You can sit back and just perceive and observe what is happening.

Repeating the intention for the dosing session

- Do you still remember your intention that we discussed last time?
- Would we like to talk briefly about your intention again?

Note: Sample statements are meant not as strict defaults but as positive examples of therapist verbalizations in the given situation. Therapists may orient themselves by sample statements but are encouraged to use their own language and therapeutic style of communication for the purpose of authenticity.

8.4.3 Main Phase of Dosing Session

The main phase of the dosing session begins when the patient receives a single dose of the study drug (25 mg psilocybin, 5 mg psilocybin, or 100 mg nicotinamide), administered as a capsule and taken with approximately 200 ml of water. Regardless of the drug received, the patient will be under observation for at least 8 hours following study drug ingestion.

Soon after the patient has ingested the study drug, therapists should start the music playlist and set the sound system in such a way that the music can be heard softly in the room (see Section 3.2.2 for detailed guidelines related to music). When the patient is ready, the therapists will invite the patient to lie down on the bed and put on the eyeshades and headphones. Focusing attention inward while lying prone with eyeshades and headphones on is encouraged as an optimal means to remove outside distractions and optimize the therapeutic potential of the experience, but it is not a strict requirement. Should a patient wish to sit up, move around, or remove the eyeshades and earphones at any time, he or she will be allowed to do so, with assistance as necessary.

The patient will, however, not be allowed to leave the session room except to use the bathroom. It is helpful to remind the patient that they have previously agreed not to leave the dosing room, and that this was a requirement for study participation.

8.4.3.1 Guidelines for Communication during the Main Phase

During the main phase of the dosing session (i.e. in the approximately 6 hours following drug administration), communication should follow specific rules: Verbal communication with the patient should be reduced to a minimum in order not to distract them from their inner processes. Since altered states of consciousness are characterized by strong emotions, physical sensations and regression, communication should be simple, calm, reassuring and patient centered. As a rule of thumb, before addressing the patient, therapists should ask themselves whether what they are about to say or do stems from their own needs (e.g., being nervous, curious, bored, wanting to be helpful/important), or whether it is intended towards the patient's perceived needs.

Sample statements
<p>Encouraging the patient to focus on the inner experience:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Do you want to lie down and close your eyes?• Would you like to try to get completely involved with the music?• Would you like to try to turn to the inner experience?• We'll be happy to talk about anything later.
<p>Encouraging the patient to go deeper into the experience:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Feel inside yourself.• Feel free to go a little deeper. Look what you find there.• Can you get more involved in this?• Trust your way.• Open yourself up to everything that comes.• Everything that happens is fine. Everything is welcome.

Checking in:

- How are you?
- Is everything okay?
- Do you need something?

Cardiovascular monitoring and taking blood samples:

- Don't be disturbed, I'm going to measure your blood pressure now. If possible, stick to the experience.
- Is it okay if we take your blood now?
- I now measure your blood pressure again.
- We're going to take your blood now, it's best to stick to your experience.
- Please raise your hand if you want to refuse the blood sample now.
- I'll ask you again in an hour.

Note: Sample statements are meant not as strict defaults but as positive examples of therapist verbalizations in the given situation. Therapists may orient themselves by sample statements but are encouraged to use their own language and therapeutic style of communication for the purpose of authenticity.

8.4.3.2 Guidelines for Handling Psychological Distress

During preparatory sessions, therapists have discussed with the patient potential challenging experiences and techniques for handling them (Section 7.3.4). At the beginning of dosing sessions (Section 8.4.2), therapists will encourage patients to respond to overwhelming challenges by reaching out to therapists. Nevertheless, therapists should remain alert and aware for signs of agitation, anxiety, and continued psychological distress, as verbal or gestural communication on the part of the patient may be hindered because of the study medication.

Interventions for handling psychological distress can be broadly distinguished with respect to the following characteristics:

- **Engagement** versus **disengagement** from the process that is experienced as distressful
- **Promoting self-efficacy** versus **supporting the patient**

As a general rule, self-efficacy and engagement interventions should be preferred over support and disengagement interventions whenever possible (talking through before talking down). Support and disengagement interventions should be used sparingly, and only when deemed necessary due to the severity of distress experienced by the patient. Accordingly, the list below can be read as a gradient from "earlier" (first choice) to "later" (last resort) interventions:

- 1) **Promoting self-efficacy for engagement** (e.g., "You can do it"; "Would you like to try and go deeper?"; "Do you notice any changes when you pay close attention?")
- 2) **Supporting engagement** (e.g., "We are with you while you go through this"; "Should I hold your hand?"; "We will go through this together")
- 3) **Promoting self-efficacy for disengagement** (e.g., "Follow your breath [...] observe the sensation of breathing in and out")
- 4) **Supporting disengagement** (e.g., "I will now mute the music for a while"; "Would you like a glass of water?")

When used to support the patient during an extremely challenging situation, "later" interventions such as holding the hand, reminding the patient that he or she has taken a psychoactive substance, or changing the stimulus environment can have a strong relaxing effect. However, the same interventions may irritate, disturb, or disconcert the patient when used without need in situations where an earlier intervention such as mild encouragement would be sufficient.

Therapists may use the following types of techniques to help the patient through challenging experiences.

Encouraging the patient to use patient-led techniques discussed in preparatory sessions:

Therapists may gently remind the patient of the patient-led techniques discussed in preparatory sessions (Section 7.3.4.1; details there), and encourage and/or guide their use:

- Mindfulness
- "Leaning into" the experience

Ideally, therapists and the patient will have agreed on brief cues for prompting these techniques in preparatory sessions (e.g., "perceive and observe"; "go deeper"). Therapists should pay attention to using the agreed upon cues, and not to use too many different cues.

Sample statements
<p>Encouraging the patient to assume a mindful attitude:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Perceive and observe• Allow everything.• Let go.• Be completely open.• Watch everything you experience as if from a moving train... Let it pass by on its own... Just observe.
<p>Encouraging the patient to "lean into" the experience:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Go deeper.• Get involved.• Take a look.• Take a look. What you are experiencing right now will soon be different again.• Get closer and observe what changes.

Note: Sample statements are meant not as strict defaults but as positive examples of therapist verbalizations in the given situation. Therapists may orient themselves by sample statements but are encouraged to use their own language and therapeutic style of communication for the purpose of authenticity.

Reassurance:

Reassurance can either focus on self-efficacy (earlier interventions) or therapist support (later interventions). The latter should be reserved for more extreme situations (talking through before talking down). For instance, if the patient reports distressful physical sensations (e.g., of dissolving, warping, disappearing, or melting) to the point that they may feel as if they are dying, therapists should reassure the patient that their physical body is safe and will continue to function. Therapists may also remind the patient by that they have ingested a psychoactive drug (which the patient may have forgotten), that they are participating in a study, and that the effects of the drug are time-limited and will wear off. They can remind the patient that while the psychological and somatic effects may feel extreme and real, the physical risks of ingesting the drug remain extremely low.

Sample statements

- You do it very well.
- You can do it.
- Trust your way.
- Everything that happens is fine. Everything is allowed.
- That's what you're here for.
- That's all part of it.
- We are here for you.
- You are safe here. Nothing can happen to you.
- We take care of you.
- I remind you that you are here in a study. You have taken a substance that greatly alters your perception. The effect will soon wear off. Then everything will be back to normal. You can rest assured.

Note: Sample statements are meant not as strict defaults but as positive examples of therapist verbalizations in the given situation. Therapists may orient themselves by sample statements but are encouraged to use their own language and therapeutic style of communication for the purpose of authenticity.

Physical touch:

Within the boundaries agreed with the patient (this agreement has been noted by therapists in the checklist and summary of the Prep 1/Prep 2 session, Appendix E), therapists may hold the patient's hand or placing one hand on the patient's shoulder. At no time throughout the course of the study there should be any unsolicited physical contact between therapists and the patient.

Sample statements
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If you want, I'll hold your hand. • Would you take my hand?

Note: Sample statements are meant not as strict defaults but as positive examples of therapist verbalizations in the given situation. Therapists may orient themselves by sample statements but are encouraged to use their own language and therapeutic style of communication for the purpose of authenticity.

Guiding the patient's attention:

Therapists may encourage the patient to focus attention on any given aspect of the experience to support engagement with or disengagement from the process that is experienced as distressful. Guided breathing exercises can be used for both engagement (e.g., "breathing into" a sensation, emotion, or image) and disengagement (e.g. focusing on the sensation of inhalation and exhalation of the breath).

Sample statements
<p>Guiding attention to the music:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Follow the music. • Let the music carry you away.
<p>Going back to the intention:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Go back to your intention.
<p>Guided breathing exercises:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Breathe into the feeling. • Let your breath flow... Watch the breath flow in and out... Just observe.

Note: Sample statements are meant not as strict defaults but as positive examples of therapist verbalizations in the given situation. Therapists may orient themselves by sample statements but are encouraged to use their own language and therapeutic style of communication for the purpose of authenticity.

Changing the stimulus environment:

The patient's well-being, safety, and trust in the therapeutic process is of primary concern. If the patient becomes overwhelmed by his or her experience, it may be of benefit to remove the eyeshades and/or headphones to relax. During this time, the patient may desire therapeutic touch, conversation with the therapists about current emotions and sensations, or connecting with other special items that he or she brought for the session. Once the patient has regained a sense of centering and relaxation, he or she should be gently encouraged to re-engage with the therapeutic process by putting on the eyeshades and headphones and turning once again toward the inner experience. Note that to maintain the fit between the music and the experiential arc of the psilocybin experience, the music playlist may be muted but should never be stopped or paused during the dosing session (see Section 3.2.2).

Sample statements
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Should we turn down the music?• Do you want to take off the eyeshades?• Here's a glass of fresh water.• Do you want to sit up for a moment?• I have now turned down the music. I think that will be good for you.

Note: Sample statements are meant not as strict defaults but as positive examples of therapist verbalizations in the given situation. Therapists may orient themselves by sample statements but are encouraged to use their own language and therapeutic style of communication for the purpose of authenticity.

Rescue medication

In the unlikely case that the study physician determines that a patient's symptoms are too severe, not an expected part of the psilocybin experience and not tolerable, safety medications such as an oral benzodiazepine will be available for on-site acute anxiety (e.g., oral lorazepam), and an oral antipsychotic will be available for on-site antipsychotic treatment (e.g., oral tablets of risperidone or olanzapine). The necessity to prescribe any rescue medication is always assessed by the study physician. For the most part, using any rescue medication will be a joint decision of the study physician and patient. However, in the case of an unresolvable difference of opinion, the patient must accept the clinical judgement of the study physician.

Sample statements
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• We have now weighed up together and think the time has come to make it a little easier for you with a drug. If you take this tablet, you will feel better quickly.• Take this tablet now, you will feel better in a short time.• I would like you to take this tablet now, you're going to feel better in a moment.• We are concerned about you and believe it is urgent that you take this medication now.

Note: Sample statements are meant not as strict defaults but as positive examples of therapist verbalizations in the given situation. Therapists may orient themselves by sample statements but are encouraged to use their own language and therapeutic style of communication for the purpose of authenticity.

8.4.4 Ending Phase of Dosing Session

The ending phase of the dosing session begins when the music playlist has come to an end, i.e. approximately 6 hours after administration of the study drug. By this point, most drug effects will have subsided in most cases. Compared to main phase of the dosing session (where interactions between therapists and patient are kept at a minimum and the patient is encouraged to focus his or her attention on the inner experience), ending phase will be characterized by more interaction in most cases. Therapists may invite the patient to eat a light snack, engage in mild conversation, or write and/or draw about his/her experience. During this period of transition, patients may sit up, stretch, and/or adjust or remove their eyeshades and headphones. Lingering effects may still be present, and so therapists should be mindful to note the patient's level of psychological, emotional, and somatic sensitivity, and proceed with the next steps accordingly.

8.4.4.1 Debriefing

Should the patient want to share about their experience, this debriefing should be led by the patient, with the therapists listening with openness, curiosity, warmth, and acceptance. During this time, one or both therapists should take notes on what the patient has shared.

Sample statements
Offering debriefing: <ul style="list-style-type: none">• How are you doing now?• Would you like to tell us a little bit about what you experienced?
Limiting the debriefing: <ul style="list-style-type: none">• We will have time to talk about this in more detail at the integration meeting tomorrow.• You can also let the experience sink in a bit, put it on paper later in the evening and tell us more tomorrow.

Note: Sample statements are meant not as strict defaults but as positive examples of therapist verbalizations in the given situation. Therapists may orient themselves by sample statements but are encouraged to use their own language and therapeutic style of communication for the purpose of authenticity.

8.4.4.2 Going for a Walk

When at least 6 hours have passed after ingesting the study drug and the patient is not experiencing any more clearly discernible acute drug effects, the therapists may invite the patient to leave the dosing room for a gentle walk. Both therapists should accompany the patient at all times and return to the dosing room afterwards.

8.4.4.3 Questionnaires

When the patient feels ready to fill out questionnaires, therapists will hand out a set of psychometric tests to quantify relevant aspects of the patient's experience for research purposes.

8.4.4.4 Blinding Assessment and Music Ratings

After the patient has completed all questionnaires, the patient and both therapists should indicate their subjective assessment of the administered study drug as well as music ratings on the on the Blinding and Music Questionnaire (Appendix N). These assessments, which are done for research

purposes only, should not be discussed with the patient or between therapists. To preserve blinding as far as possible, the completed questionnaires should be folded and put in an envelope.

8.4.4.5 Evaluating the Patient for Transfer to Overnight Stay Room

When at least 8 hours have passed after ingesting the study drug and the patient appears to have returned to their baseline psychological and physiological state and expresses a readiness to be transferred to the overnight stay room, the lead therapist and the study physician will assess the patient. Before the patient is accompanied to the overnight stay room, the therapists must remind them to write down their experience in as detailed a way as they can while the experience is still fresh in their mind. The patient's written summary of the dosing session will be required for the following day's integration session.

The lead therapist will play a central role in determining that the patient is safe and ready for being transferred to the study site bedroom for the overnight stay at the end of the dosing session. From this point on, the patient will not be monitored continuously, although the night monitor will be available in case of any upcoming issue. In making this determination, the lead therapist needs to consider several safety parameters. The Overnight Stay Transfer Form (page 5 of the Dosing Session Checklists; Appendix I) must be filled out before the patient can be transferred to the overnight stay room at the end of the dosing session.

Physical evaluation:

It will be important to confirm that vital signs have returned to an acceptable level prior to the transfer to the overnight stay room at the study site, which for this study is a systolic blood pressure less than 140 mmHg and a diastolic blood pressure less than 90 mmHg, and a heart rate less than 100 beats per minute. A full description of the procedures for assessing vital signs is provided in the Cardiovascular Monitoring Instructions (Appendix L). If patients do not return to an acceptable blood pressure and/or heart rate after repeated measurements, the study physician will make a clinical determination of the best course of action to follow. Patients should also have no abnormal motor inabilities, compared to individual baseline before dosing session.

Psychological assessment:

Given the profound alterations in thinking, feeling, and perception that can be induced by psilocybin, it will be of equal importance that the patient's mental status is appropriately assessed and documented prior to discharge. On the most basic level, patients should be oriented to person, place, and time. It would be highly unusual for this not to be the case, but an assessment of this is crucial, as individuals can respond normally and still be suffering from disorientation.

In general, patients should have returned to something approximating their pre-treatment mental status before they are accompanied to the overnight stay room. At the least, the acute emotional, perceptual and cognitive effects of the study medication should have resolved.

In this regard, therapists and the study physician should listen carefully to patient speech to confirm that thought processes are logical and that no psychotic behaviour is apparent. Hallucinatory or highly unusual experiences are common during the peak of a psilocybin experience, so endorsement of these types of experiences occurring during the session is normal. However, patients should not be transferred to the overnight stay room until all such experiences have resolved and current mental state shows no evidence of psychosis. Similarly, psilocybin sessions can induce acute anxiety and dysphoria. Patients should be screened for the continuation of these types of symptoms at levels that would cause clinical concern. Finally, suicidality should be

explicitly assessed via direct questioning. Patients demonstrating any of these abnormalities will need a full evaluation by the study physician and be transferred to the emergency room if necessary.

Continued observation:

If the patient is experiencing residual study drug effects, such as mild persistent sensorial distortions, he or she will be asked to remain in the dosing session room for continued observation by therapists and/or the attending study physician until cleared to be transferred to the overnight stay room.

8.4.5 Overnight Stay at the Study Site

Therapists will remind the patient of the time and location of next day's integration session and introduce the patient to the night monitor as their contact person for any questions or concerns that emerge throughout the evening. He/she will accompany the patient to the study bedroom. From then on, the night monitor will assist and take care of the patient until the study personnel take over for outcome assessments and the integration session on the next day. After closing the dosing session, therapists are required to submit the Session Summary Form (Appendix D) along with the Dosing Session Monitoring Form (Appendix J) and the Cardiovascular Monitoring Form (Appendix M) to the study coordinator.

8.4.5.1 Study Personnel On-Site and On-Call

The night monitor will be the contact person for the patient on-site and will provide primary somatic and psychological assessment in case there is any question or concern. At least one of the therapists and the study physician will be on-call throughout the night to speak with night monitor and the patient should any issues arise. These contact numbers will be given to the night monitor in case he/she has any safety concerns for the patient.

While it is unlikely, if it is found that the patient is experiencing severe persisting physical or perceptual drug effects, exhibits signs of significant/severe emotional distress including suicidal ideation, or any other circumstance deemed an emergency per the study physician, the patient will be escorted to the hospital emergency department/acute ward for further psychiatric assessment.

8.4.5.2 Documentation

After closing the session, therapists are required to submit the completed Session Summary Form (Appendix D) along with the Dosing Session Checklists (see Appendix I), monitoring forms, questionnaires, blinding assessments etc. to the study nurse or study coordinator.

9 Integration Sessions

Integration sessions are an important time for the patient and therapist(s) to reflect, discuss, and identify thoughts and feelings about the material that has emerged through the dosing session and the days following that session. Integration can be understood as the process of learning from the psychedelic experience. This learning process can be complex. It is the role of the therapists to support the individual learning process of the patient so that the patient can make sense of what he experienced and put his insights into concrete actions to promote changes in thought patterns, emotions, behaviour and relationships.

This study will include a total of four integration sessions (two after each dosing session), each with a duration of approximately 1-2 hours. Prior to each integration session, a series of post-dose assessments will be conducted; these assessments may occur on the same day as the integration session but must be completed prior to the integration session itself.

It is important for the patient to bring the written summary of their dosing experience with them to the integration sessions held on the days after dosing sessions (Integration 1 and 2 sessions). The summary will be photocopied. The original version of the summary will be given to the patient and the copy put in the patient's file. Integration sessions should be primarily patient-led, the therapist listening actively and empathetically. The therapist may offer guidance in the form of open-ended questions as well as suggestions on how to bring insights gleaned from the dosing and integration sessions into the patient's everyday life and in relation to their depressive symptoms. Please note that communications between the patient and therapists outside of preparatory, dosing, and integration sessions is discouraged, unless the patient or therapists have concerns about the patient's safety. Informal phone calls and in-person visits should be avoided throughout the full duration of the study. All communication should be routed through the study coordinator so as not to compromise any aspect of the study.

Therapists should review the sections below in preparation for integration sessions.

9.1 Identification of Enduring Adverse Events (AEs)

Another important purpose of integration sessions is to watch out for signs of enduring AEs (see Section 10 on safety monitoring for details). Throughout integration sessions, therapists should evaluate whether the patient is experiencing any persisting hallucinations, intensification of depressive symptoms, suicidal ideation, heightened anxiety, paranoia, or any other issues of clinical concern. This needs to be documented and submitted with each preparatory and integration session, as a part of the session checklist. If any concerns arise which remain after the patient is evaluated by the study physician and after all safety ratings have been completed, the local PI will be called to evaluate the patient before the patient leaves the facility.

9.2 Integration 1a and 2a Sessions – One Day after Dosing Sessions

9.2.1 Session Structure

The Integration 1a and 2a sessions will be held on the day following dosing sessions and will take place in the dosing session room whenever possible. Whenever possible, both therapists should be present during these sessions. These sessions should have a duration between 60 and 120 minutes.

Whenever required, therapists may suggest a short break. The following should be covered in the Integration 1a and 2a sessions (see Integration 1a and 2a Checklist; Appendix O):

- Give an overview of the session structure (~5 min)
- Obtain a comprehensive overview of the patient's experience (~15-35 min)
- Help the patient relate their experience to their larger personal context (e.g. biography, everyday life, relationships) (~15-35 min)
- Encourage the patient to think about how to integrate gained insights and perspective shifts into everyday life (~15-35 min)
- Clarify organizational issues (~5 min)
- Close the session (~5 min)

Documents needed for this session:

- Print-out of Scheduling Form (Appendix C)
- Session Summary Form (Appendix D)
- Integration 1a and 2a Checklist (Appendix O)

Prior to the start of the session, therapists should review any notes taken throughout the dosing session, highlighting any particularly meaningful or noteworthy events (perceived distress, euphoria, verbalizations, body movements, laughing, crying, etc.). If these events are not discussed through the patient's initial reflection, therapists may want to refer to them later in the session to spark the patient's memory or encourage a deepening inquiry into their experience.

9.2.1.1 Give an Overview of the Session Structure

Therapists should start by reviewing the overall structure of the session.

Sample statement
<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Today's integration session is mainly about your experience yesterday.● First, we want to know as much as we can about what you experienced during our dosing session yesterday and in the aftermath.● Then we would like to see how these experiences could relate to you as a person, to your life and to your relationships.● And we also want to start thinking together about how you can take something positive from this experience for your everyday life and your future.

Note: Sample statements are meant not as strict defaults but as positive examples of therapist verbalizations in the given situation. Therapists may orient themselves by sample statements but are encouraged to use their own language and therapeutic style of communication for the purpose of authenticity.

9.2.1.2 Obtain a Comprehensive Overview of the Patient's Experience in the Dosing Session

The purpose of the first part of the session is to obtain a comprehensive understanding of the patient's experience throughout the dosing session and address particularly meaningful and/or challenging experiences that emerged throughout the dosing session and the evening after. In this phase, statements and prompts by the therapist should encourage the patient to describe the content of the experience. Therapists should ask the patient to retrieve their written reflection from the previous evening, should they like to use it as a reference. This written summary should be kept in the patient's file. If the patient would like a copy, a photocopy must be made.

Sample statements

- First, we would like to know what you experienced yesterday. We are interested in your entire experience from the beginning to the end of the session, as well as how you fared after the session.
- What happened yesterday after we said goodbye? How was the night? How did you feel when you got up this morning?
- Do you have your written summary with you? What did you write down?
- Please describe your experience to us in as much detail as possible.
- What did you experience after taking the study drug?
- Was your experience somehow different than usual? In what way?
- Were there any sensations, impressions, feelings or thoughts that seem particularly important to you?
- Did you experience certain feelings, thoughts or sensations during the session as difficult or challenging? Can you describe these experiences to us? What do you think about it now that we are sitting here together?
- How did you feel after the end of the session? What thoughts and feelings did you have? How did your body feel?

Note: Sample statements are meant not as strict defaults but as positive examples of therapist verbalizations in the given situation. Therapists may orient themselves by sample statements but are encouraged to use their own language and therapeutic style of communication for the purpose of authenticity.

9.2.1.3 Help the Patient Relate the Experience to their Larger Personal Context

After having obtained a comprehensive understanding of the patient's experience, therapists should help the patient relate their experience to their larger personal context, including their depression, life situation, relationships, and intentions set in preparatory sessions. In this phase of the session, the therapists' statements and prompts should actively encourage the patient to express insights and perspective shifts associated with their experience.

Sample statements

Asking the patient to relate the experience to their larger personal context:

- Next, we would like to talk to you about what these experiences could mean for you personally.
- Are there any insights from what you experienced yesterday?
- What does your experience yesterday have to do with you as a person, with your life or with your relationships?

Addressing the intention:

- Do you still remember your intention, i.e. what you had planned for the dosing session?
- What does your intention sound like to you today?
- Did your intention play any role yesterday?
- Did you have any insights related to your intention?

Helping the patient relate the experience to specific aspects of their personal context (based on patient cues):

- Do you have the impression that this makes you understand your depression differently or better?
- Does this have an impact on how you see yourself?
- Did the experience affect the way you perceive your feelings, thoughts, memories, or body sensations?
- Does the experience have an impact on how you see your current life situation?
- Does this provide insights into what is important or valuable to you in your life?
- Did you learn anything new about your relationships with other people?

Note: Sample statements are meant not as strict defaults but as positive examples of therapist verbalizations in the given situation. Therapists may orient themselves by sample statements but are encouraged to use their own language and therapeutic style of communication for the purpose of authenticity.

9.2.1.4 Encourage the Patient to Think about how to Integrate Perspective Shifts

As the discussion about the patient's experience ends, therapists should begin to discuss with the patient the importance of actively bringing gained insights and perspective shifts into their everyday life. This topic will be more thoroughly addressed in the Integration 1b and 2b sessions (one week after dosing sessions; 9.3).

The importance of continued personal integration cannot be overstated. Integration is extremely important in supporting and extending the therapeutic effects that may arise from dosing sessions. The form in which personal integration takes place will vary between patients according to their interests – various forms of continued self-experience, creative expression, reflection, journaling, and emotional release are all common and encouraged.

The time, intention and awareness given to continued integration practices promotes shifts in self-perceptions, deeply held negative beliefs, incongruent life values to occur and for new, more healthful patterns to arise and be reinforced. Rarely are these processes linear, so it is important to remind patients to exercise kindness toward themselves during moments when they feel off track. Below is a list of prompts therapists may use to encourage the patient to think about and express their own ideas for specific F change:

Sample statements
<p>Asking the patient to think about how to integrate gained insights and perspective shifts into everyday life:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Now we would like to start thinking about how you can take positive things from your experience for your everyday life and your future. Do you have any ideas on how you could benefit from the insights gained?
<p>Helping the patient develop ideas for specific behaviour change (based on patient cues):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• To what extent could these findings influence your behaviour in future difficult situations?• To what extent could these findings affect your experience and behaviour in relationships?• Are there things that you want to give more (or less) space in your life in the future?• Are there any minor habits that you would like to change?• What activities could you do to help these insights lead to positive changes in your life in the long term? Are there any previous activities that you have given up and could resume? Can you think of new activities?

Note: Sample statements are meant not as strict defaults but as positive examples of therapist verbalizations in the given situation. Therapists may orient themselves by sample statements but are encouraged to use their own language and therapeutic style of communication for the purpose of authenticity.

For some (but not all) patients, the focus of these discussions will be on building activities. Below are examples of continued activities that therapists may encourage the patient to engage in for their personal benefit:

- Formal mindfulness practice (e.g. mindfulness meditation)
- Keeping a journal
- Being in nature
- Engaging in physical activities such as walking, running, dancing, hiking, etc.
- Engaging with or taking care of one's body in pleasurable ways
- Seeking pleasurable activities
- Painting, drawing, sculpting, and other art forms
- Singing or playing music
- Participating in community events

- Spending time with partner, family, or friends
- Building new social contacts or resuming old ones
- Volunteering work

If the patient expresses an interest and receptivity towards specific forms of behaviour change and/or activities, therapists may encourage or assist in the planning of next steps. Therapists should encourage the patient to be as specific as possible in defining one or two realistic first steps toward their continued integration and wellbeing.

Sample statement
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In our experience, positive changes are best achieved when they are planned as concretely as possible. You mentioned earlier that you would like to change your [behaviour]. • What exactly would you like to do differently in the future? • You've said that you want to give certain things more (or less) space in your life. Can you think of any concrete first steps in this direction? • You mentioned earlier that you'd like to spend more time on [activity]. What would be the first steps in this direction for you? How/when exactly could you do that

Note: Sample statements are meant not as strict defaults but as positive examples of therapist verbalizations in the given situation. Therapists may orient themselves by sample statements but are encouraged to use their own language and therapeutic style of communication for the purpose of authenticity.

Therapists should now talk with the patient about his or her social support network and considerations around whether (and with whom) they might want to share their dosing session experience. While patients may feel compelled to share what they have experienced to others outside of the study context, therapists should advise that patients choose to confide only in those whom they most deeply trust. Furthermore, patients can be cautioned not to "push" the sharing if initial attempts are not met with acceptance or helpful listening. Shared experiences of non-ordinary states of consciousness may not be understood, accepted, or welcomed by others, which can lead to feelings of rejection, isolation, and ostracism in the person attempting to share. Assist the patient in identifying persons in their lives in whom they feel they could confide in, and if they feel they do not currently have a deeply trusted person to share with, encourage them to find ways to honor their experience or share in a more limited way until such time as sharing becomes possible.

Sample statement
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Finally, we want to consider together with you whether and how you would like to talk to other people about your experience. Are there people in your environment you would like to talk about it? • Who would you rather not tell about it?

Note: Sample statements are meant not as strict defaults but as positive examples of therapist verbalizations in the given situation. Therapists may orient themselves by sample statements but are encouraged to use their own language and therapeutic style of communication for the purpose of authenticity.

9.2.1.5 Clarify Organizational Issues

Confirmation of next session:

Therapists should confirm the appointment for the following integration session (Integration 1b/2b). A print-out of the completed Scheduling Form (Appendix C) with all remaining appointments should be given to the patient.

Emergency and study staff contact information:

The patient information document given to the patient upon study enrolment includes emergency and study staff contact information. Therapists should remind the patient that their safety is of primary importance, above any data collection or other research-related activities. The patient should be encouraged to call the emergency number in case of any emergency, and to contact the study staff if any organizational issues (e.g., necessity to reschedule an appointment) should arise.

9.2.1.6 Closing the Session

Before closing the session, therapists should discuss with the patient the following options for dealing with worsening depression: Contacting the study team, emergency admission, and resuming antidepressant treatment. Regarding the latter, relevant information about possible exclusion from the study should be provided.

If one of the therapists is expected to be absent in the following integration session, Integration Session 2a is the last contact between the patient and that therapist. Hence, the parting therapist and the patient should say goodbye at this point.

Once the patient is ready, confirm the time and location of their next integration session and post-dose assessments, and confirm the patient has the appropriate study personnel contact information. After Integration 1a and 2a sessions, the patient will be checked for discharge by the study physician before being allowed to leave the study site.

Sample statement
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• This concludes our integration session for today - thank you very much for sharing your experiences with us and for allowing us to accompany this process with you.• We look forward to seeing you again on [date] at [time] for your next integration session.• In the next session, we will look at any changes you notice in your everyday life and in connection with your depression.• Remember that the study staff can be reached by phone if you feel that you would like to contact us.

Note: Sample statements are meant not as strict defaults but as positive examples of therapist verbalizations in the given situation. Therapists may orient themselves by sample statements but are encouraged to use their own language and therapeutic style of communication for the purpose of authenticity.

After closing the session, therapists are required to submit the Session Summary Form (Appendix D) along with the Integration Session 1a and 2a Checklist (see Appendix O) to the study nurse or study coordinator.

9.3 Integration 1b and 2b Sessions – One Week after Dosing Sessions

9.3.1 Session Structure

The Integration 1b and 2b sessions will be held after the clinical assessment that is scheduled to take place on day 7 after each dosing session, between days 7 and 11, and will take place in the

dosing session room whenever possible. Both therapists may be present during these sessions, but one therapist may be absent if deemed appropriate. These sessions should have a duration between 60 and 120 minutes. Whenever required, therapists may suggest a short break. The following should be covered in the Integration 1b and 2b sessions (see Integration 1b and 2b Checklist; Appendix P):

- Ask for open questions from previous sessions and give an overview of the session structure (~10 min)
- Discuss how the patient's quality of life and experience of depression have changed since the dosing session and address any persistent or emergent integration challenges (~30-70 min)
- Discuss and develop a longer-term plan for continued integration (~10-30 min)
- Clarify organizational issues (~5 min)
- Close the session (~10 min)

Documents needed for this session:

- Print-out of Scheduling Form (Appendix C; only needed for Integration Session #2)
- Session Summary Form (Appendix D)
- Integration 1b and 2b Checklist (Appendix P)

Prior to the start of the session, the therapist should review the notes taken throughout the previous integration session, highlighting any particularly meaningful insights, challenges, or intentions that were discussed.

9.3.1.1 Give Overview of Session Structure and Ask for Open Questions

At the beginning of the session, therapists should review the session’s overall structure. Therapists should then invite the patient to discuss remaining questions from the previous integration session.

Sample statement
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● In today's integration session, we would like to talk above all about whether and how your experience in everyday life and your depression have changed since the last session. ● In addition, we would like to look together at what you can do to benefit from your participation in this study in the long term. ● First, however, we can talk about the topics of the last meeting. Are there any questions or new findings that you would like to discuss with us?

Note: Sample statements are meant not as strict defaults but as positive examples of therapist verbalizations in the given situation. Therapists may orient themselves by sample statements but are encouraged to use their own language and therapeutic style of communication for the purpose of authenticity.

9.3.1.2 Discuss changes and address integration challenges

Below is a list of prompts that may support the unfolding of this session. Although this session should be conducted in a manner that is primarily non-directive, the therapist should assist in the process of reflection, when necessary, by encouraging the patient to share in as much detail as possible.

Sample statement

- Do you still think often about the dosing session? What goes through your head then?
- Do you feel that your experience still has an impact on you in some way?
- Are there changes in how you experience your depression?
- Are there any changes in your relationships?
- Are there changes in how you see your current life situation?
- Are there any changes in how you look at past events?
- Are there changes in how you react to certain events?
- Are there changes in your values, i.e. in what you find important or valuable in your life and what you don't?
- Have you experienced any difficulties since the last session?
- How have you experienced your personal environment in the last few days? Did you talk about your experience?
- What have you spent your time doing in the last few days?
- In the last meeting, we also talked about activities and planned first steps. Did it work out to implement this? How did you feel about it?
- Have you changed anything in your life? What are these changes, and why did you decide to make them?
- Are there any things you would like to change but haven't changed yet? Why do you want these changes? What is the difficult thing about it?
- Have you thought about your intention since our last meeting? How did you feel about that?

Note: Sample statements are meant not as strict defaults but as positive examples of therapist verbalizations in the given situation. Therapists may orient themselves by sample statements but are encouraged to use their own language and therapeutic style of communication for the purpose of authenticity.

9.3.1.3 Develop a Longer-term Plan for Continued Integration

Having explored the ways in which the patient's life and experience of depression may have changed, any emergent or persistent challenges that they may be facing, and their engagement with any continued integration modalities, the therapist should encourage the patient to consider developing longer-term plans for managing their depression or, if a significant reduction of their depression symptoms has occurred, reducing the risk of recurrence. These longer-term plans should be structured around the patient's intentions in moving towards positive change as discussed throughout the integration sessions.

Discussions of longer-term plans may build upon previous conversations around continued integration practices and may also include the addition of other activities such as reconnecting with family or friends, reigniting old hobbies or exploring new ones, shifting certain behaviour or thinking patterns, and becoming more involved in their community. Any reflections or concerns around engaging with mental healthcare professionals (e.g., how to find a psychotherapist, further antidepressant medication) can be addressed at this time as well.

Sample statement

- Finally, we would like to consider together with you how you should proceed in the next few weeks and after the completion of this study. What goes through your mind when you think about it?
- What could you do to maintain or enhance the positive effects of the treatment?
- What could you do to get closer to the changes you want?
- How would you like to organize your everyday life to improve your mood (also) in the long term?
- What would be the first steps in this direction? When/how exactly could you start?
- Under what circumstances do you think a relapse could occur? What can you do about it?
- Are there things you would like to discuss with your psychotherapist after this study?
- Can you imagine starting psychotherapy?
- Are there things you want to discuss with your psychiatrist after this study?

Note: Sample statements are meant not as strict defaults but as positive examples of therapist verbalizations in the given situation. Therapists may orient themselves by sample statements but are encouraged to use their own language and therapeutic style of communication for the purpose of authenticity.

Some patients may express a desire to seek further experiences with psilocybin or other psychedelics outside of the study. Therapists should generally discuss these desires from a harm reduction perspective. Based on an understanding of the patient's motivation for repeated psychedelic use, it will often be appropriate that therapists encourage the patient to work on thoroughly integrating the experience(s) they have already had before undergoing new experiences. Therapists should also remind the patient that any psychedelic use before completion of the study may lead to the patient's exclusion from the study. Under no circumstances should therapists encourage the patient to engage in illegal or risky activities.

9.3.1.4 Clarify Organizational Issues

Confirmation of next session (only applicable for the Integration 1b session):

Therapists should confirm the appointment for the following preparatory session (Prep 2). A print-out of the completed Scheduling Form (Appendix C) with all remaining appointments should be given to the patient.

Emergency and study staff contact information:

The patient information document given to the patient upon study enrolment includes emergency and study staff contact information. Therapists should remind the patient that their safety is of primary importance, above any data collection or other research-related activities. The patient should be encouraged to call the emergency number in case of any emergency, and to contact the study staff if any organizational issues (e.g., necessity to reschedule an appointment) should arise.

9.3.1.5 Closing the session

Before closing the session, therapists should discuss with the patient the following options for dealing with worsening depression: Contacting the study team, emergency admission, and resuming antidepressant treatment. Regarding the latter, relevant information about possible exclusion from the study should be provided.

Once the patient is ready, confirm the time and location of their next integration session (if applicable) and post-dose assessments, and confirm the patient has the appropriate study personnel contact information.

Sample statement
Integration 1b <ul style="list-style-type: none">• This concludes today's integration session. We look forward to seeing you again on [date] at [time] for your next preparation session.• It would be great if you applied/implemented what we discussed here by then. Remember that the study staff can be reached by phone if you feel that you would like to contact us.

Integration 2b

- This concludes our last integration session. This means that our joint work is now also coming to an end.
- We would both like to thank you very much for allowing us to walk this path together with you.
- Of course, we very much hope that you will continue to apply/implement what we have discussed here so that you can take something positive for yourself from your experiences in this study in the long term.
- We wish you all the best for the future.
- Remember that the study staff will still be available by phone if you feel that you would like to reach out to us.

Note: Sample statements are meant not as strict defaults but as positive examples of therapist verbalizations in the given situation. Therapists may orient themselves by sample statements but are encouraged to use their own language and therapeutic style of communication for the purpose of authenticity.

After closing the session, therapists are required to submit the Session Summary Form (Appendix D) along with the Integration 1b and 2b Checklist (see Appendix P) to the study nurse or study coordinator.

10 Safety Monitoring

The safety of patients throughout the duration of the study, and especially on the day of dosing with psilocybin (high or low dose) or active placebo (nicotinamide) is paramount. Therapists play a very important role in the safety and well-being of study patients. Below is information on specific safety monitoring as it relates to the therapist role. Please see the study protocol for additional safety monitoring information. All safety monitoring sections and forms will be reviewed and discussed in detail during in-person trainings with all therapists before they may work with patients.

Therapists should communicate any changes in the patient's physical, mental health, medications, etc. to the study coordinator promptly (the same day on which such changes occur, if possible) and discuss any concerns with the study physician and/or local PI.

10.1 Safety Monitoring in Preparatory and Integration Sessions

Each checklist for preparatory and integration sessions (Appendices A, E, O, and P) comprises a safety monitoring form that must be filled out by one of the therapists after each session. If any of the items, i.e. worsening depression, suicidality, psychotic symptoms, hallucinogen persisting perception disorder (HPPD), or other, is answered affirmatively, this must be documented in the Session Summary Form (Appendix D) and reported to the study coordinator and/or the PI.

A comprehensive safety monitoring is conducted separately by study personnel outside of therapy sessions. Therefore, therapists must actively address the items on the safety monitoring form only with the patient on given occasion.

10.1.1 Worsening Depression

Generally, patients with MDD feel better once they enter a study. Indeed, simply entering a study can activate significant placebo effects. But on occasion, an individual's depression will worsen across the course of a study. The risk for this happening in the present study may be increased due to the fact that patients will need to discontinue any psychiatric medications and/or psychotherapy in the screening period prior to dosing. Patients will be repeatedly administered questionnaires that ask about worsening symptoms. However, it may occur that a patient minimizes their distress on questionnaires and is more forthcoming in the context of the empathic relationships formed with the therapists. For this reason, therapists should remain alert to anything said by a patient that suggests worsening depression or increasingly suicidal ideation. Should such challenges emerge during preparatory or integration sessions, therapists should alert relevant study personnel and document accordingly. Required documentation will be discussed during in-person therapist trainings.

10.1.2 Suicidality

Suicidality will be monitored throughout the study and formally assessed via questionnaires. However, as with depressive symptoms in general, suicidal ideation may be more fully and honestly reported to therapists than in response to standard questionnaires administered by study personnel with which patients have less rapport. If at any time therapists have concerns that a patient is experiencing active suicidal ideation, the local PI should be contacted immediately, who will follow proper notification procedures. Therapists should remain with the patient until

additional study staff arrive to conduct an assessment. In the event of an emergency, therapists may call 112 (ambulance service).

10.1.3 Psychotic Symptoms

Rarely during the psychedelic experience, (pre-)psychotic symptoms can occur, including formal thought disorders (associative or disorganized thinking, "word salad"), delusions (delusions of reference, grandeur, persecution), thought broadcasting or insertion, illusions or hallucinations (visual, auditory, tactile, olfactory), and disorganized motor behaviour (up to mutism or catatonia). Usually psychotic symptoms only last for the duration of the acute drug effects of Psilocybin, as large surveys demonstrated no higher incidence of lasting psychosis in regular users of psychedelics (Johansen & Krebs, 2015).

If any patient should mention or show psychotic symptoms, the study physician should assess the patient's mental status thoroughly, as well as re-establish a trustful relationship and use the patient- and therapist-driven techniques to reduce stress and reassure the patient ("talking down"), as it is described in Section 7.3.4. If these methods fail to reduce the psychotic symptoms, anxiolytic and antipsychotic medication can be used to provide immediate relief (see Section 8.4.3.2 and Appendix G for details). If symptoms prevail, therapist proceed according to the suicidality protocol described above.

10.1.4 Hallucinogen Persistent Perception Disorder

Some people who have used serotonergic hallucinogens, such as psilocybin, experience persistent, distressing alterations in mostly visual perception that last from weeks to years after use (Espiard, Lecardeur, Abadie, Halbecq, & Dollfus, 2005). This rare condition is referred to as hallucinogen persisting perception disorder (HPPD). To our knowledge, no cases of HPPD have occurred in volunteers who have been administered psilocybin in contemporary research studies (Studerus, Kometer, Hasler, & Vollenweider, 2011). If any patient should mention perceptual alterations that persist after the acute effects of psilocybin subside, therapists should contact the local PI, who will arrange for further assessments.

10.2 Safety Monitoring on Dosing Days

10.2.1 Cardiovascular Monitoring During the Dosing Session

Cardiovascular functioning, i.e., blood pressure and heart rate, will be periodically measured during dosing sessions, beginning with pre-dose measurements. Please refer to the Cardiovascular Monitoring Instructions (Appendix L) for specific information on the frequency of monitoring, measurement parameters, and the protocol for contacting the study physician. All cardiovascular measurements must be documented in the Cardiovascular Monitoring Form (Appendix M).

10.2.2 Adverse Events

An Adverse Event (AE) according to the EMA-ICH Guideline for good clinical practice (GCP) E6(R2) Glossary 1.2 is as follows: "Any untoward medical occurrence in a patient or clinical

investigation subject administered a pharmaceutical product and which does not necessarily have a causal relationship with this treatment."

Therapists will play an important role in identifying AEs, given that they will be present with the patient during his/her psilocybin session. All AEs that occur during dosing sessions must be documented in the Dosing Session Monitoring Form (Appendix J). All therapists will be trained to identify markers of AEs and will be instructed on how to document them.

10.2.3 Overnight Stay Transfer Form

Towards the end of dosing sessions, the lead therapist, along with the study physician, will be responsible for assessing the patient's physical and psychological status prior to the transfer from the dosing session room to the overnight stay room. The overnight stay transfer form (page 5 of the Dosing Session Checklists; Appendix I) will be reviewed in detail during in-person trainings for all therapists who qualify to be lead therapists.

10.3 Prohibited Substances

Several medications and drugs are not allowed while the patient is in the study. Any substances a patient is currently taking will have been evaluated by study personnel. Therapists should be aware that the following substances are strictly prohibited for use at any time during the study, and inform the study coordinator if a patient should reveal, or is suspected of, taking them.

10.3.1 5-Hydroxytryptophan (5-HTP)

5-HTP is a supplement available without a prescription. Anecdotal reports, outside of the research setting suggest some individuals will take it following a psychedelic drug experience to increase serotonin production. Because of its potential effects on serotonin, it is not allowed.

10.3.2 Cannabis

Cannabis, either used for recreational or medicinal purposes, including prescribed marijuana, is prohibited throughout the duration of the study. As part of study participation, patients agree to have urine drug testing at frequent intervals throughout the study. If a patient tests positive, they may be removed from the study. If a patient tests positive on the day of dosing, the dose will be cancelled and can only be rescheduled at the discretion of the local PI.

10.3.3 Cannabidiol (CBD)

Like cannabis, CBD used for either recreational or medicinal purposes is prohibited throughout the duration of the study due to its influence on the central nervous system and potential effects on mood and anxiety.

10.3.4 Illicit and Non-Prescribed Drugs

Use of illicit and non-prescribed drugs is prohibited throughout the duration of the study. This includes psilocybin and other psychedelic substances. As part of study participation, patients agree

to urine drug testing at frequent intervals throughout the study. If a patient tests positive on the day of dosing, the dose will be cancelled.

10.3.5 Alcohol

The use of alcohol is strictly forbidden 24 hours before dosing sessions. Patients are not prohibited using alcohol during the duration of the study but will be recommended not to use alcohol on the days prior to dosing sessions (see Handout – Patient Information on Dosing Sessions; Appendix G).

A negative breathalyzer test will be required the morning of dosing prior to drug administration. If a patient test is positive (i.e. blood alcohol concentration > 0.0 ‰), the dose will be cancelled.

Appendix

Appendices are listed in order of appearance in the main text of this manual.

Appendix	Title
A	General Prep Checklist
C	Scheduling Form
D	Session Summary Form
E	Prep 1 and 2 Checklist
F	Instructions for Mindfulness Exercise
G	Handout – Patient Information on Dosing Sessions
I	Dosing Session Checklists
J	Dosing Session Monitoring Form
K	AHA Cuff Size Recommendations
L	Cardiovascular Monitoring Instructions
M	Cardiovascular Monitoring Form
N	Blinding and Music Questionnaire
O	Integration 1a and 2a Checklist
P	Integration 1b and 2b Checklist
Q	Biographical Questionnaire
R	Music Playlists

Appendix A: General Prep Checklist

Checklist General Preparation

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Patient (ID)

Date

Leading therapist

Co-Therapist

Procedure of the meeting:		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Start video/audio recording according to the patient's consent and show the camera to the patient (if applicable)	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Introduce yourself and provide an overview of the purpose and structure of the preparatory sessions	~10 min
<input type="checkbox"/>	Discuss topics relevant to the patient's depression: Motivation for study participation Depression (course, symptoms, explanatory model of the patient) Stressful life events Values, interests and important relationships Personality and self-image	~30-45 min
<input type="checkbox"/>	Discuss previous treatments	~10 min
<input type="checkbox"/>	Discuss expectations and hopes regarding treatment with psilocybin	~10-25 min
<input type="checkbox"/>	Check your acceptance of the requirements for study participation: Patient agrees to remain at the study center after taking the substance until after the integration session the following day. Patient agrees not to harm himself or others on the day of the dosing session. Patient agrees to contact study staff and/or emergency services in case of suicidal ideation for the entire duration of the study.	~5 min
<input type="checkbox"/>	Handout – Hand out patient information for dosing sessions (Appendix G) and go through the first part (instructions and recommendations for the days before the dosing session) together.	~10 min
<input type="checkbox"/>	Clarify organizational matters: Confirm support person (if applicable) Confirm the date for preparation 1 Confirm emergency and contact information	~5 min
<input type="checkbox"/>	End Session	~5 min

Safety monitoring*:	
<input type="checkbox"/> yes <input type="checkbox"/> no	Indications of exacerbation of depressive symptoms
<input type="checkbox"/> yes <input type="checkbox"/> no	Indications of suicidal tendencies
<input type="checkbox"/> yes <input type="checkbox"/> no	Indications of psychotic symptoms
<input type="checkbox"/> yes <input type="checkbox"/> no	Evidence of Hallucinogen Persisting Perceptual Disorder (HPPD)
<input type="checkbox"/> yes <input type="checkbox"/> no	Other notes: _____

*Each item answered "yes" must be documented in the session summary and reported to the study director.

Completed by therapist	Date of completion	Signature therapist
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Appendix C: Scheduling Form

Scheduling

Patient (ID)

Meeting	Date	Time	Location
General Preparation			
Preparation 1			
Substance 1			
Integration 1a			
Integration 1b			
Preparation 2			
Substance 2			
Integration 2a			
Integration 2b			

Appendix D: Session Summary Form

Appendix E: Prep 1 and 2 Checklist

Checklist Preparation 1 and 2

Patient (ID)	Date	Leading therapist	Co-Therapist

- Preparation 1
- Preparation 2

Procedure of the meeting:		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Start video/audio recording according to the patient's consent (if applicable)	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Clarify open questions and give an overview of the structure of the meeting	~5 min
<input type="checkbox"/>	Introducing Mindfulness and Performing Mindfulness Practice	~10 min
<input type="checkbox"/>	Discuss Common Experiences in Dosing sessions	~10 min
<input type="checkbox"/>	Discuss the possibility of challenging experiences and recommendations on how to deal with them	~20 min
<input type="checkbox"/>	Make and note the agreement regarding therapeutic touch:	~20 min
<input type="checkbox"/>	Show the meeting room, listen to music and let them try out the blindfold	~5 min
<input type="checkbox"/>	Develop intention for the dosing session	~10 min
<input type="checkbox"/>	Discuss the structure of the dosing session day, instructions, and recommendations (handout)	~20 min
<input type="checkbox"/>	Get to know a support person (if applicable)	~10 min
<input type="checkbox"/>	Clarify organizational matters: Confirm emergency and contact information Confirm Dosing session Date	~5 min
<input type="checkbox"/>	End Session	~5 min
Safety monitoring*:		
<input type="checkbox"/> yes <input type="checkbox"/> no	Indications of exacerbation of depressive symptoms	
<input type="checkbox"/> yes <input type="checkbox"/> no	Indications of suicidal tendencies	
<input type="checkbox"/> yes <input type="checkbox"/> no	Indications of psychotic symptoms	
<input type="checkbox"/> yes <input type="checkbox"/> no	Evidence of Hallucinogen Persisting Perceptual Disorder (HPPD)	
<input type="checkbox"/> yes <input type="checkbox"/> no	Other notes: _____	

*Each item answered "yes" must be documented in the session summary and reported to the PI.

Completed by therapist	Date of completion	Signature therapist
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Appendix F: Instructions for Mindfulness Exercise

Instructions for Mindfulness Practice

Instructions for instructions:

The present mindfulness exercise was freely adapted from Segal et al. (Segal, Teasdale, & Williams, 2002) for this study. For instructions, the following content should be presented to the patient in a calm, gentle voice. Between individual sentences, parts of sentences and sections of meaning, the speaker should leave pauses according to his own feeling. In general, the length of the break should increase towards the end of the exercise.

Instruction text:

Adopt a comfortable sitting posture, upright but relaxed. It can be helpful not to lean against it, because this way your back can support itself. Place your feet next to each other flat on the floor. Feel free to experiment with your sitting posture until you feel that you are sitting upright and comfortably.

If you like, gently close your eyes. If you want to keep your eyes open, find a point where you can gently rest your gaze.

Now turn your attention to your physical sensations. Feel the touch where your body is in contact with the floor and the chair. Feel the slight pressure in these areas. Spend some time exploring these sensations.

Now direct your attention to the sensations in your abdomen and chest. Observe inwardly how these sensations are constantly changing as the breath flows in and out of your body. Feel how the abdominal wall lifts when you breathe in. How the rib cage expands slightly. And feel how the abdominal wall lowers again when you exhale. How the slight stretching decreases again.

Now focus your attention on the sensations in and on your nose. Observe the sensations there as you breathe in and out. Watch how the airflow in your nose is constantly changing. Feel how the air you breathe flows in coolly when you breathe in, and how it flows out warm when you breathe out.

Try to follow the changing sensations of breathing with your attention. Observe very carefully what you feel there when you breathe in and when you breathe out. You may also notice the small pauses you can observe after inhaling and after exhaling.

It is not necessary to control breathing. If you can, allow the breath to flow on its own. Bring this attitude of acceptance to the rest of your experiences as best you can. It's not about changing anything. They are not supposed to reach a certain state. Observe your experiences and let them be as they are right now.

Sooner or later, your mind will wander off the breath and turn to thoughts, plans, or daydreams. That's quite normal and okay – that's just the way our mind does. It's not a problem, not a mistake when that happens. Whenever you notice that your attention is no longer on the breath, observe briefly where the mind has wandered ("Aha, there's another thought"). And then you focus your attention entirely on the sensations on and in your nose – and renew your intention to observe the sensations as you breathe in and out.

It will probably happen repeatedly that your mind wanders. This is not a mistake and not a problem. If you notice it, then very gently bring your attention back to the breath. And then proceed to observe very attentively the sensations of breathing.

When inhaling, perceive the influx of cooler air. When exhaling, the outflow of warmer air. And in between, take advantage of the small breaks.

Remind yourself from time to time that your intention is simply to observe the breath. To observe how the breath feels at this very moment. From one moment to the next moment.

And whenever you notice that your attention is no longer on the breath, then briefly observe where your mind has wandered ("Aha, another thought"). And then turn your attention back to the breath. Feel the air flowing in and out of your body. Observe what sensations arise in the process.

Observe the breath very carefully and attentively. You may notice small differences between each breath.

Now expand the focus of your attention and try to perceive your body as a whole. Perceive all the sensations you feel throughout your body.

Now get ready to finish the exercise soon. Take a few deep breaths in and out a few times. Play a bit with your fingers and toes. When you're ready, open your eyes. Maybe you want to stretch a bit.

Appendix G: Handout – Patient Information on Dosing Sessions

Handout – Dosing Session Information

This is a summary of the most important information about your upcoming dosing session. Your therapists will discuss this information with you during the next preparatory sessions. Please prepare for this by reading this document at your leisure. Open questions can be answered at the next preparatory meeting.

Instructions and recommendations for the days before the dosing session
<p><u>Night's rest:</u> Try to get enough sleep the nights before the dosing session. If you can't fall asleep or stay asleep well, this is not a problem. The only important thing is that you create the best possible conditions for a restful night's sleep. Take enough time for your night's rest and try to avoid disturbances as much as possible. Do not consume caffeinated drinks in the evening and avoid exciting or stressful activities before bedtime.</p>
<p><u>Stress:</u> Try to keep your stress levels low for a few days before the dosing session. Avoid very exciting and stressful activities as much as possible. Moderate physical activity, e.g. moderate sports or walks, can promote relaxation.</p>
<p><u>Alcohol:</u> We recommend that you refrain from consuming alcohol altogether for a few days before the dosing session. Please remember that NO ALCOHOL may be drunk from 24 hours before the dosing session. Before the dosing session, a breathalyzer test is performed. If the test is positive, the dosing session must be cancelled.</p>
<p><u>Drugs and other psychotropic substances:</u> The use of psychotropic substances of any kind (including illegal drugs, prescription drugs and over-the-counter preparations) is strictly prohibited in the context of this study. Note that a urine test will be done before the dosing session. If the test is positive, the dosing session must be cancelled.</p>
<p><u>Medications and supplements:</u> The study doctor has already talked to you about whether you should stop taking certain medications and/or supplements before the dosing session. Please follow the agreements discussed with the study doctor exactly. Note that the dosing session may be cancelled if you are taking medications or supplements that have not been specifically approved by the study physician.</p>
<p><u>Work:</u> Try to take time off for the day after the dosing session beforehand, if possible. Otherwise, please try to keep the workload as low as possible. It is possible that you will still process the experience the next day and experience correspondingly strong emotions.</p>
<p><u>Home environment:</u> To help process the experience, it is beneficial to return to the most calm and comfortable environment possible the day after the dosing session. Consider this in advance of the dosing session and make appropriate preparations.</p>
<p><u>Openness:</u> Try to approach the dosing session with an open mind. The experience doesn't have to meet certain expectations to have a positive impact. Try to let go of your expectations. Resolve to be completely open to any experiences that will come up.</p>

Instructions and recommendations for the morning before the dosing session

Breakfast:

Eat a light, not too high-fat breakfast at home. We recommend, for example, fruit, eggs, toast or rolls, yoghurt, or sugar-free cereals.

Caffeine:

Avoid caffeinated beverages in the morning before the dosing session, as they can cause nausea during the dosing session. Exception: If you know that you will experience discomfort (e.g. severe headaches) if you stop consuming caffeine, take a sufficient, smaller amount.

Personal hygiene:

Personal hygiene can help to prepare yourself internally for the upcoming experience. Take a shower in the morning before the dosing session and take care of your body so that you feel as comfortable as possible.

Comfortable clothing:

During the dosing session, you should wear comfortable, clean clothing that makes you feel as comfortable as possible (e.g., yoga or workout clothes). It is possible to change clothes on site.

What should you bring to the dosing session?

- After the dosing session, you will spend the night at the study center. Remember to bring the things you need for this (a change of clothes, toothbrush, etc.).
- During the dosing session, you will spend most of your time lying down. A comfortable, not too warm blanket and comfortable pillows can help a lot to feel comfortable and protected. You are welcome to bring your own blanket and pillows. Otherwise, we will provide you with both.
- Slippers or non-slip socks (for the way to the bathroom).
- If you wish, you can bring one or more small items with personal significance that you would like to have with you during the dosing session (e.g. photos, pictures, jewelry, lucky charms, etc.).

Provided by us

- Meals, snacks and drinks
- Blindfold and headphones
- Blankets and pillows
- Writing and painting utensils
- Some selected books and illustrated books for the evening after the dosing session

Procedure of the dosing session

Medical examination: Before the dosing session begins, you will meet the study doctor for a medical examination. Here, any changes in health and possible changes in medication intake are discussed, and vital signs such as breathing and heart activity are checked. You will also give a urine sample.

Arrival at the meeting room: After the medical assessment, you will go to the meeting room and be greeted by your two therapists. As already discussed, the therapists will first ask you to agree to the following points again:

1. They undertake to spend the night at the study center after taking the substance and to remain there until after the end of the integration session the following day. You can then leave the study center.
2. They undertake not to harm themselves or others until they leave the study center.
3. You agree to contact the study staff and/or call the emergency number (112) in the event of suicidal thoughts during the entire study participation.

Substance intake: At the beginning of the dosing session, you will be given a capsule that contains either psilocybin in high doses, psilocybin in low doses, or a placebo (nicotinamide). All capsules look the same. Neither you nor the study staff know what substance and dosage you are receiving. You take the capsule orally with a glass of water.

- After taking the substance, your therapists will ask you to lie down, put on the blindfold and put on the headphones. As a rule, you will spend most of the time of the dosing session in this way.
- Through the headphones, you can listen to a playlist of music that has been specially compiled for this purpose. Music is a central part of the treatment. Among other things, the music helps you to focus your attention on your inner experience during the dosing session. The various emotions, sensations, thoughts, memories and images that music can trigger in you together with the substance are an important part of the treatment.
- If you need to go to the toilet, a therapist of your gender will take you there and wait for you outside the door. The treatment room has its own bathroom.
- Two and three hours after taking the substance, blood will be taken to determine the psilocybin level.

Safety and medical monitoring: Your physical and mental health will be monitored by our team throughout the dosing session.

- During the dosing session, both therapists will be in your room. If one of the therapists has to leave the room for a short time (e.g. to go to the toilet), the other therapist will stay with you. Throughout the dosing session, you will never be left alone.
- During the dosing session, you may experience a variety of intense emotions and body sensations. If this happens, it is by no means an undesirable side effect, but part of the treatment. Try to be as open as possible to all experiences. If you experience severe restlessness or anxiety and need help or gentle support, contact your therapists. The therapists are there for you throughout the session.
- During the preparatory sessions, your therapists have made an agreement with you on physical touch. Depending on the agreement, the therapists will gently touch you on the shoulder, arm or hand if necessary.
- In the course of the dosing session, the therapists will regularly measure your pulse and blood pressure. In addition, blood will be taken from you twice.
- In the unlikely event of a medical emergency, a study physician is available throughout the dosing session. The study doctor may also be one of your therapists. The study doctor may administer antihypertensive or anti-anxiety medication if necessary. In previous studies, however, this has only been necessary extremely rarely.

End of the dosing session: After taking the capsule, you and your therapists will remain in the session room for at least 8 hours. The acute psychotropic effect of the substance will then usually have subsided.

- Before you are escorted to the overnight room, you will complete a few short questionnaires with questions about your experience.
- After 8 hours, your blood pressure and pulse will be measured again. If the values are elevated, the study doctor may decide that you will stay in the meeting room even longer. Your therapists stay in the room with you.
- If you continue to feel significant physical or psychological effects of the substance, stay in the meeting room with your therapists until the effects have completely subsided. The decision that you can be safely discharged into the overnight room lies with the study doctor. In the extremely unlikely event of a medical emergency, the study doctor will arrange for you to be taken to the emergency room.
- Before you are escorted to the overnight room, the study doctor and the lead therapist must agree that this is responsible from a medical and psychological point of view.

Evening and overnight stay

Overnight room:

After the end of the dosing session, you will be accompanied by the study staff to the overnight room. There you will be introduced to the Night Watch. The Night Watch will stay close to you from now until the next morning and will be there for you if you need anything. They will spend the evening and night in the overnight room until the integration session the next morning. For safety reasons, leaving the station for walks or similar is not permitted. The overnight room has its own bathroom.

Visit of support person:

If you have designated a support person, this person can now visit you and, if you wish, can keep you company until 9:30 p.m. at the latest.

Rest:

In the evening after the dosing session, rest and relaxation help to process the experience. Try to keep excitement and distractions low. We recommend that you avoid having extensive or intensive conversations with your support person if possible.

Use of electronic media:

We expressly ask you to refrain from using electronic media (e.g. smartphone, tablet, laptop or television) in the evening after the dosing session, or to limit it to the absolute minimum. This important phase should be dedicated to silent reflection on the experience and should not be disturbed by distractions if possible.

Written summary of your experience:

Your therapists will ask you to prepare a written summary of your experience the evening after the dosing session. This is an important part of the treatment, as memories of the experience can otherwise fade quickly. We recommend that you write down your memories as comprehensively as possible. In addition to written notes, making sketches, pictures, short poems, etc. can also help to consolidate the memory of what you have experienced. Pens and paper are available in the overnight room. Please bring your summary to the integration session with your therapists the next morning.

Possible after-effects:

You may experience after-effects such as mood swings or strong emotions in the evening after the dosing session, or you may experience sleep disturbances. This is usually not a cause for concern, and you can always contact the night watch if you need to talk. Headaches can also occur as an after-effect. If necessary, you will receive a suitable painkiller from the night watch. Be sure to contact the night watch if you experience highly stressful emotions, severely depressed moods, suicidal thoughts or hallucinations. In this case, the night guard can contact the study doctor.

If you have any questions or concerns in advance of your dosing session, please do not hesitate to contact the study staff!

Appendix I: Dosing Session Checklists

Dosing Session Checklists (Page 1)

Patient (ID)	Date	Leading therapist	Co-Therapist

Dosing session 1

Dosing session 2

Before the patient arrives, check:	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Setup Bed, armchairs, table, vase (with fresh flowers), carpet, art pieces, potted plant
<input type="checkbox"/>	Door sign "Do not disturb" or similar; conspicuous and legible attached to the outer door
<input type="checkbox"/>	Clock with minute display
<input type="checkbox"/>	Lighting Pleasant color temperature; Brightness dimmable
<input type="checkbox"/>	Blankets and pillows Ready to hand and clean
<input type="checkbox"/>	Music system Tablet, playlist, speakers, headphones, etc. ready to use; Volume appropriate
<input type="checkbox"/>	Equipment for video/audio recording Ready to use and powered on (if applicable)
<input type="checkbox"/>	Blindfold Ready to hand and clean
<input type="checkbox"/>	Snacks and drinks e.g. bananas, apples, nuts and berries, still water, orange juice, decaffeinated tea
<input type="checkbox"/>	Bucket Ready to hand and out of sight
<input type="checkbox"/>	Study substance Ready to hand (with container for administration)
<input type="checkbox"/>	Emergency medication Lorazepam 1-2 mg (IV if necessary): tablets, orodispersible tablets or IV injection Risperidone 2 mg or Olanzapine 10 mg: Tablets Metoclopramide 10 mg tablets, up to 30 mg/d: tablets Nitrendipine (Bayotensin®) 5 mg vial: oral solution Ibuprofen 600 mg, up to 2400 mg/d: tablets
<input type="checkbox"/>	Forms and documents Appendix D, J, K, L, M
<input type="checkbox"/>	Envelopes (3x) To store the completed questionnaires on blinding and music
<input type="checkbox"/>	Questionnaires Psychometric tests and questionnaires to record blinding (Appendix N)
<input type="checkbox"/>	Medical Equipment Blood pressure cuff, stethoscope; Ready to hand and out of sight
<input type="checkbox"/>	Writing and painting materials 5 pages A4 paper, pencil, colored pencils
<input type="checkbox"/>	Overnight room and night watch Available/Ready

Dosing Session Checklists (Page 3)

Substance administration and main phase of the dosing session During the main phase, the patient is actively encouraged to focus attention on the inner experience. Interactions between patient and therapist should generally be kept to a minimum, but the type and extent of interactions should always be adapted to the needs of the patient.											
<input type="checkbox"/>	Substance administration at (time): <table style="display: inline-table; border-collapse: collapse; vertical-align: middle;"> <tr> <td style="border: 1px solid black; width: 20px; height: 20px; text-align: center;"> </td> <td style="border: 1px solid black; width: 20px; height: 20px; text-align: center;"> </td> <td style="padding: 0 5px;">:</td> <td style="border: 1px solid black; width: 20px; height: 20px; text-align: center;"> </td> <td style="border: 1px solid black; width: 20px; height: 20px; text-align: center;"> </td> </tr> <tr> <td colspan="5" style="text-align: center; font-size: small;">(hh:mm)</td> </tr> </table>			:			(hh:mm)				
		:									
(hh:mm)											
<input type="checkbox"/>	Pat. suggest lying down and putting on a blindfold and headphones										
<input type="checkbox"/>	Start a music playlist. The music can be muted, if necessary, but should not be paused. Select music block (90 min) for phase 1: <input type="checkbox"/> 1a <input type="checkbox"/> 1b <input type="checkbox"/> 1c <input type="checkbox"/> 1d <input type="checkbox"/> 1e										
<input type="checkbox"/>	30 minutes after substance administration: Measure pulse and blood pressure and enter them in the cardiovascular monitoring form										
<input type="checkbox"/>	60 minutes after substance administration: Measure pulse and blood pressure and enter them in the cardiovascular monitoring form										
<input type="checkbox"/>	90 minutes after substance administration: Measure pulse and blood pressure and enter them in the cardiovascular monitoring form										
<input type="checkbox"/>	approx. 90 min after substance administration: Select music block (90 min) for phase 2: <input type="checkbox"/> 2a <input type="checkbox"/> 2b <input type="checkbox"/> 2c <input type="checkbox"/> 2d <input type="checkbox"/> 2e										
<input type="checkbox"/>	2 hours after substance administration: Measure pulse and blood pressure and enter them in the cardiovascular monitoring form										
<input type="checkbox"/>	2 h after substance administration: Take blood										
<input type="checkbox"/>	3 h after substance administration: Take blood										
<input type="checkbox"/>	approx. 3 hours after substance administration: Select music block (90 min) for phase 3: <input type="checkbox"/> 3a <input type="checkbox"/> 3b <input type="checkbox"/> 3c <input type="checkbox"/> 3d <input type="checkbox"/> 3e										
<input type="checkbox"/>	4 hours after substance administration: Measure pulse and blood pressure and enter them in the cardiovascular monitoring form										
<input type="checkbox"/>	approx. 4:30 h after substance: Select music block (90 min) for phase 4: <input type="checkbox"/> 4a <input type="checkbox"/> 4b <input type="checkbox"/> 4c <input type="checkbox"/> 4d <input type="checkbox"/> 4e										
<input type="checkbox"/>	6 h after substance administration: Measure pulse and blood pressure and enter them in the cardiovascular monitoring form										
<input type="checkbox"/>	approx. 6 h after substance administration: end of the music playlist										

Notes:

Dosing Session Checklists (Page 4)

Appendix J: Dosing Session Monitoring Form
(may be substituted by an overarching Adverse Event Log)

Dosing Session Monitoring Form

Patient (ID)	Date	Leading therapist	Co-Therapist					
			<input type="checkbox"/> Dosing session #1 <input type="checkbox"/> Dosing session #2					
			<table style="margin: auto;"> <tr> <td style="border: 1px solid black; width: 20px; height: 20px;"></td> <td style="border: 1px solid black; width: 20px; height: 20px;"></td> <td style="font-size: 24px; vertical-align: middle;">:</td> <td style="border: 1px solid black; width: 20px; height: 20px;"></td> <td style="border: 1px solid black; width: 20px; height: 20px;"></td> </tr> </table> Time of substance administration (hh:mm)			:		
		:						

The following events are listed to monitor the safety of the patient throughout the dosing session. This form is used by therapists to document adverse events and follow-up measures. All adverse events can be identified by self-report of the patient or by observation of the therapists.

Note: All events that meet the criteria for an adverse event must be documented in the observation form. Any concomitant medication administered must be recorded in the electronic study documentation (eCRF). The documentation of adverse events and medication administration is completed by the study coordinator in cooperation with the therapists and the study doctor.

The following key is used to encode typical adverse events:

Keys	Event	Description
1	Headache	Pain in the area of the head and/or upper neck
2	Nausea	Any occurrence of nausea, indicated by restless stomach or nausea
3	Increased blood pressure	Elevated blood pressure, defined as systolic blood pressure > 140 mmHg or diastolic blood pressure > 90 mmHg with three separate readings and medication needs
4	Increased heart rate	Increased pulse, defined as pulse > 100 bpm and medication requirement
5	Vomiting	Vomiting
6	Psychological distress or restlessness	Psychological stress or restlessness that does not respond to attempts at calming down on the part of the therapist
7	Physical discomfort	Any physical symptom that could indicate a medical emergency (e.g., cardiac events with chest tightness, pain, and shortness of breath) must be reported to the study physician immediately. In an acute emergency, the emergency number (112) must be dialed.
8	Other/Miscellaneous	Any other physical or psychological event that is worrying, clinically significant and may require medical attention or evaluation by the study doctor. A detailed description must be provided.

Event (key)	Start (hh:mm)	Resolution (hh:mm)	Description	Intervention required	Course
	:	:		<input type="checkbox"/> No intervention required <input type="checkbox"/> Contacted Study Doctor <input type="checkbox"/> emergency medication <input type="checkbox"/> Medical care <input type="checkbox"/> Psychiatric Care <input type="checkbox"/> Miscellaneous (mention in description)	<input type="checkbox"/> Recovered / Resolved <input type="checkbox"/> Recovering / Resolving <input type="checkbox"/> Not recovered / Not resolved <input type="checkbox"/> Recovered with sequelae <input type="checkbox"/> Fatal
	:	:		<input type="checkbox"/> No intervention required <input type="checkbox"/> Contacted Study Doctor <input type="checkbox"/> emergency medication <input type="checkbox"/> Medical care <input type="checkbox"/> Psychiatric Care <input type="checkbox"/> Miscellaneous (mention in description)	<input type="checkbox"/> Recovered / Resolved <input type="checkbox"/> Recovering / Resolving <input type="checkbox"/> Not recovered / Not resolved <input type="checkbox"/> Recovered with sequelae <input type="checkbox"/> Fatal
	:	:		<input type="checkbox"/> No intervention required <input type="checkbox"/> Contacted Study Doctor <input type="checkbox"/> emergency medication <input type="checkbox"/> Medical care <input type="checkbox"/> Psychiatric Care <input type="checkbox"/> Miscellaneous (mention in description)	<input type="checkbox"/> Recovered / Resolved <input type="checkbox"/> Recovering / Resolving <input type="checkbox"/> Not recovered / Not resolved <input type="checkbox"/> Recovered with sequelae <input type="checkbox"/> Fatal

1 = headache; 2 = nausea; 3 = increased blood pressure; 4 = increased heart rate; 5 = vomiting; 6 = psychological distress or restlessness;
 7 = Physical discomfort; 8 = Other/Miscellaneous

Page _____ by _____

Appendix K: AHA Cuff Size Recommendations

AHA recommendations on blood pressure cuff sizes

The American Heart Association (AHA) recommends blood pressure cuff sizes below. Before starting the dosing session, ensure that all cuff sizes are available.

Arm circumference	Recommended cuff size
22 – 26 cm	12 x 22 cm (small adult)
27 – 34 cm	16 x 30 cm (adult)
35 – 44 cm	16 x 36 cm (large adult)
45 – 52 cm	16 x 42 cm (adult thigh)

Source: Pickering TG, Hall JE, Appel LJ, Falkner BE, Graves J, Hill MN, et al.; Subcommittee of Professional and Public Education of the American Heart Association Council on High Blood Pressure Research. Recommendations for blood pressure measurement in humans and experimental animals. Part 1: blood pressure measurement in humans. Hypertension 2005; 45:142–61.

As a rule of thumb, the length of the cuff must be at least 80% of the upper arm circumference. The width of the cuff must be at least 40% of the arm circumference.

The midline of the cuff (usually labeled "artery mark") should be positioned above the brachial artery above the antecubital fossa. Ideally, there should be a distance of 2 to 3 cm between the lower edge of the cuff and the antecubital fossa for the stethoscope (in the case of manual blood pressure measurement), unless this would require a cuff that is too small.

Before the first measurement, the patient should lie down for at least 10 minutes. During this time, the patient should relax and not have any conversations. At the time of measurement, make sure the patient is not talking, feet are not crossed, and the arm is supported at heart level. If you have multiple measurements, make sure there are at least 5 minutes between each measurement.

Appendix L: Cardiovascular Monitoring Instructions

Instructions for cardiovascular monitoring (before substance administration)

Cardiovascular monitoring before substance administration:		
Blood pressure and pulse measurement must be carried out before the substance is administered ¹ . In this case, the AHA recommendations on blood pressure cuff sizes (Appendix K) must be observed. All blood pressure and pulse measurements must be carried out by study staff trained in this area and documented in the form provided for this purpose (Appendix M). The following safety parameters have been defined:		
Measurement result (blood pressure)	Rating	Instructions
Syst. blood pressure < 140 mmHg and Diast. Blood pressure < 90 mmHg	Acceptable	Substance can be administered.
Syst. Blood pressure ≥ 140 mmHg or Diast. Blood pressure ≥ 90 mmHg	Increased	Measure again after at least 5 minutes to determine if it is a temporary increase. The patient should continue to lie down.
		If a new measurement yields acceptable values, the substance can be administered.
		If three consecutive measurements at least 5 minutes apart show elevated values ² , the study physician must be consulted for further observation. At the discretion of the study physician and the principal investigator, the dosing session may be postponed ³ .
Measurement result (pulse)	Rating	Instructions
≥ 50 bpm and ≤ 100 bpm	Acceptable	Substance can be administered.
< 50 bpm or > 100 bpm	Slows or increases	Measure again after at least 5 minutes to determine if it is a temporary slowdown/increase. The patient should continue to lie down.
		If a new measurement yields acceptable values, the substance can be administered.
		If three consecutive measurements at least 5 minutes apart show slowed/elevated levels ² , the study physician must be consulted for further observation. At the discretion of the study physician and the principal investigator, the dosing session may be postponed ³ .

¹ The patient must lie down for at least 10 minutes before the initial blood pressure and pulse measurement can be taken.

² Three slowed/elevated readings indicate an adverse event (hypertension/bradycardia/tachycardia) that must be documented in the appropriate form (Appendix J).

³ The dosing session may be postponed at the discretion of the study physician and the study director. If > 7 days have elapsed since the baseline survey, all baseline measures must be repeated. If > 35 days have passed since consent, the patient must go through the screening again and give consent again. If > 90 days have passed since screening, the patient must be excluded from participating in the study.

Instructions for cardiovascular monitoring (after substance administration)

Cardiovascular monitoring at the end of the dosing session:	
Blood pressure and pulse measurements must be taken 30, 60, 90 and 120 minutes as well as 4, 6, 7 and 8 hours after the substance has been administered. In this case, the AHA recommendations on blood pressure cuff sizes (Appendix K) must be observed. All blood pressure and pulse measurements must be carried out by study staff trained in this area and documented in the form provided for this purpose (Appendix M). The following safety parameters have been defined:	
Measurement result (blood pressure)	Instructions
Syst. blood pressure \leq 170 mmHg and Diast. Blood pressure \leq 95 mmHg	No further observation required. The next measurement will take place at the predetermined time.
Syst. blood pressure $>$ 170 and $<$ 200 mmHg or Diast. Blood pressure $>$ 95 and $<$ 110 mmHg	If three consecutive measurements at least 5 minutes apart show elevated values ¹ , the study physician must be informed.
Syst. Blood pressure \geq 200 mmHg or Diast. Blood pressure \geq 110 mmHg	The study physician must be consulted for assessment and further observation. Medication decisions ² are subject to the clinical judgment of the study physician. The following medication suggestions are recommendations: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nitroglycerin 0.4 mg sublingually • If blood pressure does not drop below the threshold after 5 minutes, nitroglycerin 0.4 mg sublingually again • If blood pressure does not drop below the threshold after another 5 minutes, nitroglycerin 0.4 mg sublingually again (maximum dose 0.4 mg x 3) • If blood pressure remains \geq 200 mmHg (syst.) or \geq 110 mmHg (diast.), oral clonidine (e.g., 0.1 mg) may be administered orally at the discretion of the study physician. The study doctor must assess whether the patient needs to be taken to the emergency room.
Measurement result (pulse)	Instructions
$<$ 50 bpm	Two repetitions of measurements after 5 minutes each. If three measurements show values $<$ 50 bpm ¹ , the study physician must be informed.
\geq 50 bpm and \leq 110 bpm	No further observation required. The next measurement will take place at the predetermined time.
$>$ 110 bpm	Two repetitions of measurements after 5 minutes each. If three measurements show values $>$ 110 bpm ¹ , the study doctor must be informed.

¹ Three slowed/elevated readings indicate an adverse event (hypertension/bradycardia/tachycardia) that must be documented in the appropriate form (Appendix J).

² All medications administered must be recorded in the study documentation (CRF).

Instructions for cardiovascular monitoring (end of dosing session)

Cardiovascular monitoring at the end of the dosing session		
<p>At the end of the dosing session (at least 8 hours after substance administration), a blood pressure and pulse measurement must be taken before the patient can be taken to the overnight room. In this case, the AHA recommendations on blood pressure cuff sizes (Appendix K) must be observed. All blood pressure and pulse measurements must be carried out by study staff trained in this area and documented in the form provided for this purpose (Appendix M). The following safety parameters have been defined:</p>		
Measurement result (blood pressure)	Measurement result (pulse)	Instructions
Syst. blood pressure < 140 mmHg and Diast. Blood pressure < 90 mmHg	>50 and < 100 bpm	No further observation required. The patient can be taken to the overnight room.
Syst. Blood pressure ≥ 140 mmHg or Diast. Blood pressure ≥ 90 mmHg	≥ 100 bmp	Measure again after at least 5 minutes to determine if it is a temporary increase. The patient should continue to lie down. The measurement can be repeated up to three times, at intervals of at least 5 minutes.
Syst. Blood pressure ≥ 140 mmHg or Diast. Blood pressure ≥ 90 mmHg	≥ 100 bmp	<p>If three consecutive measurements are syst. Blood pressure ≥ 140 or diast. Blood pressure ≥ 90 mmHg and/or pulse > 100 bpm, the study physician must be consulted for evaluation and further observation.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The patient may be discharged for transfer to the overnight stay if the study doctor considers the measured values to be harmless. Otherwise, the patient must remain in the meeting room for further observation. At the discretion of the study physician, medication may be administered. • If the measured values drop to a safe level due to waiting or medication, the patient can be discharged for transfer to the overnight room. Otherwise, the study doctor must assess whether the patient needs to be taken to the emergency room.

Appendix M: Cardiovascular Monitoring Form

Cardiovascular Monitoring Form

Patient (ID)

Dosing session #1

Dosing session #2

All blood pressure measurements must be documented with the initials of the person taking the measurement.				
_____	<div style="border: 1px solid black; display: inline-block; width: 20px; height: 20px;"></div> : <div style="border: 1px solid black; display: inline-block; width: 20px; height: 20px;"></div>	<div style="border: 1px solid black; display: inline-block; width: 30px; height: 20px;"></div>	<div style="border: 1px solid black; display: inline-block; width: 30px; height: 20px;"></div>	<div style="border: 1px solid black; display: inline-block; width: 30px; height: 20px;"></div>
Initials	Time (hh:mm)	Syst. Blood pressure (mmHg)	Diast. Blood pressure (mmHg)	Pulse (bpm)
_____	<div style="border: 1px solid black; display: inline-block; width: 20px; height: 20px;"></div> : <div style="border: 1px solid black; display: inline-block; width: 20px; height: 20px;"></div>	<div style="border: 1px solid black; display: inline-block; width: 30px; height: 20px;"></div>	<div style="border: 1px solid black; display: inline-block; width: 30px; height: 20px;"></div>	<div style="border: 1px solid black; display: inline-block; width: 30px; height: 20px;"></div>
Initials	Time (hh:mm)	Syst. Blood pressure (mmHg)	Diast. Blood pressure (mmHg)	Pulse (bpm)
_____	<div style="border: 1px solid black; display: inline-block; width: 20px; height: 20px;"></div> : <div style="border: 1px solid black; display: inline-block; width: 20px; height: 20px;"></div>	<div style="border: 1px solid black; display: inline-block; width: 30px; height: 20px;"></div>	<div style="border: 1px solid black; display: inline-block; width: 30px; height: 20px;"></div>	<div style="border: 1px solid black; display: inline-block; width: 30px; height: 20px;"></div>
Initials	Time (hh:mm)	Syst. Blood pressure (mmHg)	Diast. Blood pressure (mmHg)	Pulse (bpm)
_____	<div style="border: 1px solid black; display: inline-block; width: 20px; height: 20px;"></div> : <div style="border: 1px solid black; display: inline-block; width: 20px; height: 20px;"></div>	<div style="border: 1px solid black; display: inline-block; width: 30px; height: 20px;"></div>	<div style="border: 1px solid black; display: inline-block; width: 30px; height: 20px;"></div>	<div style="border: 1px solid black; display: inline-block; width: 30px; height: 20px;"></div>
Initials	Time (hh:mm)	Syst. Blood pressure (mmHg)	Diast. Blood pressure (mmHg)	Pulse (bpm)
_____	<div style="border: 1px solid black; display: inline-block; width: 20px; height: 20px;"></div> : <div style="border: 1px solid black; display: inline-block; width: 20px; height: 20px;"></div>	<div style="border: 1px solid black; display: inline-block; width: 30px; height: 20px;"></div>	<div style="border: 1px solid black; display: inline-block; width: 30px; height: 20px;"></div>	<div style="border: 1px solid black; display: inline-block; width: 30px; height: 20px;"></div>
Initials	Time (hh:mm)	Syst. Blood pressure (mmHg)	Diast. Blood pressure (mmHg)	Pulse (bpm)
_____	<div style="border: 1px solid black; display: inline-block; width: 20px; height: 20px;"></div> : <div style="border: 1px solid black; display: inline-block; width: 20px; height: 20px;"></div>	<div style="border: 1px solid black; display: inline-block; width: 30px; height: 20px;"></div>	<div style="border: 1px solid black; display: inline-block; width: 30px; height: 20px;"></div>	<div style="border: 1px solid black; display: inline-block; width: 30px; height: 20px;"></div>
Initials	Time (hh:mm)	Syst. Blood pressure (mmHg)	Diast. Blood pressure (mmHg)	Pulse (bpm)
_____	<div style="border: 1px solid black; display: inline-block; width: 20px; height: 20px;"></div> : <div style="border: 1px solid black; display: inline-block; width: 20px; height: 20px;"></div>	<div style="border: 1px solid black; display: inline-block; width: 30px; height: 20px;"></div>	<div style="border: 1px solid black; display: inline-block; width: 30px; height: 20px;"></div>	<div style="border: 1px solid black; display: inline-block; width: 30px; height: 20px;"></div>
Initials	Time (hh:mm)	Syst. Blood pressure (mmHg)	Diast. Blood pressure (mmHg)	Pulse (bpm)
_____	<div style="border: 1px solid black; display: inline-block; width: 20px; height: 20px;"></div> : <div style="border: 1px solid black; display: inline-block; width: 20px; height: 20px;"></div>	<div style="border: 1px solid black; display: inline-block; width: 30px; height: 20px;"></div>	<div style="border: 1px solid black; display: inline-block; width: 30px; height: 20px;"></div>	<div style="border: 1px solid black; display: inline-block; width: 30px; height: 20px;"></div>
Initials	Time (hh:mm)	Syst. Blood pressure (mmHg)	Diast. Blood pressure (mmHg)	Pulse (bpm)
_____	<div style="border: 1px solid black; display: inline-block; width: 20px; height: 20px;"></div> : <div style="border: 1px solid black; display: inline-block; width: 20px; height: 20px;"></div>	<div style="border: 1px solid black; display: inline-block; width: 30px; height: 20px;"></div>	<div style="border: 1px solid black; display: inline-block; width: 30px; height: 20px;"></div>	<div style="border: 1px solid black; display: inline-block; width: 30px; height: 20px;"></div>
Initials	Time (hh:mm)	Syst. Blood pressure (mmHg)	Diast. Blood pressure (mmHg)	Pulse (bpm)

Appendix N: Blinding and Music Questionnaire

Patient (ID)	Date

- Dosing session 1 questionnaire completed patient
 Dosing session 2 by: therapist (initials): _____

This short questionnaire is about your assessment of which preparation was administered in today's dosing session.

Please first assess whether psilocybin was administered in today's session. If you are not sure, please choose the answer that you think is most accurate. Was psilocybin (25 mg or 5 mg) administered in today's session?

- Yes, today psilocybin (25 mg or 5 mg) was administered
 No, placebo (nicotinamide) was administered today

Please indicate how confident you are in this assessment. To do this, mark the place on the following line that corresponds to **your assessment with a vertical line**. How sure are you in your above assessment of which substance was administered today?

Not sure at all |—————| **Completely sure**

Next, please assess whether a **high** dose of psilocybin (25 mg) was administered in today's session. If you are not sure, please choose the answer that you think is most accurate. Was a high dose of psilocybin (25 mg) administered in today's session?

- Yes, a **high** dose of psilocybin (25 mg) was administered today
 No, today either a low dose of psilocybin (5 mg) or placebo (nicotinamide)

How sure are you in your assessment above of whether a high dose of psilocybin was administered today?

Not sure at all |—————| **Completely sure**

We would also like to ask you how you experienced the musical accompaniment during today's dosing session.

Did you like the music overall?

NO, not at all |—————| **YES**, very much

Did you like the moments of silence?

NO, not at all |—————| **YES**, very much

Do you think the music was helpful overall?

NO, not at all |—————| **YES**, very much

Appendix O: Integration 1a and 2a Checklist

Checklist Integration 1a and 2a

Patient (ID)	Date	Leading therapist	Co-Therapist

- Integration 1a
- Integration 2a

Procedure of the meeting:		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Start video/audio recording according to the patient's consent (if applicable)	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Provide an overview of the structure of the session	~5 min
<input type="checkbox"/>	Obtain written summary of substance experience	~15-35 min
<input type="checkbox"/>	Gain a comprehensive view of the substance experience	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Establish connections between substance experience and the patient's life context	~15-35 min
<input type="checkbox"/>	Stimulate reflections on the integration of insights gained and experienced changes of perspective	~15-35 min
<input type="checkbox"/>	Clarify organizational matters: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Confirm emergency and contact information • Confirm the date for the next integration session 	~5 min
<input type="checkbox"/>	End Session	~5 min

Safety monitoring*:	
<input type="checkbox"/> yes <input type="checkbox"/> no	Indications of exacerbation of depressive symptoms
<input type="checkbox"/> yes <input type="checkbox"/> no	Indications of suicidal tendencies
<input type="checkbox"/> yes <input type="checkbox"/> no	Indications of psychotic symptoms
<input type="checkbox"/> yes <input type="checkbox"/> no	Evidence of Hallucinogen Persisting Perceptual Disorder (HPPD)
<input type="checkbox"/> yes <input type="checkbox"/> no	Other notes: _____

*Each item answered "yes" must be documented in the session summary and reported to the study director.

Completed by therapist	Date of completion	Signature therapist
------------------------	--------------------	---------------------

Appendix P: Integration 1b and 2b Checklist

Checklist Integration 1b and 2b

Patient (ID)	Date	Leading therapist	Co-Therapist

- Integration 1b
- Integration 2b

Procedure of the meeting:		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Start video/audio recording according to the patient's consent (if applicable)	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Clarify open questions and give an overview of the structure of the meeting	~5 min
<input type="checkbox"/>	Discuss changes in quality of life and experience of depression	~30-70 min
<input type="checkbox"/>	Develop a longer-term plan for ongoing integration	~10-30 min
<input type="checkbox"/>	Clarify organizational matters: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Confirm emergency and contact information • Confirm the date for the next prep session (if applicable) 	~5 min
<input type="checkbox"/>	Integration 2b only: Adoption	~10 min

Safety monitoring*:	
<input type="checkbox"/> yes <input type="checkbox"/> no	Indications of exacerbation of depressive symptoms
<input type="checkbox"/> yes <input type="checkbox"/> no	Indications of suicidal tendencies
<input type="checkbox"/> yes <input type="checkbox"/> no	Indications of psychotic symptoms
<input type="checkbox"/> yes <input type="checkbox"/> no	Evidence of Hallucinogen Persisting Perceptual Disorder (HPPD)
<input type="checkbox"/> yes <input type="checkbox"/> no	Other notes: _____

*Each item answered "yes" must be documented in the session summary and reported to the study director.

Completed by therapist	Date of completion	Signature therapist
------------------------	--------------------	---------------------

Appendix Q: Biographical Questionnaire¹

¹ Version 1.1 (March 19, 2021). Adapted from: Neudeck & Mühlig (2013). *Therapy Tools Behavioural Therapy*. Beltz.

Life Questionnaire

Name: Date:

To tailor the treatment to your individual needs, we ask you to complete this questionnaire. First of all, we would like to get an overview of your life story as well as your current personal and social situation. We will then deal in more detail with the different areas of life in a personal conversation. Please answer all questions yourself and do not ask anyone (e.g. partner, friends) to help you answer them. The careful processing of the questions makes it easier for us to respond well to them during treatment.

Please describe in which areas of life your symptoms affect you.

.....
.....
.....
.....

What experiences have you had in the past with psychiatric and/or psychotherapeutic treatments?

.....
.....
.....
.....
.....

What else have you tried to do about your complaints so far?

.....
.....
.....
.....
.....
.....

What explanation do you have for your complaints?

.....
.....
.....
.....
.....

Since the beginning of the problem, have there been times when your symptoms did not occur or only rarely?

.....
.....
.....
.....

Please write down your three biggest fears:

- (1)
- (2)
- (3)

Please write down your three biggest wishes:

- (1)
- (2)
- (3)

What are the most important values in your life?

- (1)
- (2)
- (3)

What are your expectations regarding the treatment in this study?

.....
.....
.....

Please formulate a preliminary order for treatment. What do you want to achieve? (Please be as specific as possible)

.....
.....
.....

What should not happen under any circumstances during treatment?

.....
.....
.....

In your opinion, what characterizes a good relationship between therapist and patient?

.....
.....
.....

Please describe your "normal" daily routine in keywords:

Morning:
.....

Afternoon:
.....

Evening:
.....

To what extent would you describe your childhood as happy?

Not at all **Very happy**
happy
1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8

Were there any abnormalities in your childhood or any typical behaviours that were attributed to you as a child?

.....
.....
.....

How was the contact with your classmates? What role did they have at school?

.....
.....
.....
.....

What was your general health like during your childhood and adolescence? If necessary, please mention serious illnesses, prolonged hospital stays or accidents during childhood and adolescence.

.....
.....
.....
.....
.....

Please describe how you see yourself as a child in retrospect.

.....
.....
.....

Please describe how you see yourself as a young person in retrospect.

Positive:

.....

Negative:

.....

Please describe how you see yourself as an adult today.

Positive:

.....

Negative:

.....

Do you make friends quickly? Do your friendships last long?

.....

With whom do you spend most of your free time (please tick)?

Alone

Rather a lot	_____	Rather not much
---------------------	-------	------------------------

With partner

Rather a lot	_____	Rather not much
---------------------	-------	------------------------

With relatives

Rather a lot	_____	Rather not much
---------------------	-------	------------------------

With your own friends

Rather a lot	_____	Rather not much
---------------------	-------	------------------------

With mutual friends of you and your partner

Rather a lot	_____	Rather not much
---------------------	-------	------------------------

Who do you currently live with?

.....

Marital status (multiple information possible):

single

engaged

married

- remarried
- living separately
- divorced
- widowed
- unmarried, living with partner
- stable partner relationship, but living in separate households
- not a stable partner relationship, but sexual contacts
- neither a stable partnership nor sexual contacts

How do you live?

- House
- Apartment
- Subletting
- Other:

How many children do you have? Please list in chronological order: (use the back if necessary)

(1) Name: Age: years Gender: w m d

Relationship:

.....

(2) Name: Age: years Gender: w m d

Relationship:

.....

(3) Name: Age: years Gender: w m d

Relationship:

.....

Please provide information about your family background:

Mother	Father
Name:	Name:
Age:	Age:
Occupation:	Occupation:

Health:	Health:
If deceased, cause:	If deceased, cause:
How old were you at that time?	How old were you at that time?

Did your parents live together or was there a separation / divorce?

.....

.....

Where did you grow up? Were there moves? Please note chronologically (if necessary, use the back).

Age (from to)	Place of residence

Describe how you experienced your mother during your childhood and adolescence.

.....

.....

Describe how you experienced your father during your childhood and adolescence.

.....

.....

What is your relationship with your mother / father like at the moment?

Mother:
.....

Father:
.....

If you have siblings, please indicate the age of your siblings and briefly describe your relationship with them in your childhood or today. (Use the back if necessary)

(1) Name: Age: years

- only same biological mother
- only same biological father

Relationship in the past:

.....
.....

Current relationship:

.....
.....

(2) Name: Age: years

- only same biological mother
- only same biological father

Relationship in the past:

.....
.....

Current relationship:

.....
.....

(2) Name: Age: years

- only common mother
- only common father

Relationship in the past:

.....
.....

Current relationship:

.....
.....

Please describe how you experienced your family during your childhood and adolescence:

.....
.....

Please describe the parenting style in the family:

.....
.....

Were there any important events or experiences during your childhood that could be important for therapy?

.....
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.....

What was your parents' relationship like?

.....
.....
.....
.....
.....
.....
.....

Do you have a stepfather/stepmother? How old were you when you remarried?

.....
.....

To what extent could you feel safe and secure in your family?

Not at all 2 3 4 5 6 7 **Very much**
1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8

Do you belong to a religious community or denomination? If so, which one?

.....

To what extent do you currently feel connected to a religious community?
(Please tick)

Not at all 2 3 4 5 6 7 **Very much**
1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8

Do you believe in life after death? If so, what is your idea of it?

.....
.....
.....

Do you deal with the topics of death and dying? (Please tick)

Not at all **Very much**
1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8

Can you enjoy your sexuality? (Please tick)

Not at all **Very much**
1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8

When and with whom did you have your first sexual contacts?

.....
.....
.....

Were or are there any unpleasant sexual experiences for you? Has sexuality (including masturbation) ever been associated with fear or guilt for you?

.....
.....
.....

For women only:

Age at first period: years

Are the periods regular? Yes no Duration of period: Days

Are you in pain? Yes no

Does your period affect your mood? Yes no

If necessary, provide information about previous marriages or partnerships that you consider important:

.....
.....
.....

If you do not have a permanent partner at the moment, please make a cross here and go to the next point (**school career**).

Details of your current partner:

Age: years Gender: w m d

Duration of partnership: years

Occupation:

What do you see positively about the relationship, what negatively?

Pros:
.....

Cons:
.....

How does your partner deal with your depression?

.....
.....
.....

School career

Age at start of school: years

Age at time of leaving school: years

Age at start of career: years

What school-leaving certificate do you have?

What were your strengths at school?

.....
.....

What were your weaknesses at school?

.....
.....

Please list your most important professional activities and training.

.....
.....
.....
.....
.....

Are you satisfied with the work you are currently doing? Yes no

Why are you satisfied or dissatisfied?

.....
.....

Important life events

Please enter particularly important events in your life in the following table in the form of keywords. Please also indicate your (approximate) age. For events that lasted longer, you can specify age periods (from-to).

	Age	Event
Childhood to Back to school		
Primary school years		

Puberty		
16-25 years of age		
Adulthood		

Appendix R: Music Playlists – Blocks with Individual Tracks

Music Playlists – Blocks with individual tracks

Block 1a				
Track No	Track Name	Album Name	Artist Names	Duration
1	At Ease	At Ease	Steve Gorn	00:05:32
2	In the Androgynous Dark	Charcoal	Brambles	00:04:43
3	Opening	Precipice	Nathaniel Bartlett	00:06:31
4	þÚ Ert Jörðin	...And They Have Escaped the Weight of Darkness	Ólafur Arnalds	00:04:34
5	Calm Upon You (Hang Solo)	Calm Upon You	Ravid	00:05:01
6	Djansa	The First Annual Fundraiser - War Child	Daniel Waples	00:02:06
7	Call Within (Instrumental Meditation With Bamboo Flute; Ukulele; Voice & Nature Sounds)	Call Within	Manose	00:06:23
8	Oltremare	Oltremare	Floraleda Sacchi; Ludovico Einaudi	00:11:53
9	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks		00:06:00
10	Alto Paraíso	Aukai	Aukai	00:02:26
11	Sacred Fire	ORIGIRO	Zen Baboon	00:07:46
12	Illusion Of Time	Illusion Of Time	Daniel Avery; Alessandro Cortini	00:04:22
13	Keep	Felt (Special Edition)	Nils Frahm	00:03:25
14	Path 5 (delta)	From Sleep	Max Richter; Grace Davidson	00:11:14
15	Silence 6 Minutes	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:06:00
16	Full Panther	Long Stories	Amon Tobin	00:03:23
17	Aguas da Amazonia: Japurá River	Philip Glass: Aguas da Amazonia	Philip Glass; Uakti	00:04:44

Block 1b				
Track No	Track Name	Album Name	Artist Names	Duration
1	Translucent Shadow	Coyote Oldman	Under an Ancient Sky	00:06:00
2	Silence 10 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:10
3	Ila Espanoleta	Fantasia para un Gentilhombre	Joaquin Rodrigo	00:05:04
4	Call Within (Instrumental Meditation With Bamboo Flute; Ukulele; Voice & Nature Sounds)	Call Within	Manose	00:06:23
5	Silence 10 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:10
6	In a Landscape	Der Bote	John Cage;Alexei Lubimov	00:08:51
7	Illusion Of Time	Illusion Of Time	Daniel Avery;Alessandro Cortini	00:04:22
8	Silence 10 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:10
9	Ba Ba	Ba Ba Ti Ki Di Do	Sigur Rós	00:06:12
10	Keep	Felt (Special Edition)	Nils Frahm	00:03:25
11	Opening	Precipice	Nathaniel Bartlett	00:06:31
12	Purus River	Aguas da Amazonia	Philip Glass	00:07:43
13	One River	One River	Benjy Wertheimer	00:07:04
14	Silence 10 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:10
15	Devorzhum	Spirit Chaser	Dead Can Dance	00:06:00
16	The Southern Sea	Flying	Garth Stevenson	00:08:59
17	Nanga Parbat	Tibet Nada Himalaya 2	Deuter	00:07:07
18	Grounded	Music to die to	East Forest	00:07:35

Block 1c				
Track No	Track Name	Album Name	Artist Names	Duration
1	In a Landscape	Der Bote	John Cage;Alexei Lubimov	00:08:51
2	Silence 5 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:05
3	Alto Paraíso	Aukai	Aukai	00:02:26
4	Agra	Inside The Taj Mahal	Paul Horn	00:01:39
5	Silence 5 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:05
6	At Night	After Midnight	Annelie	00:09:13
7	Vardani mor voghp - Vardan's lament	The Music of Armenia Sampler	Anonymous;Karineh Hovhannessian	00:03:04
8	Silence 5 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:05
9	Dungtitled	And Their Refinement of the Decline	Stars Of The Lid	00:05:54
10	Silence 5 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:05
11	Oshusanaya	Japanese Masterpieces for the Shakuhachi	Masters Of The Meian-Ryu;Masters of Kimpu-Ryu;Masters of Tozan-Ryu;Masters of Kikusi-Ryu	00:07:11
12	Silence 5 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:05
13	Zenmai	Acid Mt.Fuji (2016 Remaster Deluxe Edition)	Susumu Yokota	00:04:08
14	Moments	Between a Smile and a Tear	Be Svendsen	00:04:57
15	Purus River	Aguas da Amazonia	Philip Glass	00:07:43
16	Silence 5 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:05
17	Mazame (Awakening)	Aquariussssss	Carlos Nino & Friends	00:04:29
18	Symphony No. 3; Op. 36: II. Lento e Largo - Tranquillissimo	Górecki: Symphony No. 3	Henryk Górecki;Dawn Upshaw;London Sinfonietta;David Zinman	00:09:27
19	ÞÚ Ert Jörðin	...And They Have Escaped the Weight of Darkness	Ólafur Arnalds	00:04:34
20	Organ Solo	Dead Man: A Film By Jim Jarmusch	Neil Young	00:01:33
21	Silence 5 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:05
22	1/2 Singing Bowl (Ascension) - Excerpt	Dead Man: A Film By Jim Jarmusch	Jon Hopkins	00:04:31

23	Diving Deeper; Remembering Love	Hearing Music	Joanna Brouk	00:05:33
24	An Ending (Ascent) - Remastered 2019	Apollo: Atmospheres And Soundtracks (Extended Edition)	Brian Eno	00:04:24
25	Silence 5 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:05

Block 1d				
Track No	Track Name	Album Name	Artist Names	Duration
1	Silence 10 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:10
2	The Space Between	The Space Between	Joanna Brouk	00:21:53
3	Silence 10 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:10
4	Iluminar	Ayahuasca (Original Motion Picture Soundtrack)	Poranguí	00:04:52
5	Silence 10 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:10
6	At Night	After Midnight	Annelie	00:09:13
7	Silence 7 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:07
8	Oltremare	Oltremare	Floralada Sacchi;Ludovico Einaudi	00:11:53
9	Calm Upon You (Hang Solo)	Calm Upon You	Ravid	00:05:01
10	Silence 20 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:20
11	In Paradisum	Sacred Treasures IV	The Cambridge Singers	00:03:48
12	Vardani mor voghp - Vardan's lament	The Music of Armenia Sampler	Anonymous;Karineh Hovhannessian	00:03:04
13	Silence 5 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:05
14	In a Landscape	Der Bote	John Cage;Alexei Lubimov	00:08:51
15	Silence 10 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:10
16	Opening	Precipice	Nathaniel Bartlett	00:06:31
17	Calling The Lama From Afar - Part I	Roads Of Blessings - Songs Of Awakening	Lama Gyurme;Jean-Philippe Rykiel	00:09:51
18	Silence 10 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:10
19	Track3a (2waynice)	Playthroughs	Keith Fullerton Whitman	00:05:30
20	Silence 5 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	5,8E-05

Block 1e				
Track No	Track Name	Album Name	Artist Names	Duration
1	Alto Paraíso	Aukai	Aukai	00:02:26
2	Iluminar	Ayahuasca (Original Motion Picture Soundtrack)	Poranguí	00:04:52
3	Call Within (Instrumental Meditation With Bamboo Flute; Ukulele; Voice & Nature Sounds)	Call Within	Manose	00:06:23
4	In a Landscape	Der Bote	John Cage;Alexei Lubimov	00:08:51
5	At Night	After Midnight	Annelie	00:09:13
6	Þú Ert Jörðin	...And They Have Escaped the Weight of Darkness	Ólafur Arnalds	00:04:34
7	Keep	Felt (Special Edition)	Nils Frahm	00:03:25
8	Silence 9 Minutes	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:09:00
9	Vardani mor voghp - Vardan's lament	The Music of Armenia Sampler	Anonymous;Karineh Hovhannessian	00:03:04
10	Calm Upon You (Hang Solo)	Calm Upon You	Ravid	00:05:01
11	At Ease	At Ease	Steve Gorn	00:05:32
12	Opening	Precipice	Nathaniel Bartlett	00:06:31
13	Aguas da Amazonia: Japurá River	Philip Glass: Aguas da Amazonia	Philip Glass;Uakti	00:04:44
14	Silence 9 Minutes	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:09:00
15	Illusion Of Time	Illusion Of Time	Daniel Avery;Alessandro Cortini	00:04:22
16	Moments	Between a Smile and a Tear	Be Svendsen	00:04:57

Block 2a				
Track No	Track Name	Album Name	Artist Names	Duration
1	Silence 10 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:10
2	Rosetti Noise/Crystal Garden And A Coda	The Pavilion Of Dreams	Harold Budd	00:14:20
3	Silence 5 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:05
4	Them	Music for the Motion Picture Victoria	Nils Frahm	00:03:59
5	The Atomium Part 2	Avec Laudenum	Stars Of The Lid	00:10:43
6	Silence 10 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:10
7	Seah Jahan	Inside The Taj Mahal	Paul Horn	00:05:39
8	Silence 10 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:10
9	Letters Of A Traveller	The Chopin Project	Ólafur Arnalds;Alice Sara Ott	00:04:17
10	Silence 10 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:10
11	Silence 5 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:05
12	Dissolving Clouds	Dropsonde	Biosphere	00:04:28
13	Silence 20 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:20
14	El Indio Y la Quena (Melodia Andina)	Yupanqui: La paloma enamorada	Atahualpa Yupanqui, Roberto Aussel, Bénédicte Frénaud	00:03:51
15	Silence 10 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:10
16	Wurzel	Sonne und Wasser	H.Takahashi	00:07:23
17	Silence 20 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:20
18	Xomustar	Buura	Alash Ensemble	00:03:52
19	Wiegenlied	Storyteller	Richard Strauss	00:04:29
20	Silence 10 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:10
21	Purcell : Funeral Sentences for the death of Queen Mary II Z27 : I March	Purcell : Music for Queen Mary (Apex)	Henry Purcell;John Eliot Gardiner;Equale Brass Ensemble;Monteverdi Orchestra	00:02:17
22	Silence 30 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:30
23	Akasha - The Pleasure Of Being One With The Supreme Soul	Tibetan Singing Bowls	Danny Becher	00:09:05

24	Silence 10 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:10
25	Prayer In Passing	Rise	Anoushka Shankar	00:06:21
26	Silence 1 Minute	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:01:00
27	Dream 3 - Short Edit	Sleep (Remixes)	Max Richter;Ben Russell;Yuki Numata Resnick	00:05:25
28	Silence 20 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:20

Block 2b				
Track No	Track Name	Album Name	Artist Names	Duration
1	Silence 10 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:10
2	Wurzel	Sonne und Wasser	H.Takahashi	00:07:23
3	Rothko Chapel 5	Rothko Chapel	Morton Feldman	00:02:53
4	The Atomium Part 2	Avec Laudenum	Stars Of The Lid	00:10:43
5	Silence 10 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:10
6	Rosetti Noise/Crystal Garden And A Coda	The Pavilion Of Dreams	Harold Budd	00:14:20
7	Akasha - The Pleasure Of Being One With The Supreme Soul	Tibetan Singing Bowls	Danny Becher	00:09:05
8	Silence 10 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:10
9	Dream 3 - Short Edit	Sleep (Remixes)	Max Richter;Ben Russell;Yuki Numata Resnick	00:05:25
10	Water Memory 1	Water Memory	Emily A. Sprague	00:07:28
11	Seah Jahan	Inside The Taj Mahal	Paul Horn	00:05:39
12	Dissolving Clouds	Dropsonde	Biosphere	00:04:28
13	Silence 10 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:10
14	Open	Pinô	Otto Totland	00:02:30
15	Silence 20 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:20
16	Magnificat: VI. Esurientes	Rutter: Magnificat	John Rutter;Patricia Forbes;The Cambridge Singers;City of London Sinfonia	00:06:22
17	Silence 10 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:10
18	Pavane pour une infante défunte	Ravel: Orchestral Works	Maurice Ravel	00:06:08
19	Silence 10 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:10
20	Golden Cloud Layers	The Space Between	Joanna Brouk	00:06:36
21	Silence 10 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:10

Block 2c				
Track No	Track Name	Album Name	Artist Names	Duration
1	Silence 20 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:20
2	Prizewinning	The Magic Place	Julianna Barwick	00:06:42
3	The Evil That Never Arrived		Stars of the Lit	00:05:05
4	Letters Of A Traveller	The Chopin Project	Ólafur Arnalds; Alice Sara Ott	00:04:17
5	Silence 20 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:20
6	Teil IV	Der Klang der Offenbarung	Kjartan Sveinsson	00:11:40
7	Them	Music for the Motion Picture Victoria	Nils Frahm	00:03:59
8	Silence 10 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:10
9	Atair	La traversée	Armand Amar	00:06:28
10	Silence 10 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:10
11	Coucher de Lune	Illumination of the Heart	Deuter	00:04:45
12	Seah Jahan	Inside The Taj Mahal	Paul Horn	00:05:39
13	Silence 10 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:10
14	13 Angels Standing Guard 'Round The Side Of Your Bed	He Has Left Us Alone But Shafts Of Light Sometimes Grace The Corner Of Our Rooms	Silver Mt. Zion	00:07:22
15	Concerto for Lute, 2 Violins and Continuo in D, RV 93:2. Largo	Guitarrenkonzerte	Antonio Vivaldi	00:03:53
16	Wien	Fixed:: Content	Labradford	00:05:43
17	Silence 20 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:20
18	13. Depart and Eternity Theme Variation II	Eternity and a Day	Eleni Kalaindrou	00:06:50
19	Tides	Flying	Garth Stevenson	00:05:43
20	Silence 20 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:20
21	Wiegenlied	Storyteller	Richard Strauss	00:04:29
22	Silence 3 Minutes	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:03:00

Block 2d				
Track No	Track Name	Album Name	Artist Names	Duration
1	Prayer In Passing	Rise	Anoushka Shankar	00:06:21
2	Liberation: Moonlight; Introduction	The Lords of the Secrets	Homayoun Shajarian;Sohrab Pournazeri;Siavash Ensemble	00:08:09
3	Xomustar	Buura	Alash Ensemble	00:03:52
4	Mists Inhabit This Place	Mists Inhabit This Place	Brambles	00:03:50
5	Something Heavens	Ephemeris	H.U.V.A. Network	00:06:43
6	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks		00:08:00
7	Third	Third EP	Hiatus	00:04:46
8	Kraft des Meeres: Windharfe mit Meeresgeräuschen und Walgesängen; Pt. 1	Windharfe: Wohltuende Windspiele der Natur	Frank Tuppek	00:05:54
9	Blood of Earth	Blood of Earth	Deya Dova	00:03:50
10	Atair	La traversée	Armand Amar	00:06:28
11	Hovern' engan	Songs From a World Apart	Lévon Minassian	00:05:08
12	Them	Music for the Motion Picture Victoria	Nils Frahm	00:03:59
13	III. Mrs Dalloway: War Anthem	Three Worlds: Music From Woolf Works	Max Richter;Deutsches Filmorchester Babelsberg;Robert Ziegler;Hila Karni	00:06:56
14	Letters Of A Traveller	The Chopin Project	Ólafur Arnalds;Alice Sara Ott	00:04:17
15	Week No. 8	Autumn Stories 2019 (Remastered Version)	Fabrizio Paterlini	00:04:54
16	Feel First Life	Singularity	Jon Hopkins	00:05:33
17	Silence 2 Minutes	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:02:00

Block 2e				
Track No	Track Name	Album Name	Artist Names	Duration
1	Silence 1 Minute	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:01:00
2	Dissolving Clouds	Dropsonde	Biosphere	00:04:28
3	Silence 30 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:30
4	The Atomium Part 2	Avec Laudenum	Stars Of The Lid	00:10:43
5	Silence 30 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:30
6	Wurzel	Sonne und Wasser	H.Takahashi	00:07:23
7	Silence 30 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:30
8	Prizewinning	The Magic Place	Julianna Barwick	00:06:42
9	Silence 30 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:30
10	Letters Of A Traveller	The Chopin Project	Ólafur Arnalds;Alice Sara Ott	00:04:17
11	Silence 30 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:30
12	Purcell : Funeral Sentences for the death of Queen Mary II Z27 : I March	Purcell : Music for Queen Mary (Apex)	Henry Purcell;John Eliot Gardiner;Equale Brass Ensemble;Monteverdi Orchestra	00:02:17
13	Silence 30 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:30
14	Maggi's Flute - Mary's Watch; Pt. 2	Hearing Music	Joanna Brouk	00:04:41
15	Silence 30 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:30
16	Ataïr	La traversée	Armand Amar	00:06:28
17	Silence 30 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:30
18	Them	Music for the Motion Picture Victoria	Nils Frahm	00:03:59
19	Silence 30 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:30
20	Kraft des Meeres: Windharfe mit Meeresgeräuschen und Walgesängen; Pt. 1	Windharfe: Wohltuende Windspiele der Natur	Frank Tuppek	00:05:54
21	Silence 30 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:30
22	Cello Blue	Cello Blue	David Darling	00:08:11
23	Silence 30 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:30

24	Dream 3 - Short Edit	Sleep (Remixes)	Max Richter;Ben Russell;Yuki Numata Resnick	00:05:25
25	Silence 30 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:30
26	Indian Nights	OM Yoga Mix	Steve Gorn	00:11:26
27	Silence 30 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:30
28	Silence 1 Minute	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:01:00

Block 3a				
Track No	Track Name	Album Name	Artist Names	Duration
1	Silence 10 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:10
2	Part I	Chicago Waves	Carlos Nino	00:03:22
3	Aguas de Amazonia: Negro River	Philip Glass: Aguas de Amazonia	Philip Glass	00:04:22
4	Silence 10 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:10
5	Crystal Bowls And Aeolian Fingers	Poetry Without Words - Awakening the Anahata	Danny Becher	00:02:52
6	Root Chakra	Resonance Meditation	Beautiful Chorus	00:04:41
7	Silence 20 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:20
8	Saudade	Silencia	Hammock	00:05:18
9	Dawn	Book of Days	Meredith Monk	00:03:20
10	Silence 10 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:10
11	Jaran hailaas	Lieder aus dem mongolischen Grasland	Urna Chahartugchi;Tal Nutag	00:06:57
12	Silence 10 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:10
13	Verses	The Chopin Project	Ólafur Arnalds;Alice Sara Ott	00:04:03
14	Silence 10 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:10
15	I'm Going Home	Hosianna MantraInterstellar OST	Hans Zimmer	00:05:48
16	Silence 10 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:10
17	Spiegel im spiegel	Arvo Pärt: Portrait	Arvo Pärt;Angèle Dubeau;La Pietà	00:08:23
18	Silence 10 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:10
19	Der tod des cobra verde	Cobra verde (Original Motion Picture Soundtrack)	Popol Vuh	00:04:35
20	Abschied	Hosianna Mantra	Popol Vuh	00:03:14
21	Silence 20 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:20
22	Symphony No. 5 in C-Sharp Minor: IV. Adagietto	Mahler: Symphony No.5	Mahler, Barenboim, Chicago Symphony Orchestra	00:09:43
23	Silence 10 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:10

24	Baïlèro	Marie-Joseph Canteloube: Chants d'Auvergne et chants des Pays Basques	Joseph Canteloube; Maria Bayo; Orquesta Sinfonica De Tenerife; Victor Pablo Pérez	00:07:06
25	Silence 10 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:10
26	Sérénade No. 10 Gran Partita K.361; en Si Bémol Majeur: Sérénade No. 10 Gran Partita K.361; en Si Bémol Majeur: III. Adagio	Mozart: Gran Partita; Sérénade No. 12 Nacht Musique K. 388	Wolfgang Amadeus Mozart; Harmonie de l'Orchestre des Champs- Elysées; Philippe Herreweghe	00:05:15
27	Skies	The Tree of Life (Original Motion Picture Soundtrack)	Alexandre Desplat	00:05:18
28	Silence 20 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:20
29	Wayra (Dance of the Winds)	Virgin of the Sun God	Yma Sumac	00:03:01
30	Silence 6 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:06
31	Silence 6 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:06

Block 3b				
Track No	Track Name	Album Name	Artist Names	Duration
1	Silence 10 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:10
2	Verses	The Chopin Project	Ólafur Arnalds;Alice Sara Ott	00:04:03
3	Spiegel im spiegel	Arvo Pärt: Portrait	Arvo Pärt;Angèle Dubeau;La Pietà	00:08:23
4	Silence 30 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:30
5	Heart Sutra	Opening To Bliss	Wah!	00:07:32
6	Silence 10 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:10
7	Offering	The Essential	Ravi Shankar	00:09:44
8	Bailèro	Marie-Joseph Canteloube: Chants d'Auvergne et chants des Pays Basques	Joseph Canteloube;Maria Bayo;Orquesta Sinfonica De Tenerife;Victor Pablo Pérez	00:07:06
9	Silence 1 Minute	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:01:00
10	A Mystic Meandering	The Eternal Presence	Alan Tower	00:05:45
11	Silence 10 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:10
12	Dew Drops	Vortex	Pieter de Graaf	00:05:36
13	Galatea's Guitar	Dreams	Gábor Szabó	00:05:40
14	Silence 10 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:10
15	The Choice	Gustavo Santaollala, Alan Umstead	The Last of Us Part II (OST)	00:01:42
16	Silence 10 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:10
17	See Above, Sky Below	Ocean Songs	Dirty Three	00:06:04
18	Silence 1 Minute	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:01:00
19	Das Rosas	Tristeza on Guitar	Baden Powell	00:05:33
20	Silence 30 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:30
21	Maraba Blue	Cape Town Flowers	Abdullah Ibrahim	00:04:35
22	Silence 30 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:30
23	Piano Sonata No.3: Largo	The Chopin Project	Frédéric Chopin, Ólafur Arnalds;Alice Sara Ott	00:09:17
24	Silence 30 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:30

25	Sérénade No. 10 Gran Partita K.361; en Si Bémol Majeur: Sérénade No. 10 Gran Partita K.361; en Si Bémol Majeur: III. Adagio	Mozart: Gran Partita; Sérénade No. 12 Nacht Musique K. 388	Wolfgang Amadeus Mozart; Harmonie de l'Orchestre des Champs-Elysées; Philippe Herreweghe	00:05:15
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Block 3c				
TrackNo	Track Name	Album Name	Artist Names	Duration
1	Dance of the Tree Spirits	Parsons: Rainforest Dreaming	David Parsons	00:10:24
2	Mir	Patashnik	Biosphere	00:05:18
3	Photosynthesis	World of Sleepers	Carbon Based Lifeforms	00:06:48
4	Root Chakra	Resonance Meditation	Beautiful Chorus	00:04:41
5	The Swan	Impressions	Camille Saint-Saëns;Philippe Entremont;Gaby Casadesus;Yo-Yo Ma	00:03:05
6	Silence 10 Minutes	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:10:00
7	Natural Sounds	Nature Sounds	Nature Sounds Nature Music	00:09:18
8	Forest Falling Night	Healing Collection: Quiet Comfort	Takashi Kokubo	00:06:19
9	Jaran hailaas	Lieder aus dem mongolischen Grasland	Urna Chahartugchi;Tal Nutag	00:06:57
10	Mama Teaches Sanskrit	Sixteen Oceans	Four Tet	00:04:24
11	Flight From The City	Orphée	Jóhann Jóhannsson;Yuki Numata Resnick;Tarn Travers;Ben Russell;Clarice Jensen	00:06:31
12	The Mission: Gabriel's Oboe	Yo-Yo Ma Plays Ennio Morricone (Remastered)	Ennio Morricone;Yo-Yo Ma;Roma Sinfonietta	00:03:12
13	Secret Agent	Philip Glass: The Secret Agent	Philip Glass	00:04:51
14	Dream 2 (entropy) - Pt. 1	Sleep	Max Richter	00:02:20
15	Mamaké	Fasiya	Sona Jobarteh	00:05:08
16	Over There; It's Raining	Spaces	Nils Frahm	00:03:07

Block 3d				
Track No	Track Name	Album Name	Artist Names	Duration
1	Babbling Ocean	Babbling Ocean	Osmosis Flux	00:03:36
2	Silence 30 seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:30
3	Concertino bianco. 2: con venerazione	Georgs Pelecis	Into silence	00:06:25
4	Silence 30 seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:30
5	Words of Truth	The Garden of Mirrors	Stephan Micus	00:05:23
6	Antiphon, o quam mirabilis est	The Origen of Fire	Hildegard von Bingen	00:03:32
7	Barber: Adagio for Strings	Samuel Barber - Adagio	Samuel Barber, Sir Simon Rattle	00:08:57
8	Silence 30 seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:30
9	Der tod des cobra verde	Cobra verde (Original Motion Picture Soundtrack)	Popol Vuh	00:04:35
10	Skies	The Tree of Life (Original Motion Picture Soundtrack)	Alexandre Desplat	00:05:18
11	Silence 30 seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:30
12	Sarabande (from "Barry Lyndon")	Kubrick	The City of Prague Philharmonic Orchestra	00:04:10
13	On Earth As It Is In Heaven	The Mission: Music From The Motion Picture	Ennio Morricone	00:03:50
14	Silence 20 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:20
15	5 Stücke im Volkston. 1: Mit Humor	Roots	Robert Schumann, Martin Fröst	00:02:57
16	At the Mercy of Waves	Evidence of intense Beauty	Clem Leek	00:05:00
17	Silence 30 seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:30
18	Haja o que houver	O Paraiso	Madredeus	00:04:34
19	Oscarine	Chamber Music	Ballake Sissoko	00:05:41
20	Silence 30 seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:30
21	Nana	Jardim	Rainer Scheurenbrand	00:07:21
22	Amazon River	Aguas da Amazonia	Philip Glass	00:07:25
23	A Mystic Meandering	The Eternal Presence	Alan Tower	00:05:45

Block 3e				
Track No	Track Name	Album Name	Artist Names	Duration
1	Silence 10 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:10
2	Root Chakra	Resonance Meditation	Beautiful Chorus	00:04:41
3	Mir	Patashnik	Biosphere	00:05:18
4	Heart Sutra	Opening To Bliss	Wah!	00:07:32
5	Verses	The Chopin Project	Ólafur Arnalds;Alice Sara Ott	00:04:03
6	Jaran hailaas	Lieder aus dem mongolischen Grasland	Urna Chahartugchi;Tal Nutag	00:06:57
7	Silence 5 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:05
8	Bailèro	Marie-Joseph Canteloube: Chants d'Auvergne et chants des Pays Basques	Joseph Canteloube;Maria Bayo;Orquesta Sinfonica De Tenerife;Victor Pablo Pérez	00:07:06
9	Spiegel im spiegel	Arvo Pärt: Portrait	Arvo Pärt;Angèle Dubeau;La Pietà	00:08:23
10	Saudade	Silencia	Hammock	00:05:18
11	Der tod des cobra verde	Cobra verde (Original Motion Picture Soundtrack)	Popol Vuh	00:04:35
12	Dream 2 (entropy) - Pt. 1	Sleep	Max Richter	00:02:20
13	Silence 6 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:06
14	Sérénade No. 10 Gran Partita K.361; en Si Bémol Majeur: Sérénade No. 10 Gran Partita K.361; en Si Bémol Majeur: III. Adagio	Mozart: Gran Partita; Sérénade No. 12 Nacht Musique K. 388	Wolfgang Amadeus Mozart;Harmonie de l'Orchestre des Champs-Elysées;Philippe Herreweghe	00:05:15
15	The Swan	Impressions	Camille Saint-Saëns;Philippe Entremont;Gaby Casadesus;Yo-Yo Ma	00:03:05
16	Symphony No.6 In F; Op.68 -Pastoral: 2. Szene am Bach: (Andante molto mosso)	Beethoven: Symphony No.6 Pastorale; Choral Fantasy; Calm Sea and Prosperous Voyage	Ludwig van Beethoven;Wiener Philharmoniker;Claudio Abbado	00:12:25
17	Natural Sounds	Nature Sounds	Nature Sounds Nature Music	00:04:12
18	Skies	The Tree of Life (Original Motion Picture Soundtrack)	Alexandre Desplat	00:05:18
19	Silence 5 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:05

20	Wayra (Dance of the Winds)	Virgin of the Sun God	Yma Sumac	00:03:01
21	Silence 5 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:05

Block 4a				
Track No	Track Name	Album Name	Artist Names	Duration
1	Silence 10 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:10
2	I skyn	Diagonal Musik	Prins Emanuel	00:03:29
3	Regreso Del Pastor	La Humilde	Atahualpa Yupanqui	00:03:16
4	Guitar Solo, No. 6	Dead Man: A Film By Jim Jarmusch	Neil Young	00:03:22
5	Under an Ancient Sky	Under an Ancient Sky	Coyote Oldman	00:06:28
6	Silence 10 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:10
7	Cumulonimbus - Pt. 1	Sleep	Max Richter	00:03:20
8	Cumulonimbus - Pt. 2	Sleep	Max Richter	00:06:48
9	Silence 10 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:10
10	Suite bergamasque; L. 75: 3. Clair de lune	Debussy	Claude Debussy; Seong-Jin Cho	00:05:30
11	Silence 10 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:10
12	L'enfance	La Double vie de Véronique (Original Film Soundtrack)	Zbigniew Preisner	00:03:11
13	Only in Sleep	There Will Come Soft Rains	Āriks Ešņvalds;The Pacific Lutheran Choir Of The West;Richard Nance	00:05:31
14	Silence 10 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:10
15	Opening (from Glassworks)	Philip Glass: Escape	Gerard Cousins, Philip Glass	00:05:06
16	Dudamel: Let the Children Play - Sarabande (Based on a Theme by George Frideric Handel)	Embrace of the Serpent (Original Motion Picture Soundtrack)	Nascuy Linares	00:02:02
17	Silence 10 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:10
18	San Luis Obispo	Press Enter (with Luques Curtis & Kendrick Scott)	Romain Collin;Luques Curtis;Kendrick Scott	00:03:27
19	Silence 10 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:10
20	Le Chant Des Fauves	The Radio Tisdas Sessions	Tinariwen	00:07:32
21	Peace Piece	Life	Bill Evans;Igor Levit	00:06:13
22	Love - Remastered 2010	Plastic Ono Band	John Lennon	00:03:22
23	Silence 10 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:10
24	Meditation No.1	Ambient 3: Day of Radiance	Laraaji	00:18:47

25	Silence 2 Minutes	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:02:00
26	Ocean Waves	Ocean Waves (Alpha Relaxation Solution)	Dr. Jeffrey Thompson	01:00:09

Block 4b				
Track No	Track Name	Album Name	Artist Names	Duration
1	Dudamel: Let the Children Play - Sarabande (Based on a Theme by George Frideric Handel)	Embrace of the Serpent (Original Motion Picture Soundtrack)	Nascuy Linares	00:02:02
2	Silence 1 Minute	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:01:00
3	Regreso Del Pastor	La Humilde	Atahualpa Yupanqui	00:03:16
4	Suite bergamasque; L. 75: 3. Clair de lune	Work From Home With Piano Music	Claude Debussy; Alice Sara Ott	00:04:54
5	Silence 1 Minute	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:01:00
6	Cumulonimbus - Pt. 1	Sleep	Max Richter	00:03:20
7	Cumulonimbus - Pt. 2	Sleep	Max Richter	00:06:48
8	Silence 1 Minute	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:01:00
9	The Trial of Ed Crane	The Man Who Wasn't There - OST	Carter Burwell	00:03:52
10	Pretty in Plums	Homes	Shida Shahabi.	00:04:40
11	Silence 1 Minute	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:01:00
12	A Shimmer	Empty	Nils Frahm	00:06:36
13	San Luis Obispo	Press Enter (with Luques Curtis & Kendrick Scott)	Romain Collin; Luques Curtis; Kendrick Scott	00:03:27
14	Silence 1 Minute	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:01:00
15	Le Chant Des Fauves	The Radio Tisdas Sessions	Tinariwen	00:07:32
16	Abend Spat	Filmmusik	Hubert von Goisern	00:07:52
17	Silence 1 Minute	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:01:00
18	Canção verdes anos	Guitarra portuguesa	Carlos Paredes	00:03:06
19	New York - Mad Rush			00:06:23
20	Silence 1 Minute	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:01:00
21	Peace Piece	Life	Bill Evans; Igor Levit	00:06:13
22	Bridge over Troubled Water	The Don Shirley Point Of View	Don Shirley	00:06:50
23	Silence 1 Minute	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:01:00
24	Here Comes the Sun	Here Comes the Sun (Expanded Edition)	Nina Simone	00:03:34
25	Silence 2 minutes	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:02:00

26	Ocean Waves	Ocean Waves (Alpha Relaxation Solution)	Dr. Jeffrey Thompson	01:00:09
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Block 4c				
Track No	Track Name	Album Name	Artist Names	Duration
1	Under an Ancient Sky	Under an Ancient Sky	Coyote Oldman	00:06:28
2	Soft Meditation Rain	Soft Rain	Yoga Rain	00:02:49
3	Silence 20 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:20
4	Gottes Zeit ist die allerbeste Zeit	Kurtag, Bach	J. S. Bach	00:02:18
5	Silence 20 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:20
6	El pequeno zorro colorado	El Libro de los arboles magicos	Federico Durand	00:05:11
7	Silence 20 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:20
8	L'enfance	La Double vie de Véronique (Original Film Soundtrack)	Zbigniew Preisner	00:03:11
9	The Rising	As I return	Essie Jain	00:09:32
10	Silence 20 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:20
11	All in the Past	Roots	Georgs Pelecis	00:02:56
12	Bird's Lament	Sax Pax for a Sax	Moondog	00:02:03
13	Le Chant Des Fauves	The Radio Tisdas Sessions	Tinariwen	00:07:32
14	Sol Lua Estrela	Pé Com Pé; Vol. 1	Palavra Cantada	00:02:23
15	Silence 20 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:20
16	I skyn	Diagonal Musik	Prins Emanuel	00:03:29
17	Silence 50 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:50
18	Symphony No. 9 in E minor Op. 95 "From the New World". 2. Largo	Dvorak, Symphony No. 9	Antonin Dvorak, New York Philharmonic, Alan Gilbert	00:12:43
19	Silence 50 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:50
20	Cumulonimbus - Pt. 1	Sleep	Max Richter	00:03:20
21	Cumulonimbus - Pt. 2	Sleep	Max Richter	00:06:48
22	Silence 20 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:20
23	Dudamel: Let the Children Play - Sarabande (Based on a Theme by George Frideric Handel)	Embrace of the Serpent (Original Motion Picture Soundtrack)	Nascuy Linares	00:02:02
24	Abend Spat	Filmmusik	Hubert von Goisern	00:07:53
25	Don't Think Twice, it's alright	The First 10 Years	Joan Baez	00:03:09

26	Silence 2 Minutes	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:02:00
27	Ocean Waves	Ocean Waves (Alpha Relaxation Solution)	Dr. Jeffrey Thompson	01:00:00

Block 4d				
TrackNo	TrackName	AlbumName	ArtistNames	Duration
1	I skyn	Diagonal Musik	Prins Emanuel	00:03:29
2	Ténèbres	Absinthe	Dominic Miller	00:04:22
3	L'enfance	La Double vie de Véronique (Original Film Soundtrack)	Zbigniew Preisner	00:03:11
4	Cumulonimbus - Pt. 1	Sleep	Max Richter	00:03:20
5	Cumulonimbus - Pt. 2	Sleep	Max Richter	00:06:48
6	Bus Ride to Gulu	equilibrium	Pete Kuzma	00:06:28
7	You want it darker	You want it darker	Leonard Cohen	00:04:44
8	Only in Sleep	There Will Come Soft Rains	Þriks Ešenvalds;The Pacific Lutheran Choir Of The West;Richard Nance	00:05:31
9	Rêverie; L. 68 (Arr. Badzura)	Classical Legends: Debussy	Claude Debussy;Daniel Hope;Zürcher Kammerorchester	00:06:08
10	Divinire	Islands-Essential einaudi	Ludovico Einaudi	00:06:42
11	Mere Gurudev	Door of Faith	Krishna Das	00:05:36
12	Gnossienne No.1 (Arr. Kleynjans)	Work From Home With Satie	Erik Satie;Kaori Muraji	00:03:40
13	A Shimmer	Empty	Nils Frahm	00:06:36
14	Halving the Compass	Eingya	Helios	00:05:26
15	Naturaleza (Mose Edit)	Naturaleza (Mose Edit)	Danit;Mose	00:07:25
16	El pequeno zorro colorado	El libro de los Arboles Magicos	Federico Durand	00:05:11
17	Translucent Shadows	Under an Ancient Sky	Coyote Oldman	00:06:00
18	Silence 2 minutes			00:02:00
19	Ocean Waves			01:00:09

Block 4e				
Track No	Track Name	Album Name	Artist Names	Duration
1	Silence 20 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:20
2	Suite bergamasque; L. 75: 3. Clair de lune	Work From Home With Piano Music	Claude Debussy; Alice Sara Ott	00:04:54
3	Silence 1 Minute	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:01:00
4	Regreso Del Pastor	La Humilde	Atahualpa Yupanqui	00:03:16
5	Silence 2 Minutes	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:02:00
6	San Luis Obispo	Press Enter (with Luques Curtis & Kendrick Scott)	Romain Collin; Luques Curtis; Kendrick Scott	00:03:27
7	Silence 30 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:30
8	I skyn	Diagonal Musik	Prins Emanuel	00:03:29
9	Silence 10 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:10
10	L'enfance	La Double vie de Véronique (Original Film Soundtrack)	Zbigniew Preisner	00:03:11
11	Dudamel: Let the Children Play - Sarabande (Based on a Theme by George Frideric Handel)	Embrace of the Serpent (Original Motion Picture Soundtrack)	Nascuy Linares	00:02:02
12	Silence 1 Minute	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:01:00
13	A Shimmer	Empty	Nils Frahm	00:06:36
14	Silence 30 Seconds	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:00:30
15	Rêverie; L. 68 (Arr. Badzura)	Classical Legends: Debussy	Claude Debussy; Daniel Hope; Zürcher Kammerorchester	00:06:08
16	Silence 2 Minutes	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:02:00
17	Cumulonimbus - Pt. 1	Sleep	Max Richter	00:03:20
18	Cumulonimbus - Pt. 2	Sleep	Max Richter	00:06:48
19	Silence 1 Minute	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:01:00
20	Thaïs / Acte Deux: Méditation	Méditation - The Beautiful Music Of Massenet	Jules Massenet; Nigel Kennedy; National Philharmonic Orchestra; Richard Bonyngue	00:05:42
21	Silence 1 Minute	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:01:00

22	Only in Sleep	There Will Come Soft Rains	Þriks Ešenvalds;The Pacific Lutheran Choir Of The West;Richard Nance	00:05:31
23	Silence 1 Minute	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:01:00
24	Le Chant Des Fauves	The Radio Tisdas Sessions	Tinariwen	00:07:32
25	Silence 1 Minute	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:01:00
26	Peace Piece	Life	Bill Evans;Igor Levit	00:06:13
27	Silence 1 Minute	Silence	Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:01:00
28	Bridge over Troubled Water	The Don Shirley Point Of View	Don Shirley	00:06:50
29	Silence 2 Minutes		Silent Meditation; No Sound Pause Breaks	00:02:00
30	Ocean Waves	Ocean Waves (Alpha Relaxation Solution)	Dr. Jeffrey Thompson	01:00:09

Appendix R: Music Playlists – Spotify Links

Music Playlists – Spotify Links

- 1a <https://open.spotify.com/playlist/5vJ0oYfHvT7bbJJajqxwBy?si=d9cfee269b97434d>
- 1b <https://open.spotify.com/playlist/6mBV2oL0pfWm7zmZ8mrOIC?si=a73fbc5124b64183>
- 1c <https://open.spotify.com/playlist/6RIZxYtu3XeZ7ele97SnnW?si=6f54206268754669>
- 1d <https://open.spotify.com/playlist/782JFAyBP5KK3nKAPJDqQv?si=5778069187904c95>
- 1e <https://open.spotify.com/playlist/1MF3Z9V0ojhIbRNdC6cbmj?si=e47b19e986da4380>

- 2a <https://open.spotify.com/playlist/3Kci3dZKyRgXgzpW9Tw0fB?si=92be4dd5f72149c6>
- 2b <https://open.spotify.com/playlist/5PMGISZFwTzUdUHXsSyUZ2?si=fddddd3a871a9444b>
- 2c <https://open.spotify.com/playlist/0IZpzJTgp5MhqN2317bKdU?si=a1da4e77cdd64d80>
- 2d <https://open.spotify.com/playlist/0v78dT7pAhwYHXIlmdsJNS?si=3172f002836648b9>
- 2e <https://open.spotify.com/playlist/3MhiFSPnftlwOrUDkdAcCL?si=46b1ed92e5e3457b>

- 3a <https://open.spotify.com/playlist/7gfwVv2QAn0VYFz33iyaYB?si=a008af8c2d624596>
- 3b <https://open.spotify.com/playlist/3dq9bJJZmPRH9tJsQAHR9b?si=7d7bba7c14e64c89>
- 3c <https://open.spotify.com/playlist/0SZ1wXlsRqMU2tZ7U64FO0?si=624576ad435840d6>
- 3d <https://open.spotify.com/playlist/34y3Pq37YjAFiF9VjBGYfs?si=c11fa5852fc64a84>
- 3e <https://open.spotify.com/playlist/2fuxjaiXCfyV0y5GUP5hix?si=bc3fcbd266fc4f43>

- 4a <https://open.spotify.com/playlist/3yDEYKwyEvOY9YDb5WkzOs?si=849b212d3dde41eb>
- 4b <https://open.spotify.com/playlist/5RtS6p8joqvqPFzKkwIjZP?si=87e2d6e229f5468e>
- 4c <https://open.spotify.com/playlist/2ImVMcuENBGUUs31vilw5j?si=122917136c614971>
- 4d <https://open.spotify.com/playlist/OSFtGjWGyeehshJILL9iML?si=48a6e7ef9acb46de>
- 4e <https://open.spotify.com/playlist/2BYaAYuihSHREtsEfp3Gxn?si=4d5ea4f65a804595>

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